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**RETROELEMENTS-DRIVEN REGULATORY EVOLUTION OF
HUMAN GENES AND MOLECULAR PROCESSES: ANALYSIS
OF GENOME BINDING PROFILES OF TRANSCRIPTION
FACTORS AND HISTONE MODIFICATIONS**

T H E S I S

Submitted for the Degree
of Candidate of Biological Sciences (PhD)
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Nothing in biology makes sense except in the
light of evolution - *Theodosius Dobzhansky*
(Dobzhansky, 1973)

Nothing in evolution makes sense except in the
light of parasitism - *Hickinbotham, Stepney*
and Hogeweg (Hickinbotham et al., 2021)

DEDICATION

To my beloved wife, Irina Nikitina.

For eight years, your love, support, and acceptance have been my constant inspiration, encouraging me to delve ever deeper into the mysteries of life—especially into the evolution of complex molecular machineries and the endless struggle between genomic parasites and their hosts.

Our own story began at a ball, wrapped in the elegance of a 19th-century setting. Since that moment, we have faced every challenge as one: the difficulties of relocating to Armenia with our two young sons, the youngest only two months old; the trials of illness and injury. Together, we have climbed the highest mountains and explored the deepest underwater caverns. You have listened to every nascent idea and celebrated the completion of each section of this work as a shared victory.

This thesis would not exist without you. It is as much a testament to your love and perseverance as it is to any effort of my own.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABBREVIATIONS

AMP - adenosinemonophosphate

AMPK - AMP-activated protein kinase
ASP - antisense promoter
ATAC-seq - assay for transposase-accessible chromatin using sequencing
CAGE - cap analysis of gene expression
CNE - constructive neutral evolution
CNN - convolutional neural network
CRISPR - clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeat
CRISPRa - CRISPR activation
CRISPRi - CRISPR interference
ChIP-seq - chromatin immunoprecipitation and sequencing
DNMT - DNA methyltransferase
EGFR - epidermal growth factor receptor
EM - expectation-maximization
ERV - endogenous retrovirus
ESCs - embryonic stem cells
FDR - false discovery rate
FOLR - folate receptor
GAG - glycosaminoglycane
GO - gene ontology
GPCR - G-protein-coupled receptor
GRE - gene RE-linked regulatory elements enrichment score
GTE - gene total regulatory enrichment score
GWAS - genome-wide association study
HDAC - histone deacetylase
HERV – human endogenous retrovirus
HMM - hidden Markov model
HSRE - high-site recurrence element
HUSH - human silencing hub
IDR - irreproducible discovery rate
IGF1R - insulin-like growth factor 1 receptor
KAT - lysine acetyltransferase
KMT - lysine methyltransferase
KRAB-ZFPs - KRAB zinc finger proteins
LAD - lamina-associated domain
LECA - last universal eukaryotic ancestor
LINE - long interspersed nuclear element
LTR - long terminal repeat
LUCA - last universal common ancestor
MAP - microtubule associated protein
MIR - mammalian-wide interspersed repeat
MSA - multiple sequence alignment
MSK - mitogen- and stress-activated protein kinase
NAD - nucleolus-associated domain
NAHR - non-allelic homologous recombination

NGRE - normalized gene RE-linked regulatory elements enrichment score
NHEJ - non-homologous end joining
NK - natural killer
NPPI - normalized pathway involvement index
OR - olfactory receptor
ORF - open reading frame
PCA - principal component analysis
PDGF - platelet-derived growth factor
PGI - pathway gene-based index
PII - pathway involvement index
PKA - protein kinase A
PP - protein phosphatase
PRMT - protein arginine methyltransferase
PSM - plant secondary metabolite
RE - retroelement, retrotransposon
RIG - repeat-induced gene silencing
RIP - repeat-induced point mutation
RNAi - RNA interference
RNP - ribonucleoprotein
RT - reverse transcriptase
SE - super-enhancer
SED - super-enhancer domain
SGE - selfish genetic element
SINE - short interspersed nuclear element
SP - sense promoter
SPDS - spermidine synthase
SPMS - spermine synthase
SRP - signal recognition particle
SV - structural variant
T2T - telomere-to-telomere
TAD - topologically associating domain
TBP - TATA-binding protein
TF - transcription factor
TFBS - transcription factor binding site
TGF- β - transforming growth factor beta
TLR - Toll-like receptors
TME - tumor microenvironment
TPRT - target-primed reverse transcription
TSS - transcription start site
TTS - the total number of reads mapped to the TSS 10 kb neighborhood
UMAP - uniform manifold approximation and projection
UPS - ubiquitin-proteasome system
UTR - untranslated region
WGS - whole genome sequencing

dsDNA - double-stranded DNA
dsRNA - double-stranded RNA
hiPSCs - human induced pluripotent stem cells
iPSCs - induced pluripotent stem cells
lncRNA - long non-coding RNA
mya - million years ago
ncRNA - non-coding RNA
piRNA - Piwi-interacting RNA
siRNA - small interfering RNA
snRNA - small nuclear RNA

INTRODUCTION

Across the major evolutionary transitions in the human lineage - including the emergence of cells, eukaryogenesis, multicellularity, the adaptive immune system, invasive placentation, and the complex neocortex - the emergence of increased biological complexity appears to have been driven by a dynamic interplay and evolutionary arms race between multilevel selfish genetic elements (SGEs) - such as viruses, endosymbionts, and transposons - and the host genome, thereby creating novel arenas for evolutionary innovation at higher levels of organization (Patten et al., 2023; Szathmáry & Smith, 1995). The cellular membrane and DNA synthesis could originate as a defense mechanism against primordial viruses in the RNA world (Forterre & Prangishvili, 2009), the eukaryotic nucleus and spliceosome originated from and because of massive invasion of self-splicing group 2 introns (Vosseberg & Snel, 2017), SGEs could drive primitive multicellular organisms towards germline and somatic sequestration (Johnson, 2008a), vertebrate adaptive immune system with VDJ-recombination developed from the two mutually interacting transposons (Yakovenko et al., 2021a), invasive hemochorial placenta, specific to humans and other great apes (Hominoidea) (Carter, 2021; Shimode, 2023), evolved because of endogenous retroviruses genes for cell fusion being domesticated and human neocortex is transcriptionally diversified because of controlled retrotransposons mobilizing (Garza et al., 2025) - the abundance of SGE-driven evolutionary breakthroughs supports the provocative hypothesis that the human phenotype - including its development, modeling, and pathological deviations - can be fully understood and effectively addressed only by considering the complex and often antagonistic interactions between the host genome and various classes of SGEs.

Initially elaborated by Richard Dawkins back in 1976 in the popular science book “The Selfish Gene” (Dawkins, 2006) and further developed in a series of groundbreaking evolutionary debates and studies (Dawkins & Carlisle, 1976; Dawkins & Krebs, 1979), the concept of the selfish genetic replicator remains a dominant paradigm within contemporary molecular biology and evolutionary research, coexisting with a pervasive adaptationist framework and an implicit, often unexamined, Panglossian assumption that evolution sculpts organisms as cohesive, optimally designed entities - akin to the work of an engineer or a deity (Gabora, 2013). The recognition of inherent genetic conflict within every genome (Koonin et al., 2021) - particularly within the complex and variable human genome - as a fundamental force shaping molecular processes and contributing to pathology is gradually advancing, driven by the accumulation of data and insights from evolutionary genomics facilitated by the rapid progress

of sequencing technologies (Kokoris et al., 2025). Arguably the most impactful, extensively studied, and economically significant domain within biotechnology - cancer research (Jovčevska et al., 2019; Shtam et al., 2019) - now broadly acknowledges the evolutionary arms race between malignant cells and the immune system (Fiore et al., 2025; Laukien, 2021; Sorokin et al., 2022). Moreover, although less widely recognized, there is growing acceptance of the view that carcinogenesis may represent a by-product of earlier evolutionary innovations in the human lineage (Casás-Selves & DeGregori, 2011). For instance, the capacity for metastasis has been linked to the highly invasive nature of the human placenta (Kz et al., 2019), a feature that emerged, in part, through the domestication of endogenous retroviral genes such as *syncytins* (Q. Wang et al., 2023). Despite significant advancements in targeted and general anticancer therapies, the emergence of resistant tumor clones remains a pervasive challenge (Tian et al., 2024). This phenomenon is intricately linked to the evolutionary dynamics within tumors, where therapeutic interventions impose selective pressures that favor the survival and proliferation of resistant subpopulations (Pressley et al., 2021). The tumor microenvironment (TME) further contributes to this complexity by influencing genetic drift and natural selection processes, thereby facilitating resistance development (de Visser & Joyce, 2023). Current biotechnological approaches have yet to fully overcome these adaptive mechanisms, underscoring the need for alternative strategies that account for the evolutionary nature of cancer (Tian et al., 2024). Apart from defeating cancer, arguably the most ambitious and long-lasting problem that requires complete understanding of the intragenomic genetic conflict is human genetic enhancement for interplanetary and even interstellar space missions and colonization, including the induced synthetic torpor (hibernation) (Shi et al., 2021) and radio resistance (Cortese et al., 2018), although significant ethical concerns remain (Szocik et al., 2021).

The current state of knowledge regarding the human molecular phenotype in both health and disease - including insights from cancer biology - highlights the critical importance of investigating the evolutionary arms race between the human genome and selfish genetic elements (SGEs). The human genome is not only structurally complex but also densely populated with SGEs; more than two-thirds of its sequence consists of repetitive elements of various classes (A. P. J. de Koning et al., 2011). Notably, retrotransposons, or retroelements (REs) - mobile genetic elements capable of reverse-transcribing their RNA into DNA and reintegrating it into the genome - constitute at least 40% of the total genomic content, illustrating the pervasive and enduring influence of SGEs on genome architecture and function

(Lander et al., 2001). Gene regulatory networks - modular systems underpinning the molecular and organismal complexity of the human body - are themselves shaped by an ongoing evolutionary arms race between SGEs and host genomic defense mechanisms (Werren, 2011). A paradigmatic example of such a defense mechanism is RNA interference (RNAi), which plays a crucial role in silencing repetitive genomic elements, particularly REs flanked by tandem repeats, thereby preserving regulatory integrity and genomic stability (Cornec & Poirier, 2023). The entirely new families of transcription factors evolved in primates to counteract the spreading REs, such as ZNF91/93 which evolved in response to expansion of the LINE (Long Interspersed Nuclear Element) L1PA3 subfamily and SINE (Long Interspersed Nuclear Element) related SVA elements (Jacobs et al., 2014). Conversely, RE often retain active promoters necessary for the expression of their own sequences, and these promoters frequently harbor transcription factor binding sites (TFBS) that can modulate the expression of nearby host genes at or near the sites of recent RE insertions (Göke & Ng, 2016; Hermant & Torres-Padilla, 2021). Indeed, the regulatory influence of REs is substantial: they contribute to approximately 44% of open chromatin regions in the human genome and up to 63% of those specific to primates (Jacques et al., 2013). These findings suggest that REs play an active role in the recent evolutionary remodeling of gene regulatory networks. Notably, as many as 80% of distinct human endogenous retrovirus (HERV) subfamilies are enriched within open chromatin regions (Jacques et al., 2013), further underscoring their potential contribution to transcriptional regulation. Although the increasing availability of omics datasets has begun to facilitate evolutionary investigations into the regulatory roles of REs (Satam et al., 2023), this area of research remains relatively understudied and warrants further systematic exploration (Ali et al., 2021). The imperative for systematic, omics-driven investigations into the regulatory influence of REs on host gene expression is further supported by evidence that REs - in particular HERVs - are frequently reactivated in cancer, where they contribute to pro-inflammatory responses and the aberrant induction of gene regulatory programs typically associated with embryogenesis (Jansz & Faulkner, 2021).

The purpose of the study.

This study sought to elucidate the regulatory influence of human REs on host gene expression, with a specific focus on their interactions with transcription factor binding and histone modification patterns.

The research objectives are:

1. To compile comprehensive genome-wide epigenetic profiles - including transcription factor binding and histone modification data representing both euchromatin and heterochromatin functional states - across multiple human cell lines using publicly available datasets.
2. To investigate the regulatory influence of REs across different evolutionary timescales as a proof of concept, through analysis of transcription factor binding profiles within a single representative cell line.
3. To develop a novel computational method for assessing RE-associated regulatory influence, based on the genome proximity of epigenetic tags and REs to transcription start sites (TSS) of human genes.
4. To apply the developed methodology to transcription factor binding profiles across multiple cell lines to examine the evolutionary dynamics of RE-associated regulatory activity, with the aim of identifying genes and molecular pathways subjected to high levels of RE-mediated regulatory input and accelerated regulatory evolution.
5. To evaluate the regulatory effects of REs in diverse cellular contexts by analyzing the enrichment of activating and repressive histone modifications in relation to REs across multiple cell lines.
6. To integrate analyses of activating and repressive chromatin marks using the established computational framework, in order to identify consensus gene sets that are preferentially activated by REs while remaining largely unaffected by RE-associated heterochromatinization.

Scientific and practical significance of the results. As previously noted, REs contribute to approximately 44% of open chromatin regions in the human genome, including up to 63% of regions that are primate-specific (Jacques et al., 2013). This extensive regulatory landscape exemplifies the functional significance of REs, which influence key biological processes - such as immune system function, germline development, and tumorigenesis - by supplying cis-regulatory elements embedded within their sequences (Ali et al., 2021; Jansz & Faulkner, 2021). For instance, the reactivation of REs following MED12 silencing in pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma has been shown to trigger the type I interferon signaling pathway, resulting in a highly inflamed tumor microenvironment (TME) that enhances the tumor's sensitivity to immunotherapeutic interventions (Tang et al., 2024). This example highlights the critical need for further investigation into the epigenetic and regulatory evolutionary roles of REs in shaping human molecular processes.

To systematically examine the regulatory contributions of REs to human molecular pathways, we first compiled genome-wide binding profiles for 225 transcription factors in the K562 human cell line using data from the ENCODE consortium (E. P. Consortium, 2004). This dataset included approximately 2 million TFBS overlapping with REs located within 5 kilobases of gene TSS both upstream and downstream, thereby representing a set of REs with potential regulatory competence (Nikitin et al., 2018). Through computational analysis of the relative enrichment of RE-associated TFBS near TSS regions, we identified several biological processes exhibiting substantial regulatory influence from REs. These processes included immune and pathogen response, negative regulation of transcription, ubiquitination and proteasomal degradation, extracellular matrix organization, regulation of STAT signaling, fatty acid metabolism, GTPase activity modulation, protein trafficking to the Golgi apparatus, cell division and differentiation, as well as the development and function of sensory and reproductive systems. We further investigated these pathways with a focus on evolutionarily recent RE subfamilies, specifically those that emerged following the radiation of Old World monkeys (Nikitin et al., 2018).

Building upon the proof-of-concept analysis conducted in a single cell line (Nikitin et al., 2018), we developed and formalized a computational framework for quantifying the regulatory influence of REs, which we termed RetroSpect. This methodology was subsequently applied to a larger dataset comprising binding profiles of 563 transcription factors across 13 distinct human cell lines. Using this framework, we computed both absolute and relative RE-associated regulatory enrichment scores for 24,389 protein-coding genes and 3,124 molecular pathways, enabling a systematic evaluation of RE-linked contributions to gene regulation across diverse cellular contexts (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019). The key biological processes exhibiting significant enrichment of RE-associated regulatory input - indicative of an accelerated rate of regulatory evolution - include microRNA (Zottel et al., 2020) mediated gene regulation, olfactory and color vision pathways, fertilization mechanisms, cellular immune responses, as well as metabolic pathways involved in amino acid and fatty acid processing and detoxification. In contrast, evolutionarily conserved processes that demonstrated minimal RE-linked regulatory enrichment were predominantly associated with core cellular functions, such as translation, RNA transcription and processing, chromatin organization, and fundamental molecular signaling pathways (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019). These results demonstrate the robustness and scalability of the RetroSpect framework for analyzing large-scale epigenomic datasets, while also providing novel insights

into the extent and specificity of RE-associated regulatory influence on host gene expression at the consensus level across multiple human cell lines.

Following the transcription factor analysis, we extended the application of the RetroSpect framework to a combined epigenomic dataset encompassing six key histone modifications - H3K4me1, H3K4me3, H3K9ac, H3K27ac, H3K27me3, and H3K9me3 - across five human cell lines (Igolkina et al., 2019; Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019). By leveraging whole-genome binding profiles of both activating (H3K4me1, H3K4me3, H3K9ac, H3K27ac) and repressive (H3K27me3, H3K9me3) chromatin marks, we validated the hypothesis that RE-enriched and RE-depleted biological processes exhibit coordinated regulatory evolution contingent upon the chromatin state. Specifically, rapidly evolving processes were characterized by enrichment of RE-linked activating histone modifications within the 10 kb regions flanking TSS, coupled with depletion of RE-associated repressive marks, suggesting selective evasion of RE heterochromatinization. Conversely, evolutionarily conserved processes were predominantly associated with RE-linked repressive chromatin and showed a marked absence of activating RE-derived regulatory signals.

In a recent integrative analysis of the same six histone modifications across the five cell lines, we further refined this approach to identify pathways simultaneously marked by RE-linked enhancer (H3K4me1, H3K27ac) or promoter (H3K4me3, H3K9ac) activity and depleted of RE-associated heterochromatin, highlighting candidate gene sets under selective regulatory innovation. This consensus analysis revealed a strong association of such regulatory patterns with molecular pathways implicated in cancer progression - notably chronic myeloid leukemia and small cell lung cancer - as well as in innate immune responses to human T-cell lymphotropic virus type 1 (HTLV-1) infection (Nikitin, 2025).

Approbation. The RetroSpect computation approach with the code and supplementary data was uploaded to the public GitHub repository accessible via the link https://github.com/Nikit357/supplementary_RetroSpect. The gene-level scores of regulatory RE impact at the level of 6 chromatin modifications derived by the RetroSpect method are uploaded and publicly available as supplementary materials attached to the articles (Igolkina et al., 2019; Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019). Both gene-level and molecular pathway-level scores of regulatory RE impact aggregated by whole genome binding profiles of 563 transcription factors in 13 human cell lines are also uploaded and publicly available as supplementary materials attached to the article (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019).

Publications. The main results of the dissertation are published in 5 academic papers.

Structure. This dissertation comprises 271 pages of computer-formatted English text, including 21 tables and 58 figures, consisting of the following sections: Introduction, Literature Review, Materials and Methods, Results and Discussion, Conclusion, References (including 662 sources).

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1. Overview of major evolutionary transitions impacted by SGEs

Major evolutionary transitions is a cornerstone concept introduced by John Maynard Smith and Eörs Szathmáry in their groundbreaking 1995 book and the review article (SMITH, 1995; Szathmáry & Smith, 1995) in order to explain the origin of several radical increases in cellular and organismal complexity that cannot be theoretically explained based on the Modern Synthesis theory and the widespread Panglossian adaptationism (Huxley, 1942) (Table 1).

Table 1. Major evolutionary transitions by John Maynard Smith and Eörs Szathmáry according to (SMITH, 1995).

Transition from	Transition to
Replicating molecules	"Populations" of molecules in compartments
Independent replicators (probably RNA)	Chromosomes
RNA as both genes and enzymes	DNA as genes; proteins as enzymes
Prokaryotes	Eukaryotes
Asexual clones	Sexual populations
Protists	Multicellular organisms - animals, plants, fungi
Solitary individuals	Colonies with non-reproductive castes
Primate societies	Human societies with language, enabling memes

Maynard Smith and Szathmary (SMITH, 1995) delineated several recurring features characterizing these major evolutionary transitions:

1. Smaller units frequently associate to form more complex, higher-level entities, as exemplified by the emergence of chromosomes, eukaryotic cells, sexual reproduction, and multicellular assemblages.
2. Within these larger entities, the constituent units often become functionally specialized, as seen in the division of roles among DNA and proteins, the evolution of organelles, the differentiation of gametes (anisogamy), tissue formation, and the development of castes in eusocial systems.
3. These subordinate units typically lose the capacity for independent replication, becoming reliant on the integrity and continuity of the larger organizational structure - examples include chromosomes, organelles, tissues, and social castes.
4. Conflicts may arise when lower-level units act in ways that are detrimental to the higher-level organization, manifesting in phenomena such as meiotic drive, parthenogenesis, oncogenesis, and sociopolitical subversion (e.g., coup d'etats).
5. Each transition is often accompanied by the evolution of novel mechanisms for information transmission and inheritance, including the DNA - protein system, cellular heredity, epigenetic regulation, and complex communication systems such as universal grammar.

Despite the shared characteristics observed across major evolutionary transitions, formulating a unified conceptual framework that accounts for all such events remains profoundly challenging (Szathmary, 2015). The development of a comprehensive and predictive quantitative theory is even more elusive (Szathmary, 2015). At a qualitative level of causal analysis, the most compelling current explanation for major evolutionary transitions is the evolutionary arms race between host genomes and SGEs, a hypothesis supported by evidence from comparative genomics and mathematical modeling (Figure 1, (Koonin, 2016)). This theoretical perspective is further developed in the following subsections about the most significant evolutionary transitions in human lineage and will serve as the central explanatory framework throughout the present study.

Figure 1. SGE-driven evolutionary transitions, adapted from (Koonin, 2016).

Among the alternative non-adaptationist perspectives, the Constructive Neutral Evolution (CNE) hypothesis warrants particular attention. This framework posits that molecular complexity can arise through the gradual accumulation of interactions between macromolecules, driven by the buffering of slightly deleterious mutations through emergent compensatory interactions, which subsequently become fixed within populations via genetic drift (Stoltzfus, 1999). When considered alongside the mutational burden imposed by SGEs,

this hypothesis offers a compelling account for the emergence of highly intricate molecular systems such as RNA editing, the spliceosome, and gene scrambling in ciliates (Muñoz-Gómez et al., 2021).

1.1.1. The origin of cells

Recent advances in paleobiochemical modeling suggest that the earliest RNA-like replicators likely originated within zinc-, potassium-, and sulfur-enriched surface geothermal vent systems (Mulkiđjanian, 2009; Mulkiđjanian et al., 2025). In these environments, abiogenic photosynthesis is hypothesized to have served as the principal source of both organic carbon and metabolic energy, while thermophoretic gradients within mineral microchannels provided the necessary physical conditions to drive the initial polymerization of biomolecules (Baaske et al., 2007). According to a hypothesis proposed by Armen Mulkiđjanian, such mineral-rich niches may have formed because of geochemical fallout following the Moon-forming giant impact event (Mulkiđjanian et al., 2025). It is further postulated that the earliest living systems were composed of consortia of RNA replicators and short peptides. Comparative proteomics and biochemical analyses - including the fundamental divergence in membrane lipid composition between Bacteria and Archaea - indicate that the ribosome predates both the emergence of lipid-bounded cell membranes and DNA-based replication machinery (Durzyńska & Goździcka-Józefiak, 2015; Koonin, 2009). These findings collectively suggest that the last universal common ancestor (LUCA) was not a discrete unicellular or colonial organism, but rather a pre-cellular network of molecular systems (Koonin, 2009). This raises the central question: by what mechanisms did the first cellular life forms arise?

The primordial virus world hypothesis offers an explanatory framework for the independent emergence of cellular membranes and DNA replication systems in Bacteria and Archaea. According to this model, an evolutionary arms race between cooperative and parasitic RNA-protein replicators - residing within mineral micropores that functioned as proto-compartments - drove key innovations prior to the advent of membrane-bound cells (Figure 2). Within this context, DNA is posited to have originated as a viral adaptation: a chemically modified derivative of RNA that conferred resistance against host-encoded defense mechanisms, analogous to the chemical modifications employed by contemporary viruses to evade immune surveillance (Forterre, 2005). Notably, the existence of early antiviral immune systems, such

as proto-Cas-like elements, is acknowledged even within the more conservative framework of the cellular LUCA hypothesis (Moody et al., 2024).

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the primordial virus world model in the context of precellular evolution, adapted from (Koonin, 2009). Key stages in the transition from molecular replicators to cellular life are depicted on the right. Wavy lines represent RNA-based genetic elements, while circular and oval shapes correspond to DNA molecules. Hexagonal symbols denote virus-like particles, with those enclosed within rounded rectangles indicating membrane-bound virions. DNA segments associated with archaeal-type replication machineries are highlighted in red, whereas those linked to bacterial-type replication systems are shown in blue. Membrane types follow the same color scheme, reflecting their corresponding replication systems. Arrows connecting various compartments signify horizontal gene transfer events, emphasizing the reticulate and dynamic nature of early genetic exchange during the precellular phase of evolution.

1.1.2. Eukaryogenesis

The evolutionary origin of eukaryotes has long posed a profound enigma, owing to the striking disparity in complexity between eukaryotic and prokaryotic cells (Booth & Doolittle, 2015). Eukaryotes exhibit not only significantly larger and more intricately organized genomes, but also complex membrane systems, a dynamic cytoskeleton, and endosymbiotic organelles (Booth & Doolittle, 2015; Dacks et al., 2016). Furthermore, their molecular machinery -

particularly the nuclear pore complexes (Petrovic et al., 2022) and the spliceosome apparatus (Valadkhan & Jaladat, 2010) - appears degenerately elaborate, lacking clear incremental functional advantages. For instance, the emergence of pre-mRNA splicing introduced a substantial energetic and temporal cost to gene expression, whereas the putative adaptive benefits of alternative splicing likely emerged only subsequently and thus could not have acted as an initial selective driver (Vosseberg & Snel, 2017). Given these features, any plausible model of eukaryogenesis must account for non-adaptive or even maladaptive evolutionary trajectories. In this context, the pervasive influence of SGEs offers a compelling explanatory framework, potentially resolving the longstanding puzzle of how such complex eukaryotic traits could have arisen.

The prevailing hypothesis posits that the Last Eukaryotic Common Ancestor (LECA), emerging during the early Proterozoic eon, originated from an Asgard archaeon (Krupovic et al., 2023). This ancestral archaeon exhibited complex cellular features, including a dynamic cytoskeleton, ubiquitin-mediated protein degradation pathways, and sophisticated membrane trafficking systems (Zaremba-Niedzwiedzka et al., 2017). These attributes likely facilitated the endosymbiotic incorporation of an alphaproteobacterial progenitor, culminating in the formation of mitochondria (McInerney et al., 2014). An alternative model suggests that a deltaproteobacterial endosymbiosis with an Asgard archaeon preceded mitochondrial acquisition, potentially contributing to early eukaryotic complexity (López-García & Moreira, 2020).

Irrespective of the specific endosymbiotic sequence, the alphaproteobacterial genome introduced group II self-splicing introns into the host archaeal genome through horizontal gene transfer (Zimmerly & Semper, 2015). These mobile genetic elements encode reverse transcriptase (RT), endonuclease and maturase activities, enabling them to excise themselves from RNA transcripts and integrate into new genomic loci via target-primed reverse transcription (Zimmerly & Semper, 2015). The absence of robust defense mechanisms and the limited population size of the host archaeon may have facilitated the proliferation of these introns, leading to a high intron density within coding regions (4.3 copies per 1 kbp of coding sequence in LECA) (Csuros et al., 2011). The domestication of group II introns is hypothesized to have driven the evolution of key eukaryotic molecular machineries, such as spliceosome and telomerase that evolved directly from their proteins and/or non-coding RNA (Vosseberg & Snel, 2017). These innovations may have necessitated the compartmentalization of transcription and translation processes, leading to the development of the nucleus, and spurred the emergence of RNA surveillance mechanisms such as nonsense-mediated decay and RNAi

(Koonin, 2006) (Figure 3). Furthermore, human LINEs, active REs which constitute approximately 17% of the human genome, share significant homology in their RT domains with those of group II introns (Stamos et al., 2017). This homology supports the hypothesis that LINEs originated from ancestral group II introns, underscoring the profound impact of these elements on eukaryotic genome evolution.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the hypothesized causal sequence underlying eukaryogenesis, with particular emphasis on mitochondrial endosymbiosis and the concurrent invasion of spliceosomal introns, adapted from (Koonin, 2006). Arrows denote the inferred causal relationships and putative selective pressures.

1.1.3. The origin of animal multicellularity

In contrast to the singular origin of eukaryotic cells, multicellularity has arisen independently across a diverse array of evolutionary lineages (Ruiz-Trillo et al., 2007). Of particular relevance is the emergence of multicellular animals. According to the prevailing consensus, the earliest metazoans originated from choanoflagellate-like, facultatively colonial organisms within the Holozoa clade approximately 800 to 650 million years ago (Ros-Rocher et al., 2021). This transition to obligate multicellularity was marked by the evolution of key innovations including mechanisms of cell-cell adhesion, the development of an extracellular matrix, and the emergence of intercellular signaling pathways (Ros-Rocher et al., 2021). These features were

accompanied by the establishment of spatially differentiated cell types, the evolution of programmed cell death, and the delineation of germline and somatic lineages (Ros-Rocher et al., 2021).

While the dominant explanatory paradigm for this transition remains largely adaptationist, emerging evidence suggests that SGEs played a significant role in shaping the evolutionary trajectory of animal multicellularity. Multiple lines of research now implicate SGEs as both catalysts of genetic innovation and potential drivers of developmental complexity during this major evolutionary transition. First, the evolution of programmed cell death - a fundamental prerequisite for the maintenance of multicellular organization - is hypothesized to have been driven by the selective pressures imposed by high SGE infection rates in colonial ancestors, as supported by recent computational modeling studies under kin selection frameworks (Iranzo et al., 2014; Koonin, 2016). Second, the Hedgehog signaling proteins, which are central to the regulation of developmental processes in metazoans, likely trace their evolutionary origin to inteins - SGEs that uniquely combine transpositional mobility at the DNA level with self-splicing activity at the protein level (Adamska et al., 2007; Bürglin, 2008). Third, the evolutionary fixation of germline-soma differentiation has been shown to be selectively advantageous under conditions of pervasive SGE activity, particularly when such elements frequently insert into genomic loci, thereby threatening genomic integrity and fitness (Johnson, 2008b).

More broadly, SGEs are known to destabilize lower-level biological units, thereby facilitating the emergence of higher-level cooperative systems, such as multicellular organisms derived from unicellular progenitors (Ågren, 2014). At the genomic level, SGEs promote genetic innovation through mechanisms such as gene duplication, exon shuffling, and the rewiring of regulatory networks - all of which are central to the evolution of developmental complexity in animals (Werren, 2011). Collectively, these findings support the hypothesis that SGEs have been significant, albeit indirect, drivers in the evolution of animal multicellularity, although the precise evolutionary trajectory remains to be fully elucidated.

1.1.4. The origin of vertebrates adaptive immune system

The vertebrate adaptive immune system represents an extraordinarily intricate network, encompassing numerous specialized cell types, hundreds of surface and signaling molecules, and thousands of genomic regulatory elements (Arneth, 2025). Central to its functionality is the mechanism of V(D)J recombination, which, when combined with junctional diversity, enables

the generation of an immense repertoire - estimated at hundreds of billions - of immunoglobulins and T and B cell receptors (Charles A Janeway et al., 2001). This system is believed to have emerged approximately 600 million years ago in the last common ancestor of jawed vertebrates (gnathostomes), although precursor cell types such as T and B lymphocytes likely originated earlier, in the common ancestor of all vertebrates (Flajnik & Kasahara, 2010). The complexity and energetic cost of the adaptive immune system are further amplified by the necessity of self-tolerance and clonal selection processes (Hedrick, 2004). Given its elaborate architecture, high metabolic burden and the cost of self-tolerance, the de novo emergence of such a system is difficult to reconcile with gradual adaptation alone, even under strong selective pressures for enhanced immunological defense in predatory jawed vertebrates with limited reproductive output to maintain stable predator-to-prey ratio (Flajnik, 1998; Flajnik & Kasahara, 2010).

SGEs, particularly DNA-based transposons, offer crucial mechanistic insights into the evolutionary origin of the vertebrate adaptive immune system. Accumulating evidence supports the hypothesis that V(D)J recombination - a central mechanism enabling somatic diversification of antigen receptors - arose through the molecular domestication of Transib DNA transposons (Shridharan et al., 2022) (Figure 4). Specifically, the RAG1 recombinase, the catalytic component of the V(D)J recombination complex, is derived from a Transib transposase and retains key structural features such as the conserved DDE catalytic triad (Fugmann, 2010). Furthermore, the recombination signal sequences (RSS) that direct segment rearrangement during V(D)J recombination appear to have evolved from the terminal inverted repeats of Transib elements (Kapitonov & Jurka, 2005). An evolutionary intermediate supporting this trajectory is the protoRAG transposon, identified in basal chordates such as lancelets. This element encodes RAG1/2-like proteins and retains Transib-like terminal inverted repeats, although its recombination activity is markedly reduced (Yakovenko et al., 2021b). Together, these findings outline a compelling scenario in which a once-parasitic element was co-opted to generate the complex somatic recombination machinery foundational to vertebrate immunity (Yakovenko et al., 2021b).

Figure 4. Parallel mechanisms of DNA transposition and V(D)J recombination, adapted from (Kapitonov & Jurka, 2005). (A) In classical DNA transposition, a self-encoded transposase enzyme mediates the excision of a transposable element flanked by terminal inverted repeats, followed by integration of the element into a new genomic location. The original excision site is subsequently repaired by the host DNA repair machinery.

(B) In the vertebrate adaptive immune system, V(D)J recombination proceeds via a mechanistically analogous pathway. Variable (V), diversity (D), and joining (J) gene segments are flanked by RSSs, which share structural similarity to terminal inverted repeats. The RAG1 and RAG2 recombinase complex recognizes pairs of RSSs according to the 12–23 spacer rule, catalyzing cleavage at the intervening DNA. The resulting coding ends (e.g., D and J) are then processed and ligated through non-homologous end joining (NHEJ), forming the coding and signal joints. This process underlies the combinatorial diversity of antigen receptor repertoires.

1.1.5. The origin of invasive placenta

The human placenta exhibits a markedly invasive phenotype, characterized by deep penetration into maternal uterine tissues and the establishment of direct contact with maternal blood - a feature that contrasts with the less invasive placentation observed in the majority of mammalian species (Carter, 2021). This highly invasive placental architecture is hypothesized to have evolved in the last common ancestor of eutherian mammals approximately 130 million years ago, with secondary losses and the emergence of non-invasive forms occurring independently in multiple lineages (Laundon et al., 2024; Mika et al., 2022). The enhanced maternal-fetal interface conferred by such invasiveness is thought to facilitate efficient transfer of nutrients and oxygen, a factor potentially contributing to the evolution of increased fetal

brain size in primates, including humans. However, this adaptation also introduced a maternal-fetal evolutionary conflict, which has been proposed as a driving force in the rapid diversification of placental mammals and is implicated in the etiology of various pregnancy-related pathologies (Chuong, Hannibal, et al., 2013).

Endogenous retroviruses (ERVs), ancient viral sequences stably integrated into the host genome, have played a pivotal role in the evolution of the mammalian placenta by contributing genes essential for its formation and function (Imakawa et al., 2022). Among the most notable are ERV-derived *syncytin* proteins, such as *syncytin-1* and *syncytin-2*, which mediate trophoblast cell fusion to form the syncytiotrophoblast - a multinucleated epithelial layer critical for nutrient and gas exchange at the maternal-fetal interface (X. Zhang & Muglia, 2021). These syncytins originated from retroviral envelope (*env*) genes that were independently co-opted for placental function approximately 25–40 million years ago in the lineage of Old World monkeys and other eutherian lineages, harnessing the fusogenic capabilities of viral proteins to enhance placental invasiveness (Cornelis et al., 2013; Imakawa et al., 2022). Through the process of molecular domestication, these genes have lost their pathogenic properties while retaining functional domains necessary for cell-cell fusion. In addition to protein-coding contributions, ERVs have also donated regulatory elements - such as enhancers - that modulate placental gene expression, thereby facilitating structural and functional diversification of placentas across mammalian lineages (Chuong, Rumi, et al., 2013).

The evolution of the invasive placenta in eutherian mammals appears to have been driven in part by ERV-mediated innovations in trophoblast cell function, particularly the capacity for deep implantation into maternal tissues. This invasive implantation phenotype, especially pronounced in humans and other haplorhine primates, represents a stark contrast to the more superficial placentation observed in many other mammalian taxa (Carter, 2021). These ERV-derived genetic contributions exemplify how ancient viral infections have catalyzed key evolutionary transitions, including the evolution of viviparity in placental mammals. Furthermore, the evolution of eutherian placentation is shaped by two overlapping evolutionary conflicts: an intragenomic arms race involving host defenses and SGEs, and the maternal-fetal conflict over allocation of physiological resources. Together, these selective pressures have likely contributed to the exceptional evolutionary plasticity and diversification observed among eutherian mammals.

It is important to note that the invasiveness of the human placenta has profound implications for cancer metastasis, as both processes share strikingly similar molecular mechanisms and cellular behaviors (D'Souza & Wagner, 2014). Invasive placentation and cancer metastasis both involve the migration and invasion of cells through extracellular matrices, facilitated by enzymes such as matrix metalloproteinases, changes in integrin expression, and activation of pathways like epithelial-mesenchymal transition (Costanzo et al., 2018). Additionally, both invasive trophoblasts and metastatic cancer cells use the common set of regulators to exploit immune evasion strategies, angiogenesis, and anti-apoptotic signaling, further underscoring their biological parallels (Rekowska et al., 2023). This is an example of antagonistic pleiotropy (Gems & Kern, 2024): the same genes and pathways that allow for successful placental invasion during reproduction may, later in life, increase susceptibility to malignancy and metastasis.

1.1.6. REs and human neocortex

Neocortex expanded incrementally from early mammals (~20 distinct cortical areas) to primates (~50 areas), with humans achieving ~180 areas (Kaas, 2019). Selective pressures for problem-solving, social cooperation, and tool use likely drove this progression (Kaas, 2019), supported by human-specific enhancers that enable layered neocortical structure and synaptic plasticity at the transcriptional level (Tilot et al., 2021).

While SGEs may not have been the primary drivers of human neocortex evolution, REs - particularly LINE-1 (L1) - have made substantial contributions to neuronal transcriptional diversity through somatic mosaicism during brain development (Bodea et al., 2018). Single-cell whole genome sequencing (WGS) studies have revealed that the frequency of somatic L1 insertions ranges from approximately one insertion per 25 neurons in the cerebral cortex (Evrony et al., 2012) to as many as 13.7 insertions per neuron in the hippocampus (Upton et al., 2015). These somatic insertions appear to be functionally significant: numerous developmentally regulated and cell type-specific chimeric RNAs originate from L1 activity. Notably, the human-specific long non-coding RNA (lncRNA) LINC01876, transcribed from an L1 promoter, modulates neural progenitor differentiation; CRISPR-mediated silencing of this transcript results in reduced cerebral organoid size and premature neuronal maturation (Garza et al., 2025). Additional L1-driven transcripts regulate genes involved in synaptogenesis, neurodevelopmental processes, and cellular stress responses (Bodea et al., 2018). Dysregulation

of L1 activity has been implicated in the pathogenesis of several neurodevelopmental and psychiatric disorders, including schizophrenia, autism spectrum disorder, and major depressive disorder (Bodea et al., 2018; Jahangir et al., 2022; S. Liu et al., 2016). Furthermore, in the adult hippocampus, L1 retrotransposition has been associated with long-term memory formation; experimental inhibition of L1 activity impairs memory in murine models, suggesting a role in modulating synaptic plasticity and cognitive networks (Bachiller et al., 2017). Finally, the highest insertional activity of L1 element was found in dentate gyrus and this is simultaneously the hotspot of adult neurogenesis (Kurnosov et al., 2015). Collectively, these observations highlight the pervasive and functionally relevant influence of SGEs in shaping the transcriptional landscape and evolutionary complexity of such complex organs as the human neocortex.

1.2. Classes of human retrotransposons

REs, which replicate via an RNA intermediate, constitute ~42–44% of the human genome, whereas DNA transposons occupy only 3% (Bannert & Kurth, 2004). They are classified into LTR (long terminal repeat) and non-LTR retrotransposons, each with distinct subfamilies (Bannert & Kurth, 2004):

1. Non-LTR retrotransposons

1.1. LINEs (Long Interspersed Nuclear Elements) (Bannert & Kurth, 2004; Brouha et al., 2003):

1.1.1. Proportion: ~17–22% of the genome.

1.1.2. Key family: LINE-1 (L1) is the only active autonomous retrotransposon in humans, contributing ~17–18% of genomic DNA.

1.1.3. Function: Encode proteins (ORF1p, ORF2p) for self-retrotransposition and mobilize non-autonomous elements like SINEs.

1.2. SINEs (Short Interspersed Nuclear Elements) (X.-O. Zhang et al., 2021):

1.2.1. Proportion: ~13% of the genome.

1.2.2. Key family: Alu elements (primate-specific) dominate, with ~1 million copies.

1.2.3. Function: Non-autonomous; rely on LINE-1 machinery for retrotransposition.

1.3. SVA Elements (Chu et al., 2023):

1.3.1. Proportion: ~0.15–0.2% of the genome.

1.3.2. Features: Hominid-specific, composite elements (SINE-R, VNTR, Alu-like regions).

1.3.3. Function: Recent activity, implicated in genomic instability.

2. LTR retrotransposons

2.1. HERVs (Human Endogenous Retroviruses) (Mao et al., 2021):

2.1.1. Proportion: ~8–9% of the genome.

2.1.2. Structure: Remnants of ancient retroviral infections, with LTRs flanking internal genes (e.g., *gag*, *pol*).

2.1.3. Function: Some co-opted for host biology (e.g., *syncytin* in placental development).

2.2. MaLRs (Mammalian Apparent LTR-Retrotransposons) (Zuo, 2023):

2.2.1. Proportion: Minor component (~1–2% of LTR class).

2.2.2. Features: Non-autonomous, often found near genes.

3. Other retroelements

3.1. Processed pseudogenes (Troskie et al., 2021):

3.1.1. Proportion: ~1–2% of the genome.

3.1.2. Origin: Processed mRNAs reverse-transcribed and integrated into the genome by LINE-1 REs.

In the subchapters below we discuss the structure, evolution and functional impact of the three major RE classes: LINES, SINEs and HERVs (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Major RE classes and their occupation of the human genome, adapted from (Cordaux & Batzer, 2009).

1.2.1. LINES

Long interspersed nuclear elements (LINES), particularly LINE-1 (L1), are hypothesized to have originated from group II self-splicing introns, as suggested by homology in their RT domains (Stamos et al., 2017). This evolutionary origin likely predates the Precambrian era, with no clear homologs among extant viral lineages (Baldwin et al., 2024). Phylogenomic analyses indicate that LINE-1 elements have been active components of mammalian genomes for over 100 million years, with fossilized insertions traceable to the last common ancestor of extant mammals (Boissinot et al., 2000; L. Yang et al., 2023). In contemporary human genomes, while hundreds of thousands of L1 copies exist, dozens of them retain retrotransposition competence *in vitro*, and contribute to somatic and germline insertional mosaicism *in vivo* (L. Yang et al., 2023). This ongoing activity is functionally significant, to the extent that it can interfere with CRISPR/Cas9-mediated genome editing, likely through exploitation of DNA double-strand breaks introduced during the editing process with ~2500 new insertions in experimental cell lines (Tao et al., 2022).

Comparative analyses between individual genomic LINE-1 insertions and a consensus sequence representing currently active LINE-1 elements have enabled the estimation of insertion age and the reconstruction of LINE-1 evolutionary dynamics. Such studies have identified sixteen primate-specific LINE-1 subfamilies, designated PA1 through PA16, which exhibit a monophyletic origin (Khan et al., 2006; Smit et al., 1995). The observed temporal stratification of these subfamilies supports a model of subfamily succession, whereby older LINE-1 lineages are gradually supplanted by newly emergent, more active variants over evolutionary time. Emerging evidence indicates that host-encoded restriction factors (such as KRAB zinc-finger genes ZNF91/93) targeting LINE-1 expression may play a central role in shaping this turnover, exerting selective pressure that contributes to the displacement of older subfamilies by newer ones (Jacobs et al., 2014; P. Yang et al., 2017). Interestingly, evolutionary reconstructions show that initially a newly emerged LINE-1 subfamily is repressed by RNAi and later specific transcription factors are selected to repress the transposons more specifically (Castro-Diaz et al., 2014).

Structurally, a full-length human L1 element spans approximately 6 kilobases and comprises a 5' untranslated region (UTR) harboring an internal promoters (sense and antisense ones) enriched with multiple TFBS, two open reading frames (ORF1 and ORF2) encoding an RNA-binding protein and a multifunctional protein with endonuclease and RT activities, respectively, and a 3' UTR terminating in a polyadenylation signal and poly(A) tail (Athaniyar et al., 2004; Xiao-Jie et al., 2016) (Figure 6A).

Figure 6. Structural organization and retrotransposition mechanism of a full-length LINE-1 (L1) element, adapted from (Xiao-Jie et al., 2016).

(A) A canonical human L1 is approximately 6 kb in length and consists of a 5' UTR containing both sense and antisense internal promoters (SP and ASP, respectively), ORF1 and ORF2, and a 3' UTR followed by a polyadenylation signal and poly(A) tail. ORF1 encodes a protein (ORF1p) containing an RNA recognition motif, while ORF2 encodes a multifunctional protein (ORF2p) possessing endonuclease and RT activities.

(B) The retrotransposition process initiates with transcription of L1 mRNA from the sense promoter (Step 1), followed by export to the cytoplasm (Step 2), where the transcript is either targeted by small interfering RNAs (siRNAs) and Piwi-interacting RNAs (piRNAs) for degradation, or translated into ORF1p and ORF2p (Step 3). These proteins bind the L1 mRNA to form a ribonucleoprotein (RNP) complex (Step 4), which re-enters the nucleus (Step 5).

There, reverse transcription and genomic integration occur via target-primed reverse transcription (TPRT) (Step 6), wherein the ORF2p endonuclease introduces a nick in genomic DNA to expose a 3'-hydroxyl group that primes cDNA synthesis by ORF2p RT. This process facilitates the insertion of new L1 copies into novel genomic loci. Steps are numbered in small circles.

The mechanism of L1 mobilization is called target-primed reverse transcription (TPRT, Figure 6B): after transcription, L1 mRNA is exported to the cytoplasm, where ORF1p (an RNA-binding protein with chaperone activity) and ORF2p (with endonuclease and RT functions) are translated or mRNA is repressed by siRNAs or piRNAs (Ghanim et al., 2025; Xiao-Jie et al., 2016). The siRNA-mediated repression is exerted by processing of bidirectional transcripts from SP and ASP of LINE elements (N. Yang & Kazazian, 2006). ORF1p and ORF2p preferentially bind their encoding mRNA (cis-preference), forming an RNP complex that re-enters the nucleus. ORF2p nicks the genomic DNA, using the 3' hydroxyl group to prime reverse transcription of the L1 RNA, resulting in integration at a new site (Luqman-Fatah et al., 2024). L1 retrotransposition machinery is also capable of mobilizing non-autonomous REs, including Alu and SVA elements, as well as select cellular RNAs such as U6 small nuclear RNA, through similar enzymatic mechanisms (Garcia-Perez et al., 2007). This capacity for trans-mobilization enables the retroposition of diverse RNA species, occasionally giving rise to novel classes of non-autonomous repetitive elements. For instance, chimeric insertions comprising small nuclear RNAs and L1 sequences have been identified in genomic loci, suggesting a potential mechanism by which new RE families may originate through recombination or template switching events during reverse transcription (Buzdin et al., 2002).

These LINE-1-mediated retrotransposition events are sometimes accompanied by intra-LINE-1 rearrangements (such as 5' truncations and 5' truncations associated with inversion/deletion events) or genomic structural rearrangements, both affecting the host genome structure and regulation (Figure 7). The features of these events suggest that host processes, such as DNA repair (Vladimirova et al., 2021) and/or DNA replication, may ultimately impact the structure of newly retrotransposed LINE-1 resulting in a wide variety of possible outcomes and shaping the host genome evolution in extremely diverse ways (Richardson et al., 2015).

Figure 7. Structural alterations associated with LINE-1 retrotransposition events, adapted from (Richardson et al., 2015). (A) LINE-1 insertions can disrupt the target genomic locus through a variety of mutational outcomes, including 5' truncations, internal inversions, target-site deletions, duplications, and the formation of chimeric insertions mediated by template switching. (B) In some cases, LINE-1 retrotransposition is linked to large-scale structural variations within the host genome, such as extensive deletions and duplications, illustrating the potential of LINE-1 activity to profoundly reshape genomic architecture.

The 5' UTR of L1 contains binding sites for numerous transcription factors and chromatin modifying complexes, including YY1, Runx3, Sp1, Myc, CTCF, p300 and SOX proteins, which are essential for transcriptional initiation and regulation (Athaniyar et al., 2004; X. Sun et al., 2018). Recent large-scale profiling found that over 130 transcription factors bind the L1 5' UTR promoter in human embryonic stem cells and cancer cell lines, with TF binding highly clustered in a specific promoter subregion (X. Sun et al., 2018). These interactions allow L1s to act as regulatory hubs, influencing the expression of nearby genes, sometimes providing alternative promoters or enhancers, and affecting chromatin structure (Richardson et al., 2015). Host cells regulate L1 activity via epigenetic mechanisms (e.g., DNA methylation, histone modification) and specific repressors such as TEX19.1, which ubiquitinates and targets L1-

ORF1p for degradation, thereby restricting L1 mobilization in pluripotent cells (MacLennan et al., 2025). For example, DNA methylation is initially established in primordial germ cells, is maintained in adulthood, and is believed to generally repress the expression of LINE-1 in somatic tissues (Bestor & Bourc'his, 2004). APOBEC3, the cytidine deaminase that inhibits retroviruses and other genome parasites, is also shown to combat new insertions of LINE-1 via deaminase dependent and independent pathways (Bogerd et al., 2006).

L1 insertions have been domesticated in some cases, with exaptation of L1-derived sequences into functional host genes or regulatory elements; for example, L1 promoters have been co-opted to drive expression of adjacent genes, and L1 sequences have contributed to the evolution of new exons and regulatory motifs (Richardson et al., 2015). For instance, an intronic L1M2a element functions as an interferon-inducible enhancer of the *IFNAR1* gene, playing a critical role in mediating the human antiviral response (Buttler et al., 2023). Furthermore, activation of ASP within LINE-1 elements induces expression of ORF0 and promotes cellular proliferation - an effect consistent with the widespread desilencing of LINE-1 elements observed across diverse cancer types (Honda et al., 2020). Additionally, LINE-1 promoters serve as alternative promoters for approximately 100 protein-coding genes and lncRNAs in human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs). Experimental silencing of these elements has been shown to disrupt neural differentiation and reduce the size of cerebral organoids, implicating LINE-1 derived regulatory activity in the modulation of key neurodevelopmental gene networks (Adami et al., 2025).

The involvement of LINE-1 (L1) elements in human disease is both extensive and mechanistically diverse, with over one hundred pathogenic insertions identified to date across a spectrum of conditions, including cancer, autoimmune disorders, neurodegenerative diseases, and developmental syndromes (Hancks & Kazazian, 2012). Among the most direct examples are L1 insertions disrupting the coding or splicing sequences of *F8* and *DMD* genes, leading to hemophilia A and Duchenne muscular dystrophy, respectively, through loss-of-function mutations (Hancks & Kazazian, 2016). In autoimmune pathologies such as systemic lupus erythematosus, hypomethylation and aberrant overexpression of L1 RNA and protein products can activate innate immune pathways - including Toll-like receptor (TLR)-dependent and independent mechanisms - culminating in the upregulation of type I interferons (e.g., IFN- α , IFN- β) and chronic immune activation (X. Zhang et al., 2020). In the oncological context, L1-mediated retrotransposition intermediates have been implicated in replication fork stalling, DNA damage, and copy number variation, thereby promoting genomic instability and activating DNA damage response pathways such as ATR and ATM, potentially enhancing

tumor adaptability and progression according to the recent preprint research (McKerrow et al., 2020). In non-small cell lung cancer, for instance, L1 elements generate chimeric transcripts with host genes, supporting tumor proliferation and metabolic reprogramming, and their expression is associated with poor clinical outcomes (Z. Sun et al., 2022). Additionally, cancer-specific L1 insertions - such as one located within an exon of *MOV10*, a known L1 repressor - can result in exon skipping and diminished gene expression, thereby increasing retrotransposition frequency and contributing to genomic instability, including the functional inactivation of tumor suppressors like *TP53* in gastrointestinal malignancies (Jung et al., 2018).

1.2.2. SINEs

Short interspersed nuclear elements (SINEs), in particular the Alu subfamily, are the most abundant RE in the human genome, with over one million copies constituting about 10% of the genome (Lander et al., 2001). Alu elements originated approximately 55–65 million years ago in primates through the fusion of two monomers derived from the 7SL RNA gene, a component of the signal recognition particle (SRP), resulting in a dimeric ~300 bp structure with left and right arms connected by an A-rich linker (Häsler & Strub, 2006a; Jung et al., 2018) (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Alu REs, approximately 300 base pairs in length, exhibit a characteristic dimeric architecture, with the two monomeric units separated by an A-rich linker sequence (A_5TACA_6) and terminating in a polyadenylated tail. The 5' (left) monomer harbors conserved internal RNA polymerase III promoter elements - namely the A and B boxes - which are essential for Alu transcriptional activity. Adapted from (Saeli et al., 2018).

Alu elements represent non-autonomous REs that lack protein-coding capacity and are thus dependent on the enzymatic machinery of LINE-1 elements - specifically the ORF2p-encoded endonuclease and RT - for mobilization through TPRT (Figure 6B) (Saeli et al., 2018). Embedded RNA polymerase III promoter motifs within both monomeric arms drive transcription of Alu elements into RNA intermediates that adopt distinct secondary structures requisite for recognition by L1 proteins (Polak & Domany, 2006). This parasitic co-option is facilitated by transient ribosomal association of Alu RNAs, mediated through sequence

homology to SRP, enabling physical proximity to L1 proteins during translation and thereby promoting Alu retrotransposition (Baar et al., 2022). As Alu elements lack intrinsic transcriptional terminators, transcription typically ceases at proximal genomic TTTT motifs (S. Kim et al., 2016). Notably, recent findings indicate partial involvement of RNA polymerase II in Alu transcription and relative independence of Alu transcription on the expression of adjacent genes (Baar et al., 2022; Tlučková et al., 2025). Furthermore, retrotranspositional efficiency is modulated by the length of the 3' poly(A) tail, with longer tails enhancing L1 protein interaction and subsequent mobilization (Comeaux et al., 2009).

Functionally, Alu elements have a profound regulatory impact on host gene expression. They are enriched in gene-rich regions, often residing within introns, UTRs, and near promoters, where they provide alternative promoters, enhancers, splice sites, and polyadenylation signals (Comeaux et al., 2009; Costallat et al., 2022). They are also more conserved when located upstream of the gene TSS and form enhancer-like 3D interactions as it was shown using Hi-C (Costallat et al., 2022; Su et al., 2014). Interestingly, they delineate H3K4me3-rich promoter area near TSS from the upstream DNA methylated regions, and they are located systematically closer to the promoters activated during T cell mediated immune responses (Costallat et al., 2022), highlighting the principle of SGEs co-option during major evolutionary transitions (Figure 9). Alu sequences harbor numerous TFBS, including those for hematopoietic TFs such as Gfi-1, LYF-1, GATA2/3, PITX2, Nkx2.5, and LUN1, many experimentally confirmed to bind Alu DNA (Polak & Domany, 2006). Certain Alu elements possess the capacity to bind the insulator protein CTCF, and along with other SINEs, they have contributed to the reorganization of the host genome's three-dimensional architecture across successive waves of retrotransposition in different mammalian species, inserting new CTCF binding sites that act like insulators and chromatin barriers (Schmidt et al., 2012).

Figure 9. First Alu element upstream of T-cell immune response connected genes allows to establish epigenetic memory at the level of H3K4 trimethylation. Adapted from (Costallat et al., 2022).

Alu elements harbor functional retinoic acid response elements, which serve as binding sites for retinoic acid receptors and modulate host gene transcription in response to retinoid signaling pathways (Vansant & Reynolds, 1995). Furthermore, hepatocyte nuclear factor 4 alpha (HNF4 α), a key metabolic transcription factor of the nuclear receptor family, has been shown to bind over one million Alu elements across the genome, thereby regulating a broad repertoire of genes involved in metabolic processes and RNA biogenesis, as demonstrated through chromatin immunoprecipitation and luciferase reporter assays (Bolotin et al., 2011). Experimental evidence from cell-based reporter systems further supports the notion that Alu elements can function as transcriptional enhancers, with the capacity to attenuate the expression of nearby host genes (Pérez-Molina et al., 2020). Moreover, Alu elements are considered as the primary source of novel enhancer during recent primate evolution (Deininger, 2011; Häsler & Strub, 2006a; J. Wang et al., 2022). Remarkably, Alu elements also contribute to the organization of chromatin architecture: their transcriptional state directly influences nucleosome positioning, with active Alu elements establishing phased nucleosomal arrays exhibiting ~ 167 base pair periodicity in adjacent genomic regions (Tanaka et al., 2010). Furthermore, the distribution of Alu elements is non-random: they are enriched near metabolism-related genes but underrepresented in structural genes, suggesting selective pressures for their regulatory roles (Grover et al., 2003, 2004; Polak & Domany, 2006).

Given their high density within gene-rich genomic regions, inverted Alu elements represent a particularly salient subclass of REs with distinct regulatory potential (Figure 10). When two Alu elements are inserted in opposite orientations in close genomic proximity, their transcription can give rise to double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) structures due to sequence complementarity. These dsRNAs serve as endogenous immunogenic molecules and function as key post-transcriptional cis-regulatory elements (K. Lee et al., 2024). Specifically, inverted Alus have been implicated in the regulation of circular RNA biogenesis (Wr et al., 2013), modulation of RNA transport and stability, and as ligands for Z-DNA-binding proteins (de Reuver et al., 2022), thereby contributing to both RNA metabolism and innate immune signaling. Their ability to form structured RNAs positions them as critical modulators of gene expression and genome regulation in primates (K. Lee et al., 2024).

Figure 10. Inverted Alu elements and their regulatory roles in gene expression (adapted from (K. Lee et al., 2024)). When two Alu elements are integrated within a single gene in opposing orientations, they can form an inverted configuration. Upon transcription, these elements generate intramolecular dsRNA structures through base pairing between complementary sequences. Such dsRNAs can influence host gene regulation through various post-transcriptional mechanisms. Inverted Alu elements are predominantly localized within

intronic regions and 3' UTRs, where they contribute to processes including RNA editing, stability, and localization.

Analogous to the regulatory mechanism observed in inverted Alu pairs - where two oppositely oriented Alu elements form dsRNA structures upon transcription - distinct Alu copies positioned at promoter and enhancer regions may facilitate long-range chromatin interactions. Specifically, complementary Alu-derived sequences within nascent promoter and enhancer transcripts can engage in the formation of R-loops and other RNA-DNA or RNA-RNA hybrid secondary structures, thereby bridging distal regulatory elements (Bai et al., 2021). These Alu-mediated promoter–enhancer interactions appear to be evolutionarily conserved, suggesting a broader role for Alu elements in shaping transcriptional regulation across primate genomes (Bai et al., 2021).

A regulatory mechanism associated with Alu elements that partially overlaps with enhancer function is exonisation (Figure 11) - the process by which an Alu insertion with relatively weakened secondary structure contributes sequences to mature mRNA transcripts through alternative splicing, thereby modifying the transcript architecture of the host gene (S. Schwartz et al., 2009). This mode of regulation introduces lineage-specific splicing variability and can result in the emergence of novel exonic regions, more than 3000 of such regions are identified in (Attig et al., 2016). Notably, Alu-derived exons are frequently located within the 5'-UTRs of zinc finger transcription factor genes, such as *ZNF263*, where they influence translational dynamics by generating upstream ORFs. These upstream ORFs modulate both translation efficiency and alternative splicing in a tissue-specific manner, with documented effects in neural structures such as the cerebellum (Shen et al., 2011).

Figure 11. Conceptual model illustrating the process of Alu exonization, adapted from (Sorek, 2007). (A) An Alu element is retrotransposed into the intronic region of a primate gene. (B) Over evolutionary time, nucleotide substitutions accumulate within the Alu sequence, activating previously cryptic splice donor and acceptor sites (denoted by black arrows). In parallel, additional mutations may arise that alter splicing regulatory motifs (green arrow), further enhancing the splicing potential of the sequence. (C) As a consequence of these mutational changes, a portion of the Alu element is recognized by the splicing machinery as a novel exon and becomes incorporated into the mature transcript - a process termed exonization. In most cases, the resulting Alu-containing isoform represents a minor transcript variant, owing to the typically weak nature of the de novo splice sites. Notably, exonizations predominantly occur when the Alu is in the antisense orientation, likely due to the presence of an upstream poly-T stretch that functions as a strong polypyrimidine tract, facilitating 3' splice site recognition.

Due to their diverse regulatory and structural influences on the host genome, Alu elements are implicated in a broad spectrum of human diseases through mechanisms such as insertional mutagenesis, disruption of normal gene regulation, and non-allelic homologous recombination (NAHR) between adjacent Alu copies (Gussakovsky & McKenna, 2025). With an estimated germline insertion frequency of approximately one event per twenty human births, Alu elements contribute to the etiology of over fifty documented disorders, including at least thirty-seven that affect the nervous system (Stenz, 2021). For example, homologous recombination

between Alu repeats leads to genomic rearrangements various, such as intragenic deletions (S. Kim et al., 2016): in heritable pulmonary arterial hypertension, Alu-mediated deletions in *BMPR2* (exons 1-3 or 10) impair signaling pathways (Kataoka et al., 2013). Furthermore, splicing errors induced by intronic Alu elements cause diseases like neurofibromatosis with an Alu insertion in *NFI* that results in exon skipping and frameshifts (Wallace et al., 1991). The association between Alu elements and oncogenesis is particularly pronounced, as tumor suppressor genes - such as *BRCAl* - exhibit a higher density of Alu elements relative to oncogenes, thereby rendering them more susceptible to Alu-mediated mutagenesis through NAHR (W. Zhang et al., 2011). Notably, cancer-related loci such as the von Hippel-Lindau (*VHL*) tumor suppressor gene and mixed-lineage leukemia gene (*MLL* or *KMT2A*), which is frequently involved in fusion-driven leukemias, appear especially prone to Alu-induced NAHR events, underscoring the mutagenic potential of these elements in tumorigenesis (Ade et al., 2013). These mechanisms highlight Alu's dual role as both a source of structural variation and a regulator of oncogenic pathways, contributing to tumor initiation, progression, and metastasis.

1.2.3. HERVs

Human endogenous retroviruses (HERVs), constituting a prominent subclass of LTR REs, differ fundamentally from non-LTR retrotransposons such as LINEs and SINEs since there were several gene influx events from exogenous autonomous retroviruses to human genome, although no known HERV is presently infectious (Kato & Kurata, 2013). This recurrent viral integration contributes to the genomic repertoire by introducing novel genetic material, thereby facilitating a comparatively elevated rate of HERV-derived gene domestication throughout evolutionary history (da Silva et al., 2024). HERVs are remnants of ancient exogenous retroviruses that integrated into the germline DNA of primate ancestors 5–100 million years ago, and they now comprise about 8% of the human genome (Ito et al., 2017) forming around 40 distinct families (Hohn et al., 2013; Vargiu et al., 2016).

Structurally, HERVs are typically flanked by LTRs and retain a proviral structure with *gag*, *pol*, and *env* genes, although most copies have accumulated mutations and are no longer capable of producing infectious particles (de Parseval & Heidmann, 2005). The LTRs of HERVs contain promoter and enhancer elements, polyadenylation signals, and numerous TFBS, which are crucial for both HERV and host gene regulation (A. A. Buzdin et al., 2017; Sunsova et al., 2015; Thompson et al., 2016) (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Structural organization of HERV elements and their mechanisms of influence on human gene expression and physiology, adapted from (A. A. Buzdin et al., 2017).

The majority of HERV sequences persist in the genome as solitary LTRs, which are generated through homologous recombination events between the identical 5' and 3' LTRs flanking full-length proviral sequences. Intact proviruses typically encode the canonical retroviral genes - *gag*, *pro*, *pol*, and *env* - while members of the HERV-K (HML-2) family may also harbor accessory genes such as *rec* or *np9*, depending on the specific subtype. Each LTR contains key regulatory sites, including a polyadenylation signal, enhancer sequences, and promoter elements, which can initiate transcription of adjacent host genomic loci, thereby exerting regulatory effects on human gene expression and physiology.

Mobilization of HERVs originally occurred via a “copy-and-paste” mechanism similar to exogenous retroviruses, where reverse transcription and integration were mediated by viral proteins (Figure 12) (Brady et al., 2009), but most HERVs are now immobile due to inactivating mutations (Garazha et al., 2015). Interestingly, HERV RNA/DNA can be packaged into virions of exogenous viruses (e.g., HIV-1, KSHV) (Dube et al., 2014). These "pseudotyped" particles facilitate horizontal spread and reintegration into new genomic loci (Dube et al., 2014). Conversely, viral proteins (e.g., LANA of Kaposi’s Sarcoma-Associated Herpesvirus) or host transcription factors (e.g., NF-κB) reactivate HERVs, enhancing their transcription and mobilization (E. F. Evans et al., 2024). Additionally, some HERVs (e.g., HERV-K) encode functional RT and integrase enzymes, enabling reverse transcription of RNA into double-

stranded DNA (dsDNA) without relying on exogenous retroviruses (Dube et al., 2014; Jiang et al., 2025). Interestingly, when the HERV integrase binds to the dsDNA and mediates its insertion into the host genome, it preferentially targets transcriptionally active, gene-rich regions (e.g., near CpG islands or regulatory elements) (Ciuffi et al., 2005; G. P. Wang et al., 2007), which reflects probably an intragenomic selection of HERV elements to spread out via open chromatin.

Figure 12. Canonical model of reverse transcription in retroviruses, adapted from (X.-J. Zhang et al., 2018).

The reverse transcription process in retroviruses follows a well-characterized series of molecular events. (1) Synthesis of minus-strand DNA is initiated by a host-derived tRNA molecule that anneals to the primer-binding site located near the 5' end of the viral RNA genome. (2) The nascent DNA segment, corresponding to the R and U5 regions (R'U5'), is transferred to the 3' end of the viral RNA - a process referred to as the first strand transfer or “first jump” - where it anneals to the homologous R sequence to continue minus-strand synthesis. (3) A polypurine tract, situated near the 3' end of the RNA genome, serves as a primer for the initiation of plus-strand DNA synthesis. (4) The primer-binding site sequence on the newly synthesized minus-strand DNA then primes the extension of the plus-strand,

enabling the formation of a circular DNA intermediate in a process known as the second strand transfer or “second jump”. (5) The dsDNA copy is fully synthesized.

As it was mentioned before, HERV LTRs have been shown to act as tissue-specific promoters or enhancers, particularly in immune cells and during embryonic development, and can also provide regulatory elements for non-coding RNAs (Ito et al., 2017). This widespread regulatory impact of HERV onto the host gene expression is delineated by almost 800 000 HERV-linked TFBS, including pluripotent TFs (such as SOX2, POU5F1, and NANOG), embryonic endoderm/mesoderm TFs (such as GATA4/6, SOX17, and FOXA1/2), hematopoietic TFs (such SPI1 (PU1), GATA1/2, and TAL1), and CTCF, with certain subfamilies (e.g., LTR7 of HERVH) highly enriched for pluripotency factors in embryonic stem cells (Glinsky, 2021; Hossain et al., 2024; Ito et al., 2017). Other genome-wide analyses have identified hundreds of thousands of HERV-derived TFBSs, with at least 320,000 mapped to ~110,000 individual HERV loci, implicating HERVs in the regulation of thousands of human genes (Garazha et al., 2015). Moreover, an earlier 2008 year study reported as much as 51197 HERV-derived promoters, and 97 human genes were actually transcribed from LTR of these elements, producing chimeric transcripts (Conley et al., 2008).

At the level of discrete regulatory elements, numerous instances have been documented in which HERV-derived sequences exert modulatory effects on host gene expression. A notable example involves LTRs from HERVs embedded within intronic regions of the *SLC4A8* gene, encoding a sodium bicarbonate cotransporter, and the *IFT172* gene, which encodes intraflagellar transport protein 172 (Gogvadze et al., 2009; H.-S. Kim, 2012). These LTRs, oriented antisense to the direction of host gene transcription, function in vivo as alternative promoters that initiate the synthesis of antisense RNAs that are complementary to exonic regions of their respective host genes, thereby contributing to post-transcriptional gene silencing through antisense-mediated regulatory mechanisms (H.-S. Kim, 2012). In human embryonic stem cells, the HERV-H family exhibits pronounced transcriptional activity, with its RNA transcripts constituting approximately 2% of the total cellular transcriptome, and this elevated expression is modulated by core pluripotency transcription factors, including NANOG, OCT4, and SOX2 (Ohnuki et al., 2014; Santoni et al., 2012). In steroid-responsive tissues, the accessory protein Rec - encoded by a recently integrated HERV-K provirus - has been shown to upregulate androgen receptor expression. This Rec-mediated androgen receptor activation contributes to enhanced cellular proliferation, suppression of apoptotic pathways, and, ultimately, to oncogenic transformation or tumor progression (Hanke et al., 2013).

HERVs are also subject to host repression mechanisms, including KRAB-ZFPs (Krüppel-associated box domain zinc finger proteins), which bind to HERV TFBSs and recruit the co-repressor KAP1, leading to heterochromatin formation and transcriptional silencing via histone H3 lysine 9 trimethylation (Giménez-Orenga & Oltra, 2021; Hurst & Magiorkinis, 2017). As it was discussed earlier for LINE elements, human APOBEC3G and APOBEC3F induce hypermutation in HERV genomes by deaminating cytidine to uridine during reverse transcription, effectively inactivating viral DNA (Y. N. Lee et al., 2008). The APOBEC3G gene in primates shows strong positive selection across primate lineages, reflecting co-evolutionary arms races with retroviruses and HERV elements (Sawyer et al., 2004). Furthermore, HERV LTRs are silenced by DNA methylation in somatic cells, with hypermethylation at CpG islands preventing transcription factor binding and promoter activation (Chiappinelli et al., 2015; Pappalardo & Barra, 2021). In general, the HERV epigenetic control is multi-layered, with repression combining histone deacetylation, DNA methylation, and small RNA-guided silencing (e.g., piRNAs) to maintain HERV quiescence, though "leaky" transcription occurs at ~30% of loci due to incomplete silencing (Hurst & Magiorkinis, 2017; M. Zhang et al., 2019). The prevailing model of HERV evolutionary dynamics posits that newly integrated HERV loci are initially recognized by host cellular defense systems as exogenous genetic elements, leading to their transcriptional silencing via targeted DNA methylation and mutagenic inactivation (Schlesinger et al., 2013; Turelli et al., 2014). Over time, however, as mutational decay accumulates and renders retroviral ORF non-functional, the host genome may co-opt residual HERV sequences - particularly their LTRs - for regulatory purposes (Belshaw et al., 2007; Buttler & Chuong, 2022; J. A. Frank & Feschotte, 2017). This functional exaptation involves the progressive selection of mutations that repurpose former viral regulatory elements into cis-regulatory modules, thereby contributing to the diversification of transcription factor binding landscapes and modulating host gene expression in an evolutionary context (A. A. Buzdin et al., 2017). It is also important to note that sequence divergence over time also decrease the probability of recombinational deletion when two LTRs recombine to excise the HERV element and to preserve only a solo LTR: recently integrated HERVs have this probability 200 times lower than those that predate divergence between human and chimpanzee (Belshaw et al., 2007).

The particularly important impact of HERV onto the host genome is domestication of protein-coding genes. The most notable examples are the syncytin genes (e.g., *ERVWE1* and *ERVFRD-1*, briefly discussed earlier), which are derived from HERV *env* genes and have been co-opted for placental development, mediating trophoblast fusion and immune modulation at

the maternal-fetal interface (Shimode, 2023). At present, six intact *env* genes derived from distinct HERV families have been identified as functional *syncytins* and *suppressin*, mediating critical roles in placental development - an evolutionary innovation specific to Hominoids and Old World Monkeys (Figure 13). In contrast, HERV-K-encoded accessory proteins, such as Rec and Np9, remain less well-characterized but have been implicated in the modulation of gene expression, with emerging functions in both embryogenesis and tumorigenesis (T. Chen et al., 2013; Galli et al., 2005; Shiura et al., 2023). Additionally, PEG10 and PEG11, paternally expressed and imprinted genes of putative retroviral origin, are essential for embryonic development, though their evolutionary ancestry remains unresolved (Shiura et al., 2023).

Figure 13. Phylogenetic representation of primate lineages alongside the integration status of placenta-associated HERV elements, with corresponding information on placental implantation type, morphology, and degree of invasiveness - adapted from (Shimode, 2023). Arrowheads mark the estimated timing of retroviral *env* gene integration events into ancestral primate genomes. Solid squares denote the presence of intact, conserved ORF for the respective ERV *env* genes, whereas hatched squares indicate disrupted coding potential due to inactivating mutations, insertions, deletions, or frameshift events. Color coding corresponds to specific ERV families: red (ERV-FRD), blue (ERV-W), violet (ERVH48-1), orange (ERVV-1), pink (ERVV-2), green (ERV3-1), and brown (ERVMER34-1). Abbreviations: MYA – million years ago; OWMs – Old World Monkeys; NWMs – New World Monkeys. HERVs and their associated regulatory elements have been broadly implicated in a range of more than 20 human pathologies (Figure 14). Through mechanisms such as molecular mimicry and immune system dysregulation, HERV-derived sequences contribute to the etiology of

autoimmune disorders, including rheumatoid arthritis (Tugnet et al., 2013). Furthermore, aberrant expression of envelope (Env) proteins from HERV-W and HERV-K appears to engage pathophysiological pathways leading to such neurological disorders as multiple sclerosis, schizophrenia, Alzheimer’s disease, bipolar disorder and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (Giménez-Orenga & Oltra, 2021; Küry et al., 2018). Moreover, aberrant HERV activity has been linked to tumorigenesis across various cancer types. For instance, dozens of HERV elements belonging to the ERV1 family are differentially expressed in glioblastoma, where they activate oncogenic signaling cascades and facilitate tumor progression (Yuan et al., 2021). The TF TIP60 plays a critical tumor-suppressive role by repressing HERV expression through H3K9 trimethylation; loss of this repression leads to genome-wide de-repression of HERVs, which subsequently elicits a STING-mediated innate immune response and upregulates Interferon Regulatory Factor 7, driving an inflammatory phenotype in breast and colorectal malignancies (Rajagopalan et al., 2018). In clear cell renal carcinoma, widespread transcriptional deregulation mediated by HIFs reactivates dormant HERV-associated promoters, resulting in aberrant expression of downstream transcription factors such as POU5F1, thereby promoting cancer progression (Siebenthall et al., 2019).

Figure 14. Heatmap summarizing the distribution of published studies (1979–2023) investigating the association between major HERV families and various human diseases and disorders, adapted from (da Silva et al., 2024). The intensity of shading corresponds to the number of publicly available studies, with darker hues indicating a higher volume of publications and lighter tones representing fewer studies. Importantly, the color gradient reflects publication frequency and does not imply a consistent directionality of association; studies reporting upregulation, downregulation, or no correlation between HERV activity and disease were all included. Asterisks (*) denote disease categories with fewer than ten studies addressing HERV involvement. Abbreviations: HAND - HIV-associated neurocognitive disorder; COVID-19 - Coronavirus Disease 2019.

1.3. Organs and tissues differentially affected by REs

As we have discussed in the previous sections, REs engage in complex arms race-like interactions with the human genome, encompassing a spectrum of mechanisms such as differential repression, activation, mutation-induced disruption, imprinting, and expression modulation. These interactions influence genomic function across various scales and have been instrumental in the evolution of novel structures, notably the placenta (Lavialle et al., 2013). Given this multifaceted complexity, it is anticipated that human organs and tissues exhibit differential RE impacts at the levels of TFBS and gene expression (Gasparotto et al., 2023). The previously discussed empirical evidence supports this notion, highlighting tissue-specific regulatory roles of TEs in structures like the placenta and neocortex, including instances of somatic insertional mutagenesis in the latter (Suarez et al., 2018). In the subsequent discussion, we will explore emerging trends in the tissue and organ specificity of TE-driven regulatory and structural influences on the host genome. This includes examining how TEs contribute to the diversification of gene regulatory networks across different tissues, thereby shaping the functional landscape of the human genome in a tissue-specific manner.

The brain exhibits the highest levels of RE-derived RNA expression among somatic tissues, where these transcripts contribute to chromatin remodeling, alternative splicing, somatic mosaicism, and translational repression, thereby shaping neuronal gene networks and brain-specific functions (T. A. Evans & Erwin, 2021). However, other studies challenge this view; for instance, RNA-Seq analyses indicate that RE activity peaks in embryonic stem cells

(ESCs), testes, and medullary thymic epithelial cells - suggesting a potential role in thymic self-tolerance mechanisms (Larouche et al., 2020). The same analyses show that LINE, SINE, and LTR elements form consistent tissue clusters based on their expression profiles, with notably low activity in whole blood, pancreas, heart, skeletal muscle, and liver (Larouche et al., 2020). The markedly tissue specific activation patterns of REs are also evident in cancer, where distinct subfamilies function as tissue-specific enhancers: MER11 elements exhibit hypomethylation in colorectal carcinomas, while LTR12 elements display similar epigenetic deregulation in hepatocellular carcinoma (Karttunen et al., 2023).

RE activity at the level of chromatin modification displays marked tissue specificity, particularly for LTR elements (Trizzino et al., 2018). Notably, LTRs and LINEs tend to be repressed via trimethylation of histone H3 at lysine 9 (H3K9me3), whereas SINEs and other transposable elements are more frequently associated with H3K27me3-mediated silencing - an effect that is especially pronounced for evolutionarily recent insertions. Furthermore, the same study indicates that tissue-specific gene regulation by REs is predominantly mediated by RE-derived intronic enhancers, and the host genes with tissue specific expression are more likely to be enriched with these enhancers (Trizzino et al., 2018). Intriguingly, tissues such as the aorta, brain anterior caudate nucleus, and adipose nuclei exhibit the highest number of RE families enriched in regions of active chromatin, a pattern that contrasts with RNA-seq-based analyses which identified ESCs, testis, and thymic epithelium as having the highest RE expression (Larouche et al., 2020). This apparent discrepancy may be attributed to methodological differences across studies, including the use of distinct cell lines, omics platforms, and criteria for assessing RE and tissue-specific enrichment. It is also important to note that RE inserting in intronic regions in an opposite orientation to the host gene TSS could decrease RNA polymerase II processivity and decrease the host gene expression, acting as a rheostat (J. S. Han & Boeke, 2005).

At the level of more specific tissue-specific processes RE are specifically repressed in the immune system by multiple host TFs and chromatin modifiers (such as ATF7IP, SETDB1 and KRAB ZFPs), and disruption of this repression correlates with epigenetic and chronological age according to a preprint study (Ndhlovu et al., 2023). Recent analyses of human cell lines have revealed that Alu elements are preferentially enriched in histone-modified regions associated with active chromatin, particularly in proximity to genes involved in immune regulation and metabolic processes - for instance, modulating *FOXP3* expression

in T cells and genes governing lipid metabolism in hepatic tissue (Ali & Liang, 2024). Notably, this study also found that histone modifications linked to RE-mediated transcriptional activation are among the most consistently shared across a diverse panel of 14 cell lines, whereas repressive histone marks and DNase I hypersensitive sites - indicative of accessible chromatin - exhibit a higher degree of cell type specificity. The placenta - an evolutionary novelty of eutherian mammals - exemplifies the domestication of HERV-derived protein-coding genes, as was discussed earlier, and also utilizes thousands of regulatory elements derived from REs (Chuong, Rumi, et al., 2013; Johansen et al., 1989; V. J. Lynch et al., 2015). Similarly, the endometrium, another eutherian-specific reproductive tissue, has recruited 1,532 genes into tissue-specific expression programs, and 13% of these genes lie within 200 kilobases of a eutherian-specific DNA transposon, MER20, which functions as an enhancer by binding pregnancy-associated transcription factors (V. J. Lynch et al., 2011) (Figure 15). These examples from the placenta and endometrium provide rare quantitative insights into the extent of regulatory evolution driven by REs.

Figure 15. Parsimony-based reconstruction of gene expression dynamics in the tetrapod endometrium, adapted from (V. J. Lynch et al., 2015). Numbers positioned above the branches denote the count of genes either recruited into (+) or lost from (–) endometrial expression along the ancestral lineages of Mammalia (light blue), Theria (blue), and Eutheria (red). Branch lengths are scaled in proportion to the number of inferred gene expression recruitment and loss events, as determined by Wagner parsimony (refer to inset scale bar).

The tissue-specific expression of REs is intricately regulated by correspondingly specialized repression mechanisms, and resurrection of human REs under these mechanisms being dysregulated drives cellular senescence (X. Liu et al., 2023). For instance, in the human testis, two distinct piRNA-mediated silencing pathways operate at different stages of germ cell development to suppress RE activity (Abajorga et al., 2024; Gainetdinov et al., 2017) (Figure 16). Similarly, the APOBEC family of cytidine deaminases - previously discussed as key genomic defense agents against REs - also demonstrates pronounced tissue specificity. These enzymes are most abundantly expressed in immune-related tissues (notably the spleen and lymph nodes), as well as in the lungs and reproductive organs (testis and ovary), where they are believed to safeguard the germline from retrotransposition and viral threats (F. A. Koning et al., 2009). Notably, individual APOBEC family members exhibit unique expression patterns, each associated with specific tissues such as the gastrointestinal tract, immune system, liver, lungs, or gonads (Salter et al., 2016), being significantly dysregulated in cancer (H. Lu et al., 2025). This functional diversification suggests an additional layer of regulatory complexity, potentially exerting selective mutational pressure on newly inserted REs in a tissue-dependent manner depending on a given RE activity in a selected tissue.

Figure 16. Conceptual model of innate and adaptive piRNA-mediated genome defense against retroviruses and retrotransposons, adapted from (Gainetdinov et al., 2017). Initial invasion of the germline by a novel retroviral element leads to the immediate processing of viral transcripts into sense-oriented piRNAs, constituting an innate response (left panel). Subsequently, an adaptive piRNA pathway is established, characterized by the generation of antisense piRNAs. These antisense piRNAs guide the silencing machinery to the complementary sense transcripts, exerting co-transcriptional repression of REs (right panel).

The KRAB-ZFP regulatory system, previously discussed, exhibits predominant activity during embryonic development; however, in postnatal stages, members of this transcription factor family display highly tissue-specific expression patterns (Barde et al., 2013; Corsinotti et al., 2013). Notably, this specificity is most pronounced - and the degree of repression most attenuated - in the human brain, particularly within the neocortex (Nowick et al., 2009). This observation lends support to the hypothesis that KRAB-ZFP proteins are key mediators in the co-option of REs into human gene regulatory networks (Friedli & Trono, 2015). Furthermore, it is important to highlight that KRAB-ZFPs engage REs at later evolutionary stages compared to earlier-acting genomic defense mechanisms such as RNAi and APOBEC-mediated deamination (Figure 17), a temporal pattern that aligns with the tissue-specific nature of these systems. It is noteworthy that despite the intricate, multilayered, and tissue-specific nature of host defense mechanisms against REs, their activity does not exhibit a clear correlation with genome size across vertebrates - ranging from approximately 1 to 130 Gb in the most recent comparative analyses (J. Wang et al., 2023). This observation suggests that the evolutionary dynamics of the RE–host genome conflict are shaped more by the nuanced and context-dependent interactions within specific regulatory landscapes than by the total genomic investment in defensive strategies.

Figure 17. Co-evolutionary dynamics among REs, human KRAB-ZFPs, and other genomic defense mechanisms, adapted from (Friedli & Trono, 2015). Newly integrated REs are initially subject to partial suppression by host defenses such as RNAi and APOBEC-mediated deamination, permitting limited retrotransposition activity. Over time, specific KRAB-ZFP proteins evolve to recognize and robustly repress the corresponding RE subfamilies, contributing both to their silencing and to the functional domestication of select insertions. Concurrently, REs accumulate disabling mutations that abrogate their mobilization potential. While some insertions are lost through genetic drift, others are retained under positive and/or negative selection due to their co-option into host regulatory networks.

Although, as we discussed previously in this section, there is an evolutionary tendency to repress REs by host defensive mechanisms mostly during embryogenesis, this is not particularly true for some RE classes and families that successively evade the host defense. For example, one of the recently integrated HERV families, HERV-K, is hypomethylated and

transcribed immediately during embryonic genome activation at the 8-cell stage, and HERV-K viral-like particles and Gag proteins are detected in human blastocysts (Grow et al., 2015). Moreover, HERV-H LTRs act as enhancers and alternative promoters, critical for maintaining pluripotency in human ESCs: they are bound by pluripotency factors (OCT4, NANOG) and enriched in H3K4me3 (Macfarlan et al., 2012; Santoni et al., 2012). Finally, in ESCs, REs have made substantial contributions to the regulatory landscape, accounting for up to 25% of TFBS in both humans and mice (Kunarso et al., 2010). Through this process, they have facilitated the incorporation of novel genes into the core transcriptional circuitry governing ESC identity and function.

1.4. RE impact at different timescales

A growing body of literature indicates that several major evolutionary transitions were shaped - though to varying degrees - by SGEs, and especially by REs (Koonin, 2016). This supports the hypothesis that genomic invasions by SGEs tend to occur in episodic, wave-like patterns, characterized by rapid and large-scale expansions over relatively short evolutionary timescales (Gifford & Tristem, 2003). These bursts likely reflect pivotal shifts in the evolutionary arms race between the host genome and SGEs, such as the emergence of novel mobilization strategies by the elements or the development of new host defense mechanisms.

According to the RE families sequence divergence analysis and interspecies comparative genomics, the evolutionary trajectory of L1 elements in primates can be divided into two distinct phases (Khan et al., 2006). In the first phase, spanning approximately 70 to 40 million years ago, three separate L1 lineages coexisted within ancestral primates. This coexistence was facilitated by the independent recruitment of distinct 5'UTRs, enabling each lineage to co-evolve with specific host transcription factors. The second phase, beginning around 40 million years ago, was marked by the dominance of a single L1 lineage, which underwent extensive amplification - particularly through the L1PA8 to L1PA3 families - until around 12 million years ago. During this period, positive selection acted on the ORF1 protein, likely in response to increasing repression pressure from host transcription factors. L1 elements have also been examined across a broad group of 21 mammalian species spanning 13 taxonomic orders (Kriegs et al., 2006). These analyses revealed recurrent bursts of L1 activity across all three principal placental mammal clades (boreoeutheria, xenarthra and afrotheria), with a single L1 lineage rapidly becoming predominant within each clade. Notably, among the species analyzed, rodent genomes - particularly those of rat and mouse - exhibited the highest levels

of sequence divergence and the fastest rates of L1 molecular evolution. Furthermore, L1 insertions served as highly distinctive molecular signatures characteristic of individual mammalian clades. The presence or absence patterns of these elements at the RE family level provided a powerful phylogenetic signal, enabling the reconstruction of a robust mammalian evolutionary tree that avoided confounding effects commonly associated with parallel molecular evolution (Kriegs et al., 2006; Waters et al., 2008).

A broader evolutionary analysis examined the activity of five major RE classes - L2, L1, MIR, Alu, and LTR - across an extended phylogenetic timescale in mammals (T.-M. Kim et al., 2004). Distinct waves of RE expansion were observed, each aligning with pivotal evolutionary transitions within the mammalian lineage (Figure 18):

- L2/MIR (120–150 Mya): Expansion coincided with the divergence between marsupials and placental mammals.
- Ancient L1 (100 Mya): Activity peaked during the early diversification of eutherians.
- LTR (70 Mya): A notable burst occurred around the Cretaceous-Paleogene boundary, a period marked by significant climatic upheaval and mass extinction events, marked with low effective population size even for the surviving evolutionary lineages (Berv et al., 2024).
- Recent L1 and Alu (25–40 Mya): Expansion was temporally aligned with the radiation of hominoid lineages, including the divergence of Old World and New World monkeys.

Together, these data highlight the central role of REs in shaping genomic architecture during key phases of mammalian - and particularly primate - evolution.

Figure 18. Temporal association between peak RE activity and hominoid lineage diversification, adapted from (Berv et al., 2024). Representative activity peaks of Alu, L1, and LTR elements are shown using the most pronounced signal curves on chromosomes 19, Xq, and Y, respectively. To allow visual comparison, the average chromosomal contributions of L2 and MIR (mammalian-wide interspersed repeats) elements are displayed at 5× magnification, as their peak amplitudes are otherwise too subtle. A timeline of mammalian evolution, inferred from fossil and molecular evidence, is shown on the left vertical axis. Shaded bars spanning the schematic diagram indicate time intervals associated with major RE amplification events.

Further investigations have elucidated the evolutionary trajectories of specific RE subfamilies. For instance, AluYb, among the most active Alu lineages in the human genome, emerged approximately 18–25 million years ago and remained largely quiescent for around 20 million years. Its presence across the entire hominoid clade supports this period of dormancy, followed by a significant expansion in recent evolutionary time (K. Han et al., 2005). Similarly, the

L1P_MA2 subfamily of LINE-1 elements - implicated in splicing mutations in the *dystrophin* gene - exhibits a pattern of rapid diversification punctuated by phases of evolutionary stasis within primates (Cardazzo et al., 2003). The HERV-K family, representing one of the most recent groups of HERVs, also demonstrates a burst-like evolutionary pattern since its introduction into primate genomes between 45 and 35 million years ago. Unlike other HERV families, HERV-K elements remained transpositionally active after the divergence between human and chimpanzee lineages (J. F. Hughes & Coffin, 2005; C. J., 2001). However, interpretation of these dynamics is complicated by LTR-mediated homologous recombination events, which can result in the replacement of older elements with more recent HERV-K proviruses, thus confounding divergence-based phylogenetic analyses anchored to consensus sequences (J. F. Hughes & Coffin, 2005). Additionally, new families of HERVs can arise when previously dormant elements reactivate, produce effective virions that are transferred horizontally, reinfect the germline and get inserted in new genomic loci (Belshaw et al., 2004; Ishida et al., 2014; Stoye, 2006).

More recent evolutionary and comparative genomic studies reveal that over the past 10 million years, the human lineage - along with other great apes - has experienced an approximately fourfold reduction in the rate of HERV integration (Magiorkinis et al., 2015) (Figure 19). This decline is largely attributed to the extinction of the HERV-H family, which had been the predominant contributor to new insertions over the preceding 30 million years but has since lost all transcriptionally active copies. Furthermore, no new HERV families have been acquired in the human genome during this same 30-million-year period, a trend that may reflect a decreased incidence of horizontal retroviral transmission events in the lineage.

The observed overall decline in HERV activity and the extinction of retrotransposition-competent forms across major HERV families is further substantiated by a comprehensive whole-genome survey and classification of HERV elements (Vargiu et al., 2016). Out of 3,173 distinct HERV sequences identified - many of which are present in multiple genomic copies - only 1,214 (38.3%) were classified as canonical, meaning they retained both LTRs and a full complement of retroviral protein-coding genes. However, even among these canonical elements, none exhibited functional retrotranspositional capacity. The remaining sequences were characterized by various structural disruptions, including truncated termini, incomplete ORF, duplicated or rearranged LTRs, and inversions between coding sequences and LTRs, all indicative of accumulated mutational decay. HERV families exhibit variable susceptibility to mutational degradation. For instance, the HERV-W family - which contributed to the origin of human *syncytin* genes and was actively integrating into the genome between approximately

40 and 25 million years ago - has undergone extensive structural erosion. Notably, around 85% of HERV-W elements harbor a characteristic 1.2 kb deletion within the *env* gene, a mutation that abolishes their coding potential and renders these loci retrotranspositionally inactive (Grandi et al., 2016).

Figure 19. Phylogenetic tree of catarrhines - including Old World Monkeys, great apes, and gibbons - with available genome sequences, adapted from (Magiorkinis et al., 2015). The thickness of each branch represents the number of RE integration events inferred for that lineage, with each level of thickness corresponding to a two-million-year interval of integration activity.

A more recent targeted analysis investigated the evolutionary trajectories of specific HERV insertions that function as cis-regulatory elements for adjacent human genes through their TFBS (Calero-Layana et al., 2022). Focusing on five genes harboring intronic HERV sequences - *INPP5B*, *DET1*, *PSMA1*, *USH2A*, and *MACROD2* - the study employed comparative genomic approaches across 25 primate species to estimate the timing of these insertions. The results revealed that three of the five genes acquired their HERV-derived regulatory elements in the common ancestor of catarrhines, while the remaining two insertions originated more recently, in the last common ancestors of hominids and hominins, respectively. Notably, no species-specific insertions were identified in either humans or chimpanzees, reinforcing the previously discussed conclusion that the bulk of HERV expansion in the human lineage occurred between 40 and 20 million years ago.

As outlined throughout this section, both recent human evolution and broader mammalian diversification have been profoundly influenced by episodic bursts of RE activity across all

the three RE classes discussed. While the activity of HERVs has markedly diminished over the past 10 million years, LINE and SINE elements continue to propagate throughout the genome. Each wave of RE expansion introduced substantial structural and regulatory innovations - even facilitating the emergence of novel organs such as the placenta - while simultaneously increasing the risk of deleterious insertions. These expansions further intensified the molecular arms race between the host genome and SGEs, giving rise to a complex landscape of defense and counter-defense mechanisms (Figure 20) [254]. Notably, the contribution of RE-derived TFBSs, promoters, enhancers, insulators, and other regulatory elements has had a pronounced influence on host gene regulatory networks. The subsequent section, alongside the core research chapters of this thesis, focuses on delineating the dynamics of this intricate interplay between RE-mediated regulation and host genomic control.

Geena vs Transposon

Figure 20. Schematic metaphor illustrating the evolutionary arms race between the host genome and SGEs, adapted from (Blikstad et al., 2008). The diagram presents the full array of known host defense mechanisms and SGE counterstrategies, acknowledging that not all mechanisms are universally employed across all host-parasite systems. Defensive strategies include epigenetic silencing, mutational inactivation, and RNA-based interference, while SGEs evolve various evasion tactics. Abbreviations that were not defined earlier: RIGs - repeat-induced gene silencing (Arnaud et al., 2007; Stoye, 1998); RIP - repeat-induced point

mutation (Gardner et al., 1991; Murcia et al., 2007); Lsh - lymphoid-specific helicase (Crittenden et al., 1974).

1.5. Recent studies of RE-linked regulatory impact on human genome

Over the past two decades, several specialized databases have been developed to catalog genomic and epigenomic information related to human REs, thereby supporting a growing body of evidence concerning their regulatory roles in the human genome. In this section, we first provide an overview of these resources, followed by a synthesis of key findings and the current understanding of RE-associated regulatory mechanisms.

- Among the most widely utilized resources is RepBase (Bao et al., 2015; Kojima, 2018), which serves as a comprehensive reference database for human transposable elements, including REs such as LINEs, SINEs, and HERVs. RepBase offers consensus sequences for approximately 1,300 distinct elements, along with detailed annotations and taxonomic classifications for each RE family. Additionally, it provides reconstructions of their evolutionary histories, enabling comparative and phylogenetic analyses of transposable element lineages.
- The broadly applied tool RepeatMasker enables the identification and annotation of repetitive elements in genomic sequences by leveraging RepBase and other reference databases (Tarailo-Graovac & Chen, 2009). It provides genomic coordinates and family-level classifications of annotated elements and is commonly employed to investigate their overlap with genes and regulatory regions, as well as to detect putative repetitive elements in newly sequenced genomes.
- The Dfam database provides curated sequence models for repetitive elements, including RE, and serves as a foundational resource for genome-wide annotation via integration with tools such as RepeatMasker. It hosts hidden Markov models and multiple sequence alignments representing RE families, along with associated epigenetic data (Hubley et al., 2016).
- The dbRIP (Database of Retrotransposon Insertion Polymorphisms) catalogues polymorphic RE insertions across diverse human populations. It provides genomic coordinates of insertion sites, allele frequency data, genotypic information, and

documented associations with disease phenotypes, including pathogenic insertions (J. Wang et al., 2006).

- The recent TE-TSS database contains annotations of promoter elements derived from transposons. Gathered from 2681 RNA sequencing datasets and storing data about 5768 human RE-derived promoters, this database allows for comparison between 15 mammalian species (X. Gu et al., 2024).
- The HERVd database focuses on HERVs, mapping their genomic locations, family classifications and containing additional information about their target site duplications (Pačes et al., 2002). Remarkably, another database with almost the same name (HervD Atlas) was recently made by an unrelated team, storing information about 21790 distinct HERV elements and their associations with as much as 149 human diseases (C. Li et al., 2024).
- Analogous to HERVd, the class-specific L1base focuses exclusively on LINE-1 elements, with particular emphasis on insertional polymorphisms and 5'UTR methylation landscapes (Penzkofer et al., 2017).
- Finally, the HERV Parser database (Garazha et al., 2015) provides both genome browser visualization and tabulated data on sequence divergence and TFBS enrichment within HERV elements, offering a valuable resource for investigating the evolutionary domestication and regulatory integration of these REs.

Together, these databases offer high-resolution structural, evolutionary, and regulatory annotations at the level of individual repeat elements, significantly advancing the field of RE research and shedding light on the molecular dynamics underpinning the evolutionary arms race between transposable elements and the host genome.

Genome-wide investigations into the regulatory influence of human REs commenced on a large scale during the 2010s, catalyzed by the emergence of next-generation sequencing technologies, and have continued to expand substantially throughout the 2020s. Nevertheless, the widespread contribution of human repetitive elements as sources of evolutionarily novel TFBS had already become evident by 2008 (Bourque et al., 2008), when a study examining seven key mammalian transcription factors - ESR1, TP53, MYC, RELA, POU5F1, SOX2, and CTCF - revealed that five of them (ESR1, TP53, POU5F1, SOX2, and CTCF) showed significant association with RE-derived sequences. Notably, the TFBS within these regions exhibited limited sequence conservation, implying that these regulatory sites were introduced through recent RE insertions and subsequently integrated into the host gene regulatory circuitry.

Substantial advances in the epigenomic characterization of human REs have been achieved following the release of the telomere-to-telomere (T2T) human genome assembly. Owing to their highly repetitive nature, REs posed considerable challenges for accurate mapping in earlier genome builds, such as GRCh38 (Hoyt et al., 2022). The T2T assembly has enabled the identification and precise annotation of approximately 1% more Alu elements, 1% more L1 elements, and an additional 0.6–1.2% of elements belonging to the major HERV families, thereby improving the resolution of RE landscapes in the human genome. Moreover, for 118787 repetitive elements out of 4531994 in total (2.6%) their genomic coordinates were refined by the complete genome assembly. Finally, the complete genome assembly included centromeres and revealed that fully active RE elements capable of transpositions are tending to reside within the centromeric high order repeat structures, and these REs maintain transcriptional activity.

Numerous epigenomic studies have utilized the ENCODE database, which compiles comprehensive epigenomic profiles encompassing chromatin modifications, TF binding, chromatin accessibility, and other regulatory features across a broad range of cell lines and tissues (E. P. Consortium, 2012). For instance, an analysis involving 97 transcription factors from the ENCODE and Roadmap Epigenomics (Kundaje et al., 2015) projects investigated their association with HERV elements across six cell lines, identifying 2,201 TFBS specifically linked to REs. These regulatory sequences are likely to have been introduced via recent HERV insertions, thereby influencing the expression of adjacent human genes, particularly those involved in immune responses (Ito et al., 2017). The study employed genome-wide track intersection to detect candidate RE-associated TFBS, followed by ChIP-Seq signal refinement through multiple sequence alignment (Figure 21). An additional epigenomic analysis examining 26 transcription factors across two human and two murine cell lines revealed that approximately 20% (ranging from 2% to 40%) of genome-wide TF binding sites were associated with repetitive elements. Notably, 66% of these RE-linked TFBS exhibited cell type specificity, reinforcing the pivotal role of repetitive elements in shaping the regulatory architecture of human gene expression networks (Sundaram et al., 2014). Intriguingly, a recent study showed that regulatory impact of different RE classes differs depending on essentiality and duplication status of human genes (Correa et al., 2021): SINEs and DNA transposons are enriched near singleton and, surprisingly, essential genes, whereas HERV and LINE elements are preferentially inserted in the vicinity of duplicated genes.

Figure 21. Schematic workflow for the identification of HERV-associated TFBSs and HSREs applied in (Ito et al., 2017). HERV-linked transcription factor binding sites (HERV-TFBSs) and high-site recurrence elements (HSREs) were identified independently using datasets from ENCODE and Roadmap Epigenomics, incorporating both uniquely and multi-mapped TFBS reads.

(A) HERV-TFBSs were detected in each cell type by assessing the genomic overlap between HERV elements and TFBSs. Subsequently, HERV-TFBSs for individual transcription factors were aggregated across cell types to generate merged TFBS sets.

(B) For each HERV type, a multiple sequence alignment (MSA) was generated using their genomic instances aligned to the consensus sequence, and the merged HERV-TFBSs were mapped onto the aligned sequences. Red and pink highlights mark binding sites for transcription factors X and Y, respectively.

(C) TF-binding motifs were scanned within the mapped HERV-TFBSs and projected onto the MSA. Motif instances are denoted by star and triangle symbols for TF X and TF Y, respectively. A collection of motifs was defined as an HSRE if the same motif occurred at a conserved position in more than 60% of the HERV-TFBSs in the alignment. Boxed motifs represent HSREs for TF X and TF Y.

Beyond their influence on epigenetic landscapes, human REs exert substantial regulatory effects on the non-coding transcriptome. Approximately 30% of mature lncRNAs, and nearly two-thirds of total lncRNA sequences, harbor embedded RE fragments. These sequences are often transcribed due to the presence of promoter elements within the RE insertions, highlighting their role in shaping lncRNA expression and regulatory potential (Kapusta et al., 2013).

The regulatory influence of human REs on host gene expression is particularly prominent within the immune system, where REs - especially retroviruses and HERVs - function both as sources of novel regulatory sequences and as persistent pathogenic stimuli (Figure 22). Among these, mammalian-wide interspersed repeats (MIRs), though less extensively characterized than L1 and Alu elements, contribute substantially to immune regulation. In CD4⁺ T cells, for instance, MIR elements supply over a thousand insulator sequences that function as chromatin boundary elements and enhancer blockers, thereby modulating the spatial and temporal dynamics of gene expression in a lineage-specific manner in CD4⁺ T cells (J. Wang et al., 2015). Furthermore, multiple epigenomic investigations have demonstrated that HERV elements contribute substantially - comprising approximately 15–30% - to the total pool of enhancers involved in regulating immune-related gene expression, and functional significance of these elements is validated using CRISPR-based epigenome editing (Buttler & Chuong, 2022; Larson et al., 2013). In particular, interferon-responsive enhancers appear to have been frequently disseminated by lineage-specific HERV insertions across diverse mammalian genomes, thereby driving regulatory innovation within the innate immune system (Chuong et al., 2016). Overall, immune-related genes exhibit a higher density of active RE in their genomic vicinity compared to genes involved in other biological functions, and immune enhancers demonstrate an elevated propensity for the incorporation of RE-derived TFBS (M. Ye et al., 2020). Intriguingly, the same epigenomic investigation revealed a class-specific distribution pattern of REs within enhancer regions: HERV elements predominantly localize to the central domains of enhancers, coinciding with peaks of chromatin accessibility, while SINEs preferentially occupy enhancer boundaries, displaying characteristic nucleosome positioning

and enrichment of the enhancer-associated histone mark H3K4me1, as previously discussed. Application of single cell epigenomic profiling technologies to immune cells could shed more light on cell type-specific functionality of RE-linked regulatory elements (Wimmers et al., 2021).

Figure 22. Retroviruses exert a dual role in shaping the evolution of host immunity, acting both as antagonistic pathogens and as catalysts of regulatory innovation. This figure, adapted from (Buttler & Chuong, 2022), illustrates the intricate interplay between retroviruses - including HERV - and host defense mechanisms. Through occasional endogenization, retroviral sequences may become co-opted to serve beneficial regulatory functions within the host genome. Such co-option events are especially pronounced in the immune system, where HERVs contribute to the dynamic remodeling of gene regulatory networks, facilitating rapid adaptation in the ongoing evolutionary arms race against exogenous viral agents and other immune challenges.

The previously discussed findings on the influence of SINE elements on nucleosome positioning and the binding of CTCF to specific HERV families have paved the way for a new

line of multimodal investigations into the role of REs in shaping the human epigenome - specifically, their contribution to the three-dimensional (3D) organization of the genome (Gasparotto et al., 2023) (Figure 23). SINE elements across multiple mammalian lineages have been shown to harbor binding motifs for CTCF and the cohesin complex, thereby functioning as chromatin boundary elements (insulators) that restrict the propagation of chromatin states and contribute to tissue-specific regulation during embryonic development (Lunyak et al., 2007; Schmidt et al., 2012). In particular, studies in species such as rodents, dogs, and opossums have demonstrated that CTCF-bound DNA motifs often derive from tRNA-related SINEs, which are evolutionarily distinct from the Alu elements predominantly found in the human genome (Azazi et al., 2020; Kaaij et al., 2019; Lunyak et al., 2007). Moreover, transcribed HERV-H elements establish boundaries between topologically associated domains and regulate adjacent gene expression in humans and other hominids, also demonstrating insulator properties (Y. Zhang et al., 2019).

An increasing body of evidence indicates that RNAs transcribed from REs contribute to the spatial organization of the genome by influencing the formation of nuclear subcompartments. For instance, highly expressed RE-derived transcripts - including those originating from LINE-1 elements - are predominantly localized within euchromatic regions of interphase nuclei, where they help establish distinct chromosomal territories that display resistance to mechanical compression (Hall et al., 2014). In fertilized mouse oocytes, transcriptional activation of LINE-1 elements contributes to chromatin remodeling and initiates developmental gene expression programs by modulating chromatin accessibility (Jachowicz et al., 2017). Notably, the differential distribution of the three principal classes of human REs near host genes appears to influence their three-dimensional positioning within nuclear subcompartments. SINE elements tend to be embedded within exons of housekeeping genes; LINE-1 elements are predominantly enriched near genes exhibiting tissue-, cell type-, or function-specific expression; while HERVs are commonly situated adjacent to genes involved in transcriptional regulation and developmental pathways (J. Y. Lu et al., 2020). Consequently, depending on the cellular differentiation state, transcripts derived from distinct RE classes guide associated host genes toward active or repressive chromatin compartments, thereby shaping their regulatory environment.

Ultimately, heterochromatin - and specifically the heterochromatinization induced by REs - contributes to the formation of specialized nuclear subcompartments that engage in dynamic interactions with euchromatin through phase separation mechanisms (L. Frank & Rippe, 2020; Haws et al., 2022). Variability in HERV expression may modulate the structural and

regulatory properties of these compartments. Supporting this, single-cell epigenomic profiling of mouse embryonic cells revealed that HERV reactivation leads to the dissociation of RNA polymerase II and the Mediator complex from pluripotency-associated genes and their subsequent relocation to HERV-enriched nuclear domains (Asimi et al., 2022). When considered alongside the differential spatial distribution of LINES, SINEs, and LTR elements near genes of distinct functional categories, these findings suggest that REs may contribute to the establishment of a genome-wide three-dimensional regulatory architecture capable of influencing cell lineage specification. This emerging model requires further investigation, particularly through the application of single-cell multimodal omics technologies.

A. TAD boundary

B. Gene compartmentation

C. Transcriptional condensates

Figure 23. RE elements contribute to the spatial organization of the genome, adapted from (Gasparotto et al., 2023). This schematic illustrates several mechanisms by which TEs influence three-dimensional genome architecture. (A) Accumulation of HERV-H transcripts can impede the movement of the cohesin complex, thereby establishing (topologically associating domain) boundaries; (B) TEs influence the spatial positioning of genes within the nucleus according to

their sequence characteristics and functionality: housekeeping genes are enriched in SINEs in their vicinity and associate in active nucleic subcompartments, whereas specialized genes are enriched with L1 elements and localize in the less active lamina-associated domains (LADs) and nucleolus-associated domains (NADs). (C) RE-derived RNAs participate in the formation of transcriptional condensates with conditional switching capability. On the left, in the absence of active HERV transcription, RNA Polymerase II (Pol II) and associated coactivators are localized at super-enhancer (SE) regions. On the right, during active HERV expression, these factors are sequestered into HERV-associated condensates, thereby altering the transcriptional landscape.

A distinct line of investigation has focused on genome-wide alterations in the epigenetic landscape of REs under pathological or dynamically regulated conditions. For instance, a methylome analysis of human mammary luminal epithelial cells revealed that evolutionarily recent REs - inserted within the last 100 million years, particularly Alu elements - undergo progressive demethylation with aging, a trend markedly accentuated in breast cancer. This hypomethylation facilitates the binding of lineage-specific transcription factors, thereby contributing to oncogenic regulatory reprogramming (Senapati et al., 2023). Moreover, in colorectal cancer, a subset of enhancers derived from the primate-specific HERV family LTR10 becomes transcriptionally active in response to oncogenic MAPK/AP-1 signaling. This activation contributes to the upregulation of genes implicated in tumorigenic processes, including *ATG12* and *XRCCA4*, thereby linking RE-derived regulatory sequences to cancer-associated transcriptional networks (Ivancevic et al., 2024). Dysregulated activation of RE-associated regulatory elements is also prominently observed in autoimmune disorders. In the case of multiple sclerosis, for instance, HERV-linked atypical T-cell enhancers - normally engaged only under transient stress conditions - exhibit persistent and chronic activation, suggesting their potential contribution to disease pathology through aberrant immune regulation (Azébi et al., 2019).

Collectively, the accumulating body of evidence underscores the pervasive regulatory influence of human REs on host gene expression, epigenetic landscapes, and the spatial organization of the genome. Initially emerging as transcriptionally repressed sequences with predominantly deleterious consequences, REs are increasingly co-opted into host regulatory networks. In this process, host defense mechanisms - such as heterochromatinization, RNA interference, family specific repressive transcription factors - acquire functional significance, while RE-associated TFBSs become gradually rewired into core gene regulatory frameworks.

This trajectory bears strong resemblance to the principles of constructive neutral evolution, as previously discussed: marginally deleterious epigenomic changes accumulating post-insertion may render an RE locus indispensable, such that its subsequent loss would compromise regulatory integrity. This hypothesis invites comprehensive evolutionary analyses tracking RE insertion dynamics across evolutionary lineages. Moreover, functional investigations of RE-mediated regulation - spanning distinct RE classes, epigenomic modalities, and evolutionary timescales - are critical to elucidate the balance of conflict and cooperation that shapes host-RE interactions. The present thesis is devoted to address this important evolutionary question.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Epigenome data

2.1.1. Epigenome data obtaining

We conducted a tiered analysis utilizing ChIP-seq and RNA-seq datasets from the ENCODE consortium. For the focused analysis of RE-linked TFBSs within two defined evolutionary age intervals in a single cell line (Nikitin et al., 2018), genome-wide binding profiles of 225 transcription factors were obtained for the K562 human cell line from the ENCODE database according to the standard ENCODE ChIP-seq protocol (E. P. Consortium, 2012). To expand this approach to a broader context independent of RE evolutionary age (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019), we extracted complete binding profiles for 563 transcription factors across 13 human cell lines (K562, HepG2, HEK293, GM12878, MCF-7, A549, HeLa-S3, SK-N-SH, HCT116, Ishikawa, HEK293T, MCF-10A, GM12891), using the same ChIP-seq processing standards. In parallel, for the assessment of RE-linked chromatin landscape features (Igolkina et al., 2019; Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019), we retrieved genome-wide datasets for six histone modifications (H3K4me1, H3K4me3, H3K9ac, H3K27ac, H3K27me3, and H3K9me3) in five cell lines (K562, HepG2, GM12878, MCF-7, and HeLa-S3), again in accordance with the standard ENCODE ChIP-seq pipeline.

To complement the epigenomic data with transcriptomic insights, we additionally obtained RNA sequencing-based gene expression profiles from the ENCODE database. These were selected using the filters “transcription,” “total RNA-Seq,” and “gene quantifications.” In total,

19 RNA-seq experiments with two technical replicates each were identified: 11 for K562, 5 for HepG2, and 3 for GM12878 cell lines (Igolkina et al., 2019).

2.1.2. Epigenome data processing

The 2009 human reference genome assembly (hg19) was indexed using the Burrows–Wheeler algorithm implemented in BWA software (version 0.7.10) (*ChIP-Seq Read Mapping – ENCODE*, n.d.). Processing of sequencing reads, including concatenation of FASTQ files (single-end or paired-end), alignment to the reference genome, and subsequent filtering, was conducted using a suite of bioinformatic tools: BWA, Samtools (version 1.0), Picard (version 1.92), Bedtools (version 2.17.0), and PhantomPeakQualTools (version 1.1) (*ChIP-Seq Read Mapping – ENCODE*, n.d.). Genome-wide occupancy data for TFBSs and histone modifications were derived from *bedGraph* files containing peaks filtered by a conservative Irreproducible Discovery Rate (IDR) threshold, in accordance with the standard ENCODE ChIP-seq analytical pipeline (*Genome Browser BedGraph Track Format*, n.d.).

Signal intensity profiles - representing fold enrichment over control for both TFBSs and chromatin modifications - as well as associated p-value distributions (testing the null hypothesis of no enrichment relative to control) were generated using MACS software (version 2.1.0) (Feng et al., 2011; *Transcription Factor ChIP-Seq – ENCODE*, n.d.; Y. Zhang et al., 2008), based on the mapped alignments. Quality control of all TFBS and histone mark peak calls was rigorously assessed using IDR-based reproducibility measures, following ENCODE project guidelines (Kharchenko et al., 2008; Q. Li et al., 2011; Marinov et al., 2014).

2.1.3. Epigenome data mapping on REs and genes

For each investigated cell line, aligned, filtered, and control-normalized ChIP-seq signal intensity profiles were projected onto RE coordinates annotated by RepeatMasker (version 3.2.7) (Tarailo-Graovac & Chen, 2009), as obtained from the RepeatMasker table via the UCSC Genome Browser (*Human Hg38 Chr7:155799529-155812871 UCSC Genome Browser V487*, n.d.). Genomic coordinates for human protein-coding genes were also retrieved from the UCSC Browser (RefGenes table, genome assembly hg19) (Pruitt et al., 2005, 2014; *Schema for RefGene*, n.d.), encompassing a total of 24,389 protein-coding genes.

For the subsequent analyses, all individual RE instances located within a 10-kilobase (kb) window centered around the TSS of each gene were selected (10 kb TSS neighbourhood). This window extended from 5 kb upstream to 5 kb downstream of the annotated TSS, defining the proximal gene neighborhood used to assess RE-associated regulatory potential.

2.2. Quantification of RE regulatory impact onto host gene expression and molecular pathway activity

2.2.1. Evaluation of evolutionary age of mapped REs

For each RE family, the average sequence divergence from the consensus sequence was utilized as an assessment for evolutionary age. REs exhibiting less than 8% divergence were classified as the evolutionarily younger subset, approximately corresponding to insertions that occurred after the divergence of the human lineage from New World monkeys (Giordano et al., 2007). In contrast, the larger group including all REs reflected the broader landscape of RE-driven genomic remodeling since the emergence of major eutherian lineages (Giordano et al., 2007).

Enrichment analyses for genes and molecular pathways associated with RE-linked TFBS were conducted separately for the full set of REs and the evolutionarily young fraction (Nikitin et al., 2018; Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019). The average divergence values were derived from annotations generated by RepeatMasker software (Tarailo-Graovac & Chen, 2009).

2.2.2. Overview of the RetroSpect method

The complete analytical framework for quantifying the regulatory influence of REs was designated *RetroSpect*. This pipeline is designed to identify genes and molecular pathways affected by RE-associated regulatory features, such as TFBS or histone modification peaks (Nikitin, Sorokin, et al., 2019) (Figure 24). By jointly mapping epigenomic signals onto both gene loci and RE coordinates, *RetroSpect* enables the assessment of tag enrichment at the level of individual genes and selected molecular pathways. This approach facilitates functional interpretation of RE-mediated regulatory effects across different evolutionary timescales and among distinct RE classes and families.

Figure 24. Schematic representation of the *RetroSpect* analytical framework. The pipeline integrates three genomic annotation layers: RE coordinates, 10-kb neighborhoods surrounding gene TSS, and coordinates of epigenomic peaks (e.g., TFBS, open chromatin regions, histone modifications). For each gene, epigenomic peaks are classified as either RE-associated or non-RE-associated, enabling quantification of RE-linked regulatory input. These data are used to compute enrichment scores for RE-associated epigenetic features at both gene and molecular pathway levels. Comparative analysis of these metrics identifies genes and pathways significantly enriched in RE-linked regulatory marks - suggestive of rapid regulatory evolution driven by recent RE insertions. This methodology can be flexibly applied to specific RE classes, families, or defined evolutionary age groups.

2.2.3. Gene-level metrics of RE regulatory impact

The conceptual framework underlying gene-level metrics of RE-mediated regulatory impact is illustrated in Figure 25. These metrics are designed to quantitatively capture both the absolute and relative enrichment of individual genes with RE-associated epigenetic marks, serving as indicators of potential regulatory activity linked to REs.

High GRE = High number of RE-linked TFBS in a gene
High NGRE = High proportion of RE-linked TFBS in a gene

Figure 25. Schematic representation and formulas illustrating the calculation of gene-level metrics for quantifying RE-associated regulatory impact, accompanied by a numerical example. The procedure is demonstrated using TFBS data but is equally applicable to other epigenomic features, including histone modifications, chromatin accessibility, and DNA methylation.

Gene RE-linked regulatory elements enrichment score (GRE Score). To quantify the relative enrichment of RE-associated regulatory elements in the vicinity of a given gene, we introduced a metric termed the *gene RE-linked regulatory elements enrichment score (GRE score)*. Conceptually, the GRE score for a specific gene reflects the number of RE-linked regulatory elements (e.g., TFBS, histone modifications) located within a ± 5 kb window surrounding its TSS, normalized to the genome-wide average across all annotated genes. This score enables assessment of whether a gene is disproportionately impacted by RE-derived regulatory features. For each gene, the GRE score is computed according to the following formula:

$$GRE_g = \frac{TES_g}{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n TES_i}$$

where GRE_g denotes the GRE score for a given gene g ; TES_g represents the number of filtered and control-normalized ChIP-seq reads mapped to RE sequences within the 10 kb neighborhood of gene g ; i refers to the index of each gene in the dataset; and TES_i is the corresponding number of RE-linked ChIP-seq reads for gene i ; and n is the total number of protein-coding genes analyzed in the study.

For each gene, the GRE score enables quantitative assessment of the degree to which its regulatory landscape is enriched with RE-linked elements. A GRE score of 1 indicates an average level of RE-mediated regulatory influence relative to the entire gene set, while a GRE score exceeding 1 signifies an above-average enrichment of RE-associated regulatory features. Conversely, a GRE score below 1 denotes a lower-than-average RE contribution to the gene's regulatory environment.

To further refine this measure and account for the overall density of regulatory elements near individual genes, the *normalized gene RE-linked regulatory elements enrichment score (NGRE score)* was introduced. This metric quantifies the proportion of RE-linked regulatory elements among all regulatory elements (RE-linked and non-RE-linked) within the 10 kb vicinity of the TSS of a given gene. Since genes vary in their overall regulatory complexity and in the number of associated epigenomic features, the NGRE score provides a gene-specific normalization. While the GRE score evaluates RE-linked regulatory enrichment in relation to the global gene set, the NGRE score captures the relative contribution of REs to the total regulatory architecture of an individual gene, offering insights into whether its transcriptional regulation is disproportionately influenced by RE insertions.

The *NGRE* metric was defined for a given gene g according to the following formula:

$$NGRE_g = GRE_g / GTE_g$$

In this equation, the GRE_g value represents the RE-specific regulatory enrichment previously described, while the GTE_g (*Gene total regulatory enrichment*) score reflects the overall abundance of regulatory elements - both RE-linked and non-RE-linked - in the vicinity of the gene. The GTE value provides a normalization baseline by accounting for gene-specific tendencies in regulatory element density, and is calculated as follows:

$$GTE_g = \frac{TTS_g}{TTS_m}$$

where TTS_g represents the total number of filtered and control-normalized ChIP-seq reads mapped within the 10-kb region surrounding the TSS of gene g , while TTS_m denotes the *average total signal (TTS)* calculated across all genes included in the analysis.

A higher *NGRE* score indicates a greater proportion of a gene's regulatory landscape is shaped specifically by RE-linked elements, relative to its overall regulatory input.

Conversely, lower *NGRE* values suggest a smaller RE-specific contribution to the gene's regulation.

2.2.4. Molecular pathways databases

Gene architecture information for molecular pathways was obtained from several databases, including BioCarta (*BioCarta -- Online Maps of Metabolic and Signaling Pathways | HSLs*, n.d.), KEGG (Kanehisa et al., 2024; *KEGG PATHWAY Database*, n.d.), NCI (Krupa et al., 2007) and Reactome (*Home - Reactome Pathway Database*, n.d.). Pathway structural data were downloaded in *.xml* and *biopax* formats and integrated into the Oncobox computational platform (Aliper et al., 2017; A. Buzdin et al., 2019; Gudkov et al., 2022). For each analyzed cell line, both absolute (PII) and relative (NPII) RE-linked regulatory enrichment scores were computed for a total of 3,095 molecular pathways as described in the following section.

2.2.5. Calculation of RE-linked regulatory impact at the level of molecular pathways

The conceptual framework underlying molecular pathway level metrics of RE-mediated regulatory impact is illustrated in Figure 26. Similarly to the gene level metrics, these pathway level ones are meant to quantitatively assess both the absolute and relative enrichment of molecular pathways with RE-associated epigenetic marks.

Pathway Involvement Index (PII)
Normalized Pathway Involvement Index (NPII)

$$PII_p = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n GRE_i}{n}$$

(sum of **GRE** for all pathway genes)
(number of genes in a pathway)

$$PGI_p = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n GTE_i}{n}$$

(sum of **GTE** for all pathway genes)
(number of genes in a pathway)

Normalized PII (NPII)

$$NPII_p = \frac{PII_p}{PGI_p}$$

(PII for pathway *p*)
(PGI for pathway *p*)

High PII = High number of RE-linked TFBS for pathway components

High NPII = High proportion of RE-linked TFBS for pathway components

Figure 26. Description of formulas illustrating the calculation of molecular pathway level metrics for assessment RE-associated regulatory impact. The procedure is equally

applicable to all epigenomic features, including TFBS, histone modifications, chromatin accessibility, and DNA methylation.

Pathway involvement index (PII). To quantitatively evaluate the cumulative influence of RE-linked regulatory elements on the transcriptional regulation of a given molecular pathway, a metric termed *Pathway involvement index (PII)* was introduced. The PII score for a specific pathway p is defined as:

$$PII_p = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n GRE_i}{n}$$

where PII_p is the Pathway involvement index for a pathway p ; GRE_i represents the *gene RE-linked regulatory elements enrichment score* (as defined in the previous section) for the i -th gene within the pathway; n denotes the total number of genes annotated in pathway p .

To account for potential inflation of the PII score due to variation in pathway size, normalization by the number of constituent genes was performed. A higher PII value indicates a greater absolute contribution of RE-linked regulatory elements to the transcriptional regulation of the pathway. However, this measure alone does not contextualize RE impact relative to the pathway's total regulatory input. To address this, a complementary metric was developed.

Normalized pathway involvement index (NPII). The *NPII* metric was devised to assess the relative proportion of RE-mediated transcriptional regulation within the context of a pathway's overall regulatory landscape. It is defined as:

$$NPII_p = PII_p / PGI_p,$$

where PII_p is the Pathway involvement index for pathway p as previously defined; PGI_p is the *Pathway gene-based index*, which estimates the cumulative impact of all regulatory elements (both RE-linked and non-RE-linked) for pathway p , and is calculated as:

$$PGI_p = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n GTE_i}{n}$$

where GTE_i represents the *gene total regulatory enrichment score* (defined in the previous section) for the i -th gene and n indicates the number of genes in pathway p .

A higher NPPII score signifies a greater proportion of RE-linked transcriptional regulation relative to total regulatory input, thereby highlighting pathways with disproportionately high reliance on RE-mediated regulation. Conversely, lower NPPII values suggest a minor role for REs in the overall transcriptional governance of the pathway.

2.2.6. Selection of genes and molecular pathways that are enriched or deficient by RE-linked regulatory impact

To identify genes exhibiting either enrichment or depletion in regulatory elements associated with REs, we employed a comparative analysis of GRE and NGRE scores. Following the original RetroSpect methodology (Nikitin, Sorokin, et al., 2019), for each TF or chromatin modification profile in each cell line, a scatter plot of NGRE versus GRE values was constructed. A linear trend line was fitted to the data using the least squares regression method (Charnes et al., 1976).

Genes exhibiting the greatest deviation from this expected trend were selected based on their orthogonal distance from the regression line. Specifically, the top 10% of genes with disproportionately high NGRE scores relative to their GRE values were classified as **RE-enriched**, indicating a greater-than-expected contribution of RE-linked regulatory elements in the context of the gene's overall regulatory landscape. Conversely, the bottom 10% of genes, exhibiting lower-than-expected NGRE scores, were designated as **RE-deficient**, reflecting relative depletion of RE-associated regulatory input.

Depending on the research objective, the epigenomic profiles of distinct transcription factors across multiple cell lines - or alternatively, a single chromatin modification assayed in different cell lines - could be aggregated to derive composite GRE and NGRE scores. This integrative approach enabled robust identification of gene sets that are consistently enriched or depleted in RE-linked regulation across diverse regulatory conditions.

The same analytical framework was extended to the level of molecular pathways by substituting GRE and NGRE scores with PII and NPPII values, respectively. This allowed for the detection of biological pathways disproportionately affected by RE-mediated regulatory elements, thereby providing insight into broader functional consequences of RE integration into host regulatory networks.

2.3. Functional analysis of the extracted gene sets

2.3.1. Measuring enrichment of gene sets by non-coding RNA genes

To evaluate whether the proportions of non-coding RNA genes were significantly overrepresented or underrepresented within the selected gene sets, statistical testing was performed using the hypergeometric distribution (Garcia-Moreno et al., 2022; B. Kim, 2018). This analysis was conducted independently for two major classes of non-coding RNAs: microRNAs and lncRNAs.

For each gene set under consideration, the probability of observing a given number - or more extreme counts - of genes belonging to either the microRNA or lncRNA category was computed using the hypergeometric probability mass function, defined as follows:

$$p(k, M, n, N) = \frac{\binom{n}{k} \binom{M-n}{N-k}}{\binom{M}{N}}$$

where M is the total number of genes in the background set, N is the total number of genes in the background set belonging to the RNA class of interest (microRNA or lncRNA), n is the number of genes in the selected gene set (e.g., top genes enriched or deficient in RE-linked regulation), k is the observed number of genes from the RNA class of interest within the gene set and $p(k, M, n, N)$ is the probability of observation of gene numbers k, M, n, N . Brackets denote binomial coefficients.

For each observed number k of non-coding RNA genes in a given gene set, the probability of observing a greater number by chance was computed using the cumulative upper tail of the hypergeometric distribution, as follows:

$$P(k, M, n, N) = \sum_{i=k+1}^n p(i, M, n, N)$$

where $p(i, M, n, N)$ denotes the hypergeometric probability mass function defined previously, M is the total number of non-coding RNA genes in the background population, n is the size of the selected gene set, N is the total number of genes in the background population, and k is the observed count of non-coding RNA genes in the set under investigation. A significance threshold of $p < 0.05$ was used to determine statistical overrepresentation of non-coding RNA genes in the gene set. Conversely, $p > 0.95$ was used as a criterion to reject the hypothesis of overrepresentation.

In a parallel computation, the probability of observing k or fewer non-coding RNA genes was computed using the cumulative lower tail of the hypergeometric distribution:

$$P'(k, M, n, N) = \sum_{i=1}^k p(i, M, n, N)$$

where $p(i, M, n, N)$ is the hypergeometric probability mass function defined above, M is the overall quantity of non-coding RNA genes in the background population, n is the size of the gene set of interest, N is the overall count of genes in the background population, and k is the observed count of non-coding RNA genes in the selected gene set. This calculation enabled the assessment of significant underrepresentation of non-coding RNA genes. Similarly, a value of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant for depletion, while $p > 0.95$ indicated no significant underrepresentation.

This statistical framework, applied separately for microRNA and lncRNA, enabled rigorous testing of whether non-coding RNA gene classes are significantly enriched or depleted in specific gene sets, thereby providing insight into their potential regulatory roles in association with RE-driven transcriptional programs.

2.3.2. Gene ontology enrichment analysis

Functional annotation of genes enriched or depleted in RE-associated TFBS and histone modification peaks - hereafter referred to as RE-enriched and RE-deficient genes, respectively - was conducted via Gene Ontology (GO) analysis (G. O. Consortium et al., 2023) using the DAVID bioinformatics platform (*DAVID Functional Annotation Bioinformatics Microarray Analysis*, n.d.; Huang et al., 2009b). Human gene identifiers were obtained from the

UCSC Genome Browser (*Human Hg38 Chr7:155799529-155812871 UCSC Genome Browser V487*, n.d.) and served as input for the enrichment analysis.

Visualization of GO terms, including hierarchical structure and interconnectivity, was performed using the Gorilla (Eden et al., 2009) and ShinyGO (Ge et al., 2020) web-based tools. Statistical significance of GO-term enrichment was determined using a modified version of Fisher's exact test (Huang et al., 2009a) with a p-value threshold of 0.05 applied to identify significantly overrepresented categories.

Enrichment scores for both individual GO terms and broader annotation clusters were computed as fold enrichment, defined as the ratio of term frequency in the input gene set to its expected frequency in the human genome background (Huang et al., 2009a). This approach enabled quantitative assessment of functional categories preferentially associated with RE-mediated regulatory activity.

2.3.3. Significance of correlations

The strength and statistical significance of pairwise correlations were assessed using the Pearson correlation coefficient, accompanied by the corresponding p-value. These calculations were performed utilizing the Sklearn statistical package in Python (Pedregosa et al., 2011). All data handling and computational procedures were implemented using the Pandas (McKinney, 2010) and Numpy (C. R. Harris et al., 2020) libraries.

2.3.4. Significance of gene ontology analysis

To evaluate the robustness and statistical confidence of functional enrichment patterns associated with RE-linked gene regulation, a permutation-based approach was employed (Guo et al., 2009; Koopmans, 2024). Specifically, 500 randomized datasets were generated by permuting GRE and NGRE scores across the analyzed cell lines through random shuffling of gene identifiers. For each permuted dataset, gene sets enriched or depleted in RE-linked regulation were identified following the standard RetroSpect pipeline (Nikitin, Sorokin, et al., 2019), which involves selecting top and bottom genes based on GRE-NGRE

scatter plot deviations. Functional profiling of each resulting gene set was conducted using DAVID software, and the top 100 GO terms were retained based on the lowest p-values obtained in each permutation. Subsequently, the distributions of p-values for the top-100 GO terms from the permuted gene sets were compared to those from the original, unpermuted RE-enriched and RE-deficient gene sets, thereby allowing for the assessment of statistical significance of the observed functional enrichments.

2.3.5. Visualization and dimensional reduction

All graphical representations were generated using standard Python libraries, including Matplotlib (Hunter, 2007) and Seaborn (Waskom, 2021). Dimensionality reduction of high-dimensional datasets was performed using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) (Jolliffe & Cadima, 2016) and Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) (McInnes et al., 2018), both widely established methods for unsupervised data visualization. Modified Venn diagrams illustrating set intersections were constructed using the Supervenn Python library (Indukaev, 2021).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. RE-linked TFBS analysis in the single K562 cell line in two evolutionary timescales

3.1.1. Mapping of RE-specific human TFBS in K562 cell line

To investigate the regulatory contribution of RE in a transcriptionally active cellular context, we firstly analyzed TFBS data from the ENCODE project, focusing on the human myelogenous leukemia cell line K562. This cell line was selected due to its extensive epigenomic characterization (Karagiannis et al., 2023), including the largest number of profiled transcription factor proteins at the time of analysis (225 factors, compared to 120 in the next most characterized cell line, GM12878). TFBS profiles were derived from high-

throughput sequencing of DNA fragments immunoprecipitated with transcription factor-specific antibodies (Nikitin et al., 2018; Sloan et al., 2016).

All available TFBS datasets for K562 were mapped onto the genomic coordinates of human REs. For enrichment of TFBS events with higher potential regulatory relevance, only binding sites within ± 5 kilobases of TSS of annotated protein-coding genes were considered. This 10-kb promoter-proximal region yielded a total of 13,029,963 TFBS peaks, of which 2,232,273 (~17%) overlapped with annotated RE sequences, constituting the RE-associated TFBS fraction.

Within this RE-specific TFBS subset, approximately 44% were located within SINE elements, 33% within LINEs, and 23% within HERVs. The majority of REs harboring TFBS were evolutionarily older, exhibiting substantial divergence from their consensus sequences. Notably, only 154,275 TFBS (~7% of all RE-linked TFBS) were mapped to evolutionarily younger elements (defined as having $\leq 8\%$ sequence divergence from their respective consensus), suggesting limited TF binding activity within recent insertions, which corresponds with the currently prevailing model of newly inserted REs co-option (A. A. Buzdin et al., 2017; Garazha et al., 2015). Among these younger REs, the distribution of TFBS was further skewed towards SINEs (~68%), followed by HERVs (~17%) and LINEs (~15%) (Figure 27B). This observation indicates that, within the context of recent evolutionary timescales, SINE elements have exhibited approximately 55% greater activity compared to LINEs and HERVs in contributing functional TFBS.

For comparison, the genomic distribution of RE-linked TFBS outside promoter-proximal regions is depicted in Figure 27A. Of particular interest, we observed a marked depletion of active TFBS within evolutionarily young LINE elements situated near gene promoters, suggesting that these recent LINE insertions are either selectively silenced or intrinsically less competent in supporting TF binding within gene-regulatory contexts (Figure 27B). This pattern may reflect evolutionary constraints acting against LINE-mediated regulatory interference in genic regions. Although certain RE families, such as Alu and L1 REs, retain transpositional activity in the human genome and may theoretically contribute to cell line-specific insertions, these elements constitute a minor portion of the RE landscape and are unlikely to significantly affect the global patterns of RE-linked TFBS distribution observed in the current K562 analysis.

Figure 27. Distribution of TFBS associated with REs across different genomic contexts in the K562 cell line. (A) Genome-wide distribution of RE-linked TFBS outside promoter-proximal regions (i.e., beyond ± 5 kb from TSS) by RE class and evolutionary timeframe. (B) Distribution of RE-linked TFBS within 10-kb TSS-centered neighborhoods of protein-coding genes by the same parameters. Blue bars represent TFBS associated with all annotated REs regardless of divergence level, while green bars specifically denote TFBS mapped to evolutionarily young REs, defined as those exhibiting $\leq 8\%$ divergence from their respective consensus sequences. This comparative visualization highlights the differential contribution of RE subtypes to TF binding landscapes across genic and intergenic regions.

Moreover, TFBS associated with LINE elements are more abundant than those linked to SINEs outside gene-proximal regions, while the opposite trend is observed in the vicinity of gene TSS (Figure 27). Collectively, these observations also support the hypothesis that recent insertions of LINEs and HERVs exert a more deleterious impact on the human genome compared to SINE insertions (Bannert & Kurth, 2004; Gonçalves et al., 2017; Grandi et al., 2016).

To further assess the functional regulatory potential of RE in promoter-proximal regions, we calculated the relative density of RE-associated TFBS per kilobase within 10-kb neighborhoods flanking TSS, stratified by RE class (Table 2). The analysis revealed that evolutionarily young REs ($\leq 8\%$ divergence from consensus sequences) exhibit a markedly reduced capacity to harbor TFBS, approximately 14-fold lower on average compared to the

entire RE pool. These findings are consistent with the previously proposed hypothesis that newly inserted REs into the host genome are initially subjected to strong transcriptional repression. This silencing is maintained until the elements acquire a sufficient number of mutations over time (A. A. Buzdin et al., 2017). The depletion was observed across all major RE classes, with the extent of suppression varying by type: HERV elements showed a ~14-fold decrease, LINES demonstrated the strongest reduction at ~32-fold, and SINEs exhibited a ~9-fold decrease. In terms of absolute TFBS concentration per kilobase, values ranged from ~0.1 for HERV and LINES to ~0.4 for SINEs, indicating both quantitative and qualitative differences in the regulatory potential of RE classes across evolutionary strata (Table 2).

Table 2. Relative density of RE-associated TFBS within 10-kilobase promoter-proximal regions flanking human gene TSS. Values reflect the concentration of TFBS per kilobase for distinct RE classes, enabling comparative assessment of their regulatory potential between the classes and evolutionary age groups.

RE class	All	Young	Fold change
LINE	2.939	0.093	-31.6
SINE	3.892	0.416	-9.4
LR/ERV	1.457	0.107	-13.6
Total REs	8.287	0.616	-13.5

3.1.2. Calculating gene level scores of RE-linked TFBS regulation

For every individual gene, we calculated its enrichment scores for the RE-linked TFBS: GRE and NGRE. As described in the Materials and Methods section, the GRE score enables quantification of the extent to which individual genes are enriched in RE-associated regulatory features. A GRE value of 1 indicates an average level of RE-linked transcriptional influence across all protein-coding genes. GRE scores greater than 1 denote above-average enrichment of RE-associated TFBS, while values below 1 indicate a relative depletion of such regulatory elements in the vicinity of a gene's TSS.

Our analysis revealed a distinct subset of protein-coding genes exhibiting substantial enrichment in RE-linked TFBS, with GRE scores reaching values as high as 5 (Table S1 in supplementary material in (Nikitin et al., 2018), Figure 28). In contrast, a considerable

number of genes showed minimal or negligible RE-specific regulatory influence, as reflected by GRE values approaching zero (Figure 28). This effect was pronounced for evolutionary young RE families (Figure 28B).

While GRE provides a cumulative metric reflecting the influence of all 225 TFs profiled for K562 cell line in this study, we further investigated the contribution of individual TFs to RE-mediated gene regulation. For each gene i and transcription factor j , we computed the number of TFBS associated with REs located within a 10-kb region surrounding the TSS of gene i . This yielded a matrix of RE-linked regulatory interactions indexed as (i, j) , capturing gene-specific TF targeting via RE sequences. The results indicate that most human genes are modulated by RE-linked TFBS belonging to multiple distinct transcription factors (Table S2 in supplementary material in (Nikitin et al., 2018)).

Figure 28. Distribution of GRE scores across annotated human protein-coding genes. (A) GRE score distribution based on the subset of evolutionarily young repetitive elements (defined as 0–8% sequence divergence from their respective consensus sequences). (B) GRE score distribution calculated using the complete set of repetitive elements, regardless of evolutionary age.

3.1.3. Genes affected by RE-linked TFBS regulation in the K562 cell line

To assess the differential impact of RE-associated transcriptional regulation, human protein-coding genes were ranked based on their GRE scores, which ranged from 0 to 16.4 (Figure 28B; table S1 in supplementary material in (Nikitin et al., 2018)). Subsequent functional enrichment analysis was performed on the genes within the top and bottom 6% of GRE scores, representing those with the highest and lowest inferred influence of RE-linked

TFBS, respectively. GO term enrichment was evaluated using the DAVID functional annotation tool.

3.1.3.1. Top GRE-scoring genes

Among the genes in the top 6% GRE score quantile, 48 statistically significant annotation clusters were identified (table S3 in supplementary material in (Nikitin et al., 2018)). Notably, 17% of these clusters were associated with ribosome biogenesis and translation, 15% with protein complex assembly, 10% with chromatin organization and nuclear architecture, and another 10% with cellular stress responses and innate immunity. Additional enriched categories included microtubule dynamics and mitotic spindle organization (6%), regulation of programmed cell death (6%), purine-related oxidoreductase activity (6%), DNA replication and repair mechanisms (4%), mitochondrial outer membrane complex formation (4%), and autophagy regulation (4%). Individual clusters were also found to be involved in p53-mediated signaling and nucleolar integrity maintenance. A diverse array of additional processes was captured in clusters of lesser prevalence.

3.1.3.2. Bottom GRE-scoring genes

In contrast, the bottom 6% of genes - characterized by minimal or absent RE-specific TFBS enrichment - were enriched for a distinct set of 96 annotation clusters (table S3 in supplementary material in (Nikitin et al., 2018)). Of these, a striking 83% were directly associated with embryonic development and differentiation pathways. Additional cluster categories included TF complex formation (8%), neuronal axonogenesis (2%), intercellular adhesion and signaling (2%), and positive regulation of cell proliferation (2%). These findings highlight the functional divergence between genes highly impacted and those largely unaffected by RE-linked regulatory elements. It is important to emphasize, however, that GRE scores alone do not capture the relative contribution of RE-linked elements within the full regulatory context of a given gene. High GRE values may reflect substantial absolute enrichment of RE-associated TFBS, yet these elements may still constitute only a minor component of the gene's overall transcriptional regulation - particularly in cases where the gene is highly expressed in K562 cells under the influence of multiple regulatory inputs.

3.1.4. Molecular pathways influenced by RE-linked TFBS regulation in the K562 cell line

To investigate the functional processes most strongly affected by RE-associated transcriptional regulation, we ranked molecular pathways according to their enrichment in RE-linked TFBS. The analysis was restricted to pathways comprising at least ten gene products, and rankings were based on PII scores (table S4 in supplementary material in (Nikitin et al., 2018)). A total of 130 pathways were selected for in-depth analysis: 65 with the highest PII scores (top pathways) and 65 with the lowest (bottom pathways).

3.1.4.1. Top ranked pathways

The most RE-enriched pathways (highest PII values) were predominantly involved in core cellular functions. Among them, 15 pathways (24%) were associated with DNA replication and repair; 19% with ribosome biogenesis and protein translation; 11% with cytoskeletal remodeling and cell migration; 10% with nuclear mRNA transport; and another 10% with alternative nuclear trafficking mechanisms. Additional categories included cell stress and innate immune responses (6%), vesicular trafficking and cellular export (6%), microtubule regulation and mitotic spindle assembly (3%), mRNA decay processes (3%), and other functions (8%) (table S5 in supplementary material in (Nikitin et al., 2018)). These data suggest that RE-linked TFBS regulation preferentially impacts pathways involved in protein synthesis, nuclear transport, DNA maintenance, and cytoskeletal dynamics.

3.1.4.2. Bottom ranked pathways

In contrast, the least RE-impacted pathways (lowest PII scores) were enriched for processes associated with development and extracellular signaling. Specifically, 18 pathways (30%) were related to extracellular matrix remodeling and cell migration; 16% to interleukin-mediated signaling; 21% to neurogenesis; and 15% to embryogenesis and morphogenesis. Additional categories included PTEN-associated signaling pathways (3%), G protein-coupled receptor (GPCR) pathways (3%), fatty acid metabolism (3%), and miscellaneous

processes (9%) (table S5 in supplementary material in (Nikitin et al., 2018)). These findings suggest that RE-linked regulatory elements contribute minimally to the transcriptional regulation of developmental and extracellular signaling pathways. Alternatively, as in the case of genes, these pathways could be inactivated in K562 cells regardless of the relative impact of RE-linked TFBS into regulation of their genes.

3.1.5. Comparison of RE-associated and non-RE-associated TFBS profiles in the K562 cell line

Despite the observed enrichment patterns, it remained uncertain whether genes and molecular pathways enriched in RE-associated TFBS were similarly enriched in total TFBS, regardless of their origin. To address this, we introduced normalized scores - NGRE and NPPII - to represent relative TFBS densities across all regulatory elements, as detailed in the Materials and Methods section.

At the gene level, a statistically significant positive correlation was detected between GRE values (quantifying RE-linked TFBS enrichment) and GTE scores (reflecting the total TFBS landscape) (Figure 29; Pearson correlation coefficient = 0.47, $p < 0.001$; table S6 in supplementary material in (Nikitin et al., 2018)). Correspondingly, the GO annotation terms associated with genes showing extreme GRE or GTE values exhibited substantial overlap. Terms linked to protein synthesis, chromatin organization, and DNA replication were consistently represented among the most enriched categories, whereas those related to neurogenesis, GPCR-mediated signaling, and developmental processes were commonly found among the least regulated.

These findings indicate that while RE-linked TFBS contribute substantially to regulatory complexity, their genomic distribution generally parallels broader TFBS accumulation patterns, with a moderate overall correlation ($r = 0.47$) for GRE and GTE scores.

Figure 29. Comparative distribution of GRE and GTE scores for annotated human genes. The GRE values, reflecting RE-linked TFBS enrichment, are plotted along the y-axis, while the GTE values, indicating total TFBS density, are represented on the x-axis. Each point corresponds to a single gene. Color gradient denotes the local density of gene instances in the plot. Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r) and associated p-value (p) are provided to indicate the strength and statistical significance of the observed correlation.

3.1.6. Genes and pathways under strong regulation by the REs in the K562 cell line

To delineate the specific contributions of RE-derived regulation, we analyzed the distribution patterns of NGRE scores, which quantify the relative enrichment of RE-linked TFBS normalized against the total TFBS regulation for each individual gene (table S7 in supplementary material in (Nikitin et al., 2018)). The highest NGRE values were observed for

members of the ubiquitin-specific peptidase gene family, notably *USP17L26*, *USP17L13*, and *USP17L12*, indicating a prominent RE-linked regulatory influence on these loci.

Subsequently, we examined the top and bottom 6% of genes ranked by their NGRE values (Table 3). GO enrichment analysis of the top NGRE-scoring genes revealed that 32% of the significantly overrepresented terms (64 out of 295) were associated with immune functions and host defense mechanisms. Additional enriched GO categories included organ development (7%), negative regulation of transcription (6%), chromatin assembly (6%), protein targeting to the Golgi apparatus (6%), ubiquitination and proteasomal degradation (4%), extracellular matrix organization (4%), regulation of STAT signaling (4%), development and function of sensory organs (4%), negative regulation of macromolecule metabolic processes (4%), peptide modification (3%), GTPase activity regulation (3%), reproductive system development and function (3%), and processes related to cell differentiation suppression and promotion of cell division (3%). Regulation of body fluid homeostasis accounted for 2%, while the remaining 9% encompassed various other cellular and molecular processes (table S8 in supplementary material in (Nikitin et al., 2018)).

Table 3. GO functional annotation clusters identified among the top and bottom 6% of human protein-coding genes ranked by their NGRE scores in the K562 cell line.

Cluster, GO terms	Percentage of clusters	
	Top 6%	Bottom 6%
Immunity and response to pathogens	32	–
Organ development and embryogenesis	7	45
Gene transcription and negative regulation	6	–
Chromatin assembly	6	16
Protein targeting to Golgi	6	–
Ubiquitination and protein degradation	4	–
Extracellular matrix organization	4	–
Regulation of STAT signaling	4	–
Perception organ development	4	–
Negative regulation of metabolism	4	–
Peptide modifications	3	–
Regulation of GTPases	3	–
Reproductive system development	3	–

Regulation of differentiation and cell proliferation	3	2
Regulation of body fluids	2	–
Transcription and processing of RNA	–	16
Ribosome assembly and protein translation regulation	–	8
Regulation of apoptosis	–	2
Proteasomal degradation	–	2
Steroid receptor signaling	–	2

Within the subset comprising the bottom 6% of protein-coding genes ranked by NGRE score, functional enrichment analysis revealed a predominance of gene ontology categories associated with embryonic development and stem cell differentiation (44 out of 98 clusters; 45%). Additional overrepresented categories included transcriptional regulation and RNA processing (16%), nuclear chromatin organization (16%), ribosomal function and protein translation (8%), regulation of apoptosis (2%), ubiquitin binding (2%), steroid receptor-mediated signaling (2%), regulation of cell proliferation (2%), and various other biological processes accounting for the remaining 7% (Table 3; table S8 in supplementary material in (Nikitin et al., 2018)).

Table 4. Classification of functional categories represented among the highest and lowest scoring molecular pathways, ranked according to their NPPII values in the K562 cell line.

Functional group	Percentage	
	Top 6%	Bottom 6%
Fatty acids metabolism	19	–
Immunity and response to pathogens	15	14
Nuclear transport	9	–
Maturation of RNA (mRNA and small RNAs)	9	–
DNA repair and replication	6	–
Alpha-synuclein signaling	5	–
Ubiquitination and protein degradation	3	–
Protein targeting to Golgi	3	–
Nerve growth and neuronal signaling	–	24
Organ development, embryogenesis, and cell adhesion	–	35

IGF1R signaling and regulation of glucose metabolism	–	9
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Comparable trends were observed at the level of molecular pathways (Table 4; table S9 in supplementary material in (Nikitin et al., 2018)). To assess the relative contribution of RE-linked TFBS to the regulation of molecular pathways, NPII scores were calculated. These scores reflect the degree of RE-specific regulatory input normalized by the total TFBS activity within each pathway. Among the 65 pathways with the highest NPII values, the predominant functional categories included fatty acid metabolism (19%), immune responses and pathogen recognition (15%), nuclear transport (9%), mRNA maturation (6%), DNA replication and repair (6%), alpha-synuclein signaling (5%), small RNA biogenesis and associated functions (3%), protein ubiquitination (3%), and protein trafficking to the Golgi apparatus (3%), with additional pathways contributing the remaining percentage.

Conversely, pathways with the lowest NPII values were predominantly associated with neuronal growth and synaptic signaling (24%), cell adhesion processes (19%), cytokine-mediated signaling networks (14%), developmental programs (14%), insulin-like growth factor (IGF) signaling, and glucose metabolism regulation (9%) (Table 4; table S9 in supplementary material in (Nikitin et al., 2018)).

To further elucidate these patterns, the distributions of NGRE scores at the gene level and NPII scores at the pathway level were compared for the total set of REs and for the subset of evolutionarily younger elements (defined as having 0–8% sequence divergence from their consensus). In both cases, statistically significant positive correlations were observed between gene-level NGRE scores and pathway-level NPII scores. Notably, the correlations were more robust at the pathway level: for the total RE fraction, the Pearson correlation coefficient was 0.38 ($p < 0.001$; Figure 30A), while for the young RE fraction, the coefficient was 0.57 ($p < 0.001$; Figure 30B). These findings are consistent with previous observations that pathway-level aggregation often yields more coherent and biologically interpretable signals compared to single-gene analyses (Borisov et al., 2017), particularly in the context of complex diseases such as cancer and neurodegenerative disorders (Alberio et al., 2012; Mattson et al., 1999; Yeh et al., 2006), which are often connected with nonrandom RE integration (Sultana et al., 2017).

Figure 30. Comparison of normalized TFBS enrichment between evolutionarily young and total REs. (A) Scatterplot depicting the relationship between NGRE scores calculated for young REs (0–8% sequence divergence from consensus) and for the total RE fraction at the gene level. Each data point represents an individual protein-coding gene. (B) Corresponding scatterplot of NPII scores reflecting pathway-level regulatory enrichment by young versus total REs. Each point denotes a distinct molecular pathway. Pearson correlation coefficients (r) and associated p -values (p) are indicated for each comparison.

Despite the observed moderate correlation between young and total RE-linked regulatory scores (Pearson $r = 0.38$ – 0.57 ; Figure 30), certain regulatory characteristics diverged between these two groups. To further investigate differential contributions of evolutionarily young versus all REs to gene and pathway regulation, we computed the ratio of scores derived from all REs to those from young REs, separately for NGRE (gene-level) and NPII (pathway-level) metrics. Elevated ratio values indicate stronger regulatory influence from ancient RE insertions, while lower values suggest more recent regulatory rewiring driven by younger elements (Table 5; supplementary tables S10 and S11 for NGRE and NPII ratios, respectively, available in (Nikitin et al., 2018)).

When molecular pathways were ranked by their NPII ratio values, the top 65 pathways - indicative of regulation shaped predominantly by older REs - were primarily associated with cell adhesion, Notch, Wnt, and integrin signaling (20%), immune response and cytokine signaling (20%), neuronal development and sensory functions (17%), metabolism of

chondroitin sulfate and heparin (8%), cAMP signaling (6%), endocytosis (3%), and IGF1R signaling (3%).

Table 5. Functional categorization of the top and bottom molecular pathways ranked by the ratio of NPII scores derived from all versus young RE-linked TFBS.

Functional group	Percentage	
	Top 6%	Bottom 6%
Cell adhesion, Notch, Wnt, and integrin signaling	20	–
Immunity and response to pathogens	20	17
Nerve growth and neuronal signaling	17	–
Metabolism of chondroitin sulfate and heparin	8	–
Metabolism of cAMP	6	–
Endocytosis	3	–
IGF1R signaling and regulation of glucose metabolism	3	–
Cell cycle progression and regulation of apoptosis	–	21
PDGF, TGF beta, EGFR, and p38 signaling	–	12
Histone deacetylation and DNA methylation	–	10
Phospholipid metabolism	–	9
Insulin and AMPK signaling	–	6
Protein targeting to Golgi	–	3
Estrogen signaling and oocyte maturation	–	3

The molecular pathways exhibiting the lowest ratios of NPII scores - therefore representing those most rapidly evolving in the recent evolutionary timeframe - were predominantly associated with core processes of cell cycle progression and attenuation of apoptotic signaling (21%), immune response mechanisms (17%), and key signaling cascades including PDGF, TGF- β , EGFR, and p38 MAPK (12%). Additional enriched functions included the interplay between histone deacetylation and DNA methylation (10%), phospholipid metabolic pathways (9%), insulin and AMPK signaling (6%), retrograde Golgi-to-ER transport (3%), as well as estrogen signaling and oocyte maturation (3%).

Due to the high frequency of zero denominator values in the NGRE scores for the young RE-linked TFBS, ranking individual genes by the NGRE ratio was not meaningful for

identifying top candidates. Nevertheless, the bottom 6% of genes - presumably the most rapidly evolving in recent human evolution based on recent RE-linked TFBS acquisition - were successfully identified. Functional analysis revealed that these genes were primarily involved in the metabolism and biosynthesis of heterocyclic nitrogen-containing compounds and phospholipids (50 of 163 genes; 31%), structural organization of the nuclear lumen (8%), mRNA splicing and processing (7%), ribosomal assembly and protein translation (7%), epigenetic regulation via DNA and histone methylation (4%), and mechanisms of DNA repair (2%).

3.1.7. Overview and discussion of the main results obtained by the RE-linked TFBS evolutionary analysis in K562 cell line

The obtained data provide compelling evidence that for TFBS profiles in the K562 human cell line myelogenous leukemia, evolutionary dynamics of transcriptional regulation mediated by REs are closely aligned with the functional roles of the associated genes. For this analysis, TFBS located within a ± 5 kb region flanking the TSS of annotated protein-coding genes were selected as described in the Materials and Methods (Figure 31). A total of approximately 13 million TFBS reads were mapped within these promoter-proximal regions.

Figure 31. Model illustrating transcriptional regulation mediated by RE-associated TFBS in the human K562 cell line. (A) A schematic depiction of TFBS (indicated by arrows) that may coincide with REs (shown as black boxes) positioned in proximity to TSS of annotated human genes. (B) Conceptual framework summarizing the contribution of RE-linked TFBS to gene regulation across evolutionary timescales, encompassing both long-term and recent evolutionary processes. The illustration integrates findings derived from the K562 cell line analysis at the levels of individual genes and molecular pathways.

We then quantified the absolute transcriptional enrichment scores associated with RE-linked TFBS both at the level of individual genes and molecular pathways (Adamyany et al., 2021; Sorokin et al., 2021) in the K562 cell line. The most substantially impacted genes and pathways were associated with key cellular processes, including responses to stress and innate immunity, ribosome biogenesis and protein translation, chromatin remodeling, DNA

replication, mitotic spindle organization, and cell cycle regulation. In contrast, genes and pathways displaying minimal RE-linked regulation were predominantly involved in embryonic development and neurogenesis (Tables S3 and S4 in supplementary material in (Nikitin et al., 2018)).

Subsequently, we demonstrated that the genomic distribution of RE-linked TFBS generally parallels the global distribution pattern of all TFBS, as evidenced by a statistically significant correlation (Pearson correlation coefficient = 0.47, p-value < 0.001; Figure 29). The corresponding sets of top- and bottom-ranked biological processes were also markedly overlapping between RE-specific and total TFBS distributions. In both cases, the most strongly regulated processes included protein synthesis, chromatin remodeling, and DNA replication, while the least regulated processes encompassed developmental and neurogenic programs (Table S3 in supplementary material in (Nikitin et al., 2018)).

It is important to consider that the observed TFBS densities likely reflect the functional relevance of specific genes and pathways within the biological context of the studied cell type. For instance, in the highly proliferative K562 leukemia cell line used here, pathways associated with embryogenesis and neurogenesis are expected to have reduced functional significance relative to those governing DNA synthesis, translation, and cell cycle progression. Nonetheless, although statistically significant, the moderate correlation between the distributions of all TFBS and RE-linked TFBS (Figure 29) indicates that RE-mediated transcriptional regulation also exhibits unique features that diverge from the general pattern, suggesting selective integration of RE-driven regulatory mechanisms.

The biological processes that exhibit pronounced enrichment in RE-linked TFBS regulation are likely among the most rapidly evolving ones. This is consistent with the established view that RE-linked TFBS are typically non-conserved across species, in contrast to those located within unique, evolutionarily constrained genomic regions (Cheng et al., 2014; Kundaje et al., 2015; Lowdon et al., 2016). To explore these RE-specific regulatory dynamics, we examined the normalized profiles of RE-associated TFBS, expressed relative to the total TFBS counts for the same genes (Table S7 in supplementary material in (Nikitin et al., 2018)).

Notably, the most strongly and specifically RE-regulated protein-coding genes in the K562 cell line analysis included three members of the ubiquitin-specific peptidase family,

suggesting accelerated evolutionary divergence of the associated molecular pathways. The gene ontology features most enriched among these top-ranked RE-regulated genes were primarily linked to immune responses and host defense mechanisms. In addition, substantial enrichment was observed for processes related to the negative regulation of transcription, protein targeting to the Golgi apparatus, ubiquitination and proteasomal degradation, extracellular matrix organization, STAT signaling modulation, development and functional specialization of sensory and reproductive systems, fatty acid metabolism, regulation of GTPase activity, as well as regulation of cellular differentiation, proliferation, and body fluid homeostasis (Tables 4 and 5).

In contrast, the biological processes exhibiting the weakest regulatory association with RE-linked TFBS were predominantly related to embryonic development, stem cell differentiation, axonal growth and neuronal signaling, cytokine-mediated signaling cascades, transcription and RNA processing, chromatin organization, ribosomal assembly and protein synthesis, IGF1R-mediated signaling, and glucose metabolism (Tables 4 and 5).

To further dissect the evolutionary dynamics of RE-mediated gene regulation, we separately analyzed gene level RE-linked TFBS enrichment scores for the complete set of REs as well as for the evolutionarily young subset, defined as elements diverged by less than 8% from their respective consensus sequences. The regulatory features derived from the full RE complement reflect long-term patterns of TFBS accumulation shaped over extended evolutionary timescales, whereas those associated with the young RE fraction are indicative of more recent regulatory innovations in the primate lineage, particularly since the divergence of Old World monkeys (Giordano et al., 2007; Sverdlov, 2000). Statistically significant correlations were observed between gene- and pathway-level regulatory metrics computed for young and all REs (Figure 30), supporting the notion that the principal evolutionary trajectories of RE-linked TFBS regulation are largely preserved across different temporal scales.

To identify regulatory divergence across evolutionary timescales, we computed ratios of the RE-specific metrics (NGRE and NPII scores) derived from the full RE set and from the young RE subset. Higher ratios indicate greater accumulation of regulatory elements over long-term evolution, whereas lower ratios suggest recent evolutionary changes (Table 5; Tables S10 and S11 in supplementary material in (Nikitin et al., 2018)). Among the pathways demonstrating long-term, but not recent, enrichment in RE-mediated TFBS regulation were

those associated with cytokine and immune signaling, cell adhesion, Notch, Wnt, and integrin signaling cascades, neuronal development and sensory functions, metabolism of chondroitin sulfate and heparin, cAMP signaling, endocytic transport, and IGF1R pathways.

Conversely, the pathways exhibiting the most rapid regulatory evolution in the recent evolutionary timeframe were enriched for processes related to immune defense, cell cycle progression, attenuation of apoptosis, PDGF, TGF- β , EGFR, and p38 signaling, epigenetic regulation through histone deacetylation and DNA methylation interplay, nuclear lumen architecture, catabolic and biosynthetic metabolism of phospholipids and heterocycles, insulin and AMPK signaling, retrograde Golgi-to-ER transport, estrogen-mediated signaling, and oocyte maturation (Figure 31).

Interestingly, immune-related pathways were prominently featured in both long-term and recent regulatory categories. However, their functional composition did not overlap substantially (Table 6). Long-term evolved immune pathways were primarily associated with general inflammatory responses, whereas recent changes were linked to mechanisms of innate immune activation and cytokine regulation. These observations align with contemporary experimental findings that HERVs have disseminated numerous interferon-inducible enhancers across the genome, thereby contributing to the evolution of essential regulatory modules in innate immune defense (Buttler & Chuong, 2022; Chuong et al., 2016, 2017).

Table 6. Immunity-associated molecular pathways exhibiting the highest and lowest ratios of NPII scores derived from total versus young RE-linked TFBS, reflecting differential contributions of long-term and recent evolutionary dynamics to regulatory modulation.

Pathway name	All NPII	Young NPII	Ratio (A/Y)
Top ratio pathways			
NCI downstream signaling in naive CD8 T cells pathway (pathway regulation of survival gene product expression <i>via</i> IL2RG)	1.02	0.18	5.59
NCI downstream signaling in naive CD8 T cells main pathway	0.93	0.43	2.16
Reactome toll like receptor 4 TLR4 cascade main pathway	1.19	0.32	3.72
Reactome interleukin receptor SHC signaling main pathway	0.85	0.24	3.51
Cytokine network pathway	1.04	0.32	3.24
NCI CXCR3 mediated signaling events pathway (cell adhesion)	1.06	0.39	2.76

NCI CXCR3 mediated signaling events pathway (actin polymerization or depolymerization)	1.02	0.40	2.57
NCI LPA receptor mediated events pathway (cAMP biosynthetic process)	0.87	0.35	2.46
Biocarta LCK and FYN tyrosine kinases in initiation of TCR activation main pathway	0.98	0.42	2.36
NCI IL2 mediated signaling events pathway (T cell proliferation)	1.00	0.46	2.19
NCI BCR signaling pathway (reentry into mitotic cell cycle)	0.88	0.42	2.12
NCI IL4-mediated signaling events main pathway	0.96	0.46	2.08
KEGG inflammatory bowel disease IBD main pathway	1.01	0.49	2.06
Lower ratio pathways			
Reactome IRAK2 mediated activation of TAK1 complex main pathway	1.17	1.40	0.84
Reactome IRAK2 mediated activation of TAK1 complex upon TLR7 8 or 9 stimulation main pathway	1.17	1.40	0.84
KEGG Fanconi anemia main pathway	0.98	1.17	0.83
Reactome Fanconi anemia main pathway	0.89	1.08	0.82
Reactome CD28 dependent Vav1 main pathway	1.13	1.37	0.83
Reactome thromboxane signaling through TP receptor main pathway	0.94	1.15	0.82
NCI Thromboxane A2 receptor signaling pathway (JNK cascade)	0.95	1.20	0.79
NCI Fc epsilon receptor I signaling in mast cells pathway (regulation of mast cell degranulation)	0.82	1.03	0.79
IL-10 pathway: IL-10 responsive genes transcription of BCLXL cyclin-D1 D2 D3 Pim1 c-myc and P19 (INK4D) <i>via</i> STAT3	0.99	1.31	0.76
IL-10 pathway: inflammatory cytokine genes expression <i>via</i> STAT3	0.99	1.31	0.76
Reactome membrane binding and targeting of GAG proteins main pathway	0.94	1.25	0.75

The observed patterns of genes and molecular pathways most profoundly influenced by REs align with established universals of genome evolution (Koonin, 2011). Our findings regarding RE-mediated modulation of molecular pathways in the human genome are broadly consistent with both ancestral and recent evolutionary trajectories within the hominin lineage. RE insertions, by nature of their abrupt and disruptive integration, can exert substantial regulatory influence and mutational pressure on neighboring loci, potentially instigating novel transcriptional programs (Göke & Ng, 2016). It has been previously hypothesized that genes with high and ubiquitous expression - particularly those encoding cytoplasmic and housekeeping proteins - are less tolerant to such disruptions due to the detrimental consequences of protein misfolding and stoichiometric imbalances among macromolecular complexes (Drummond et al., 2005; Drummond & Wilke, 2008; Lemos et al.,

2005). Consistent with this view, our results indicate that RE-linked transcriptional regulation predominantly affects genes and pathways associated with immunity, signal transduction, proliferation, and intercellular communication, while genes involved in core housekeeping functions exhibit comparatively limited RE influence.

Furthermore, the evolutionary history of the human lineage likely encompasses episodic accelerations in the evolution of specific molecular systems, potentially driven by forces such as host–pathogen coevolution (CAPEWELL et al., 2015), sexual selection dynamics (Wilkinson et al., 2015), or adaptive responses to dietary shifts (K. Ye & Gu, 2011). Notably, it has been suggested that regulatory innovations represent a dominant mechanism underlying phenotypic divergence in recent human evolution (Siepel & Arbiza, 2014). For instance, immune-related genes have been subjected to continual evolutionary remodeling in response to pathogenic pressures, with evidence of both ancient and ongoing adaptations (Carmona & Schatz, 2017; Hoffmann et al., 2015). The current initial K562 cell line study extended this paradigm by demonstrating that REs serve as a substrate for the regulatory rewiring of immune function, providing novel TFBS through exaptation. Importantly, the distinct temporal patterns of RE impact on different immune system modules - some affected in long-term evolution, others in more recent episodes - suggest functional modularity and temporal decoupling in immune system evolution (Table 6).

Parallel processes are evident in the evolution of the nervous system. For example, sexual selection mechanisms - particularly those associated with reduced male–male competition and increased female choice under trends toward monogamy - have been implicated in shaping human brain evolution (Stanyon & Bigoni, 2014). Our data indicate that REs have contributed regulatory input to neuronal genes across extended evolutionary timescales (Table 5), potentially reflecting multiple waves of brain innovation across mammalian and primate evolution.

Additionally, dietary transitions following the divergence from the last common ancestor with chimpanzees - including increased meat consumption and the adoption of fire and tool use ~2 million years ago - are likely to have exerted selective pressure on metabolic pathways (K. Ye & Gu, 2011). In this context, the recent RE-linked regulatory shifts we observed in genes involved in the catabolism of heterocyclic compounds and phospholipids may represent genomic adaptations to these novel nutritional environments.

A further notable observation concerns the recent RE-mediated evolution of chromatin-modifying pathways, particularly the interplay between histone deacetylation and DNA methylation. This may be partly attributable to the expansion and functional diversification of KRAB-domain zinc finger proteins, which serve as host-encoded repressors of transposon activity (Imbeault et al., 2017), reflecting a molecular arms race between host regulatory systems and mobile genetic elements.

The initial study provides an in-depth analysis of RE-linked TFBS in a single human cell line (K562), leveraging the most comprehensive TFBS dataset available at the time of analysis. The next work described in the upcoming sections benefited from the continued accumulation of high-throughput TFBS profiles across a broader spectrum of human cell lines, as well as the dataset of different epigenomic modalities, such as chromatin modifications. Such datasets enabled more refined models of RE contribution to the evolution of gene regulation and cellular function, as will be discussed later.

3.2. RE-linked TFBS analysis in thirteen human cell lines in two evolutionary timescales

3.2.1. Mapping of RE-specific human TFBS in 13 human cell lines

In order to study evolutionary impact of human RE at the level of TFBS regulation in a broader cell line context, we retrieved experimental TFBS data from the ENCODE project repository, generated through sequencing of immunoprecipitated DNA fragments for a total of 563 transcription factor proteins (Diehl & Boyle, 2016; Kundaje et al., 2015; Sloan et al., 2016). Adequate data - defined as the presence of mapped TFBS for at least three transcription factors - were available for 13 human cell lines (supplementary file 2 in (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019)). These included the myelogenous leukemia cell line K562; B lymphoblastoid lines GM12891 and GM12878; cervical adenocarcinoma HeLa S3; endometrial adenocarcinoma Ishikawa; both original and transformed embryonic kidney cell lines HEK293 and HEK293T; breast cancer cell lines MCF-7 and MCF-10A; lung adenocarcinoma A549; hepatocellular carcinoma HepG2; colorectal carcinoma HCT116; and neuroblastoma SK-N-SH. Collectively, these lines represent eight cancerous or transformed tissue types of human origin - namely blood, cervix, kidney, adrenal gland, mammary gland, lung, liver, and colon (Figure 32A). Summary statistics for TFBS datasets mapped to REs across these cell lines are presented in Table 7.

Figure 32. Comparison of NGRE and NPPII scores across human cell lines for the total RE fraction. Color coding corresponds to the anatomical origin of each cell line. (A) Schematic representation of the tissue origins for the 13 human cell lines analyzed in the current study. (B) Distribution of Pearson correlation coefficients comparing NGRE scores of the reference cell line K562 (studied previously as described earlier in the Results and

discussion section) with those of the remaining 12 cell lines. (C) Distribution of Pearson correlation coefficients comparing NPII scores of K562 with NGRE scores from the other cell lines. (D) Distribution of all pairwise Pearson correlation coefficients for NGRE scores across all 13 cell lines. (E) Distribution of all pairwise Pearson correlation coefficients for NPII scores across the full set of cell lines.

Table 7. Summary statistics for mapped TFBS in the 13 human cell lines analysis. A considerable fraction of values appear as rounded numbers, reflecting the influence of IDR thresholds applied within the standard ENCODE peak-calling pipeline (*Transcription Factor ChIP-Seq – ENCODE*, n.d.).

Cell line	Number of TFs profiled	Number of mapped TFBS	Number of TFBS mapped on SINEs	Percentage of TFBS mapped on SINEs	Number of TFBS mapped on LINES	Percentage of TFBS mapped on LINES	Number of TFBS mapped on HERVs	Percentage of TFBS mapped on HERVs
K562	265	78,021,500	25,078,428	32.1	22,646,141	29	10,394,662	13.3
HepG2	175	51,982,065	16,406,062	31.6	140,104,77	27	6,493,562	12.5
HEK293	177	53,100,000	19,214,015	36.2	15,708,687	29.6	6,089,813	11.5
GM12878	127	37,688,353	10,185,415	27	9,927,943	26.3	4,727,719	12.5
MCF-7	80	23,851,396	7,039,271	29.5	7,499,703	31.4	3,297,443	13.8
A549	44	13,044,409	3,930,407	30.1	3,569,214	27.4	1,667,464	12.8
HeLa-S3	15	4,500,000	1,112,669	24.7	1,036,667	23	566,618	12.6
SK-N-SH	15	4,500,000	874,572	19.4	958,401	21.3	473,342	10.5
HCT116	4	1,200,000	402,872	33.6	333,771	27.8	181,562	15.1
Ishikawa	4	1,200,000	268,209	22.4	266,191	22.2	141,530	11.8
HEK293T	17	5,100,000	129,7870	25.4	1,725,589	33.8	618,745	12.1
MCF_10A	3	900,000	214,458	23.8	215,576	24	103,925	11.5
GM12891	7	2,100,000	559,260	26.6	433,194	20.6	253,577	12.1

In total, 277,187,723 TFBS hits were mapped across the human genome for the entire set of analyzed cell lines. Of these, 199,925,024 (72.1%) intersected with RE sequences, supporting the conclusion that REs constitute a predominant source of TFBS in human cells.

Although this proportion may initially appear elevated in comparison to earlier reports (Sundaram et al., 2014), it is important to note that our analysis excluded all multimapping TFBS reads, adhering strictly to the ENCODE standard ChIP-seq mapping and filtering pipeline (*ChIP-Seq Read Mapping – ENCODE*, n.d.). Thus, the results reflect uniquely mapped TFBS reads only. To verify this proportion, we performed an independent validation by

mapping all annotated human RE sequences obtained from the UCSC Genome Browser (*Human Hg38 Chr7:155799529-155812871 UCSC Genome Browser V487*, n.d.) onto the reference human genome. In concordance with previously published estimates (Lander et al., 2001), REs covered approximately 45% of the genome (hg19 assembly) using the same approach. Therefore, we detected no methodological biases and interpreted the ~72% overlap between TFBS and REs as an accurate representation for the ENCODE-derived primary cell line datasets employed in this study.

Nonetheless, the proportion of RE-linked TFBS was slightly reduced when focusing specifically on those located within a 10-kilobase window surrounding TSS of annotated genes. Among 43,042,026 TFBS mapped in this TSS-proximal region, 61.4% were found to intersect with REs. This pattern was consistently observed across all investigated cell lines (Table 8). Furthermore, the distribution of TSS-proximal TFBS among RE classes was not uniform: approximately 30% were located within SINEs, 17% within LINES, and 7% within HERVs, closely resembling the K562 cell line pattern studied earlier (Nikitin et al., 2018). In comparison, the RE-class distribution for the complete set of RE-linked TFBS genome-wide (not limited to gene-proximal regions) comprised ~28% in SINEs, ~26% in LINES, and ~12% in HERVs, which differs from the earlier results of the K562 cell line with LINES having twice as much RE-linked TFBS as SINEs and HERVs outside the genes TSS 10Kb neighbourhoods have.

Table 8. Summary statistics for mapped TFBS in gene TSS proximal regions in the 13 human cell lines analysis.

Cell Line	Number of TFs Profiled	Number of Mapped TFBS	Number of TFBS Mapped on SINEs	Percentage of TFBS Mapped on SINEs	Number of TFBS Mapped on LINES	Percentage of TFBS Mapped on LINES	Number of TFBS Mapped on HERVs	Percentage of TFBS Mapped on HERVs
K562	260	12,547,055	4,667,810	37.2	2,508,956	20	1,081,084	8.6
HepG2	175	8,803,748	3,023,414	34.3	1,559,929	17.7	669,907	7.6
HEK293	177	8,074,128	3,235,573	40.1	1,569,002	19.4	587,798	7.3
GM12878	127	5,626,411	1,699,882	30.2	970,626	17.3	400,502	7.1
MCF-7	80	3,067,441	1,029,118	33.5	598,982	19.5	238,005	7.8
A549	44	2,035,359	662,458	32.5	358,084	17.6	142,842	7
HeLa-S3	15	720,963	193,365	26.8	109,683	15.2	47,759	6.6
SK-N-SH	15	679,254	139,230	20.5	90,313	13.3	36,751	5.4
HCT116	4	202,223	71,590	35.4	38,293	18.9	16,878	8.3
Ishikawa	4	194,053	52,211	26.9	28,867	14.9	12,768	6.6
HEK293T	17	518,287	162,440	31.3	115,555	22.3	42,242	8.2
MCF_10A	3	145,892	43,930	30.1	25,500	17.5	10,304	7.1

GM12891	7	427,212	94,464	22.1	48,947	11.5	21,515	5
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Averaged across all analyzed cell lines, the genome-wide distribution of TFBS (Table 7) reveals that 27.8% of TFBS intersect with SINE elements, 26.4% map to LINEs, and 12.5% fall within HERV sequences. In contrast, the distribution within promoter-proximal regions diverges notably: 33.2% of TFBS overlap with SINEs, while only 13.3% and 7.1% associate with LINEs and HERVs, respectively. This finding is in stark contrast with total genome occupancy of the three major classes of REs: LINEs comprise the highest percentage of human genome (17-22%), SINEs go next with 13% and HERV elements are the last with 8-9% of human genome. Similar to the findings from the K562-specific analysis, these observations further support the hypothesis that insertions of LINEs and HERVs near TSS are more likely to be deleterious than those of SINEs. This may be explained by the greater length and potential regulatory impact of LINE and HERV sequences, which could be subject to purifying selection or targeted silencing via heterochromatinization.

The distribution patterns of TFBS hits across different TF proteins demonstrated variability between the analyzed cell lines (supplementary file 6 in (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019)). The color scale reflects the density of mapped TFBS for each factor, while blank cells indicate the absence of available TFBS data for a given transcription factor within the corresponding cell line in the ENCODE dataset.

3.2.2. Calculation of gene- and pathway-specific characteristics of RE-linked TFBS

For a total of 25,075 annotated human genes, we computed the absolute and normalized enrichment scores of RE-linked TFBS, referred to as GRE and NGRE as described previously (Supplementary Tables 1 and 7 in (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019)). Similarly, for 3,126 molecular pathways, we calculated the corresponding absolute and normalized enrichment scores, PII and NPII (Supplementary Tables 1 and 8 in (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019)). All enrichment scores were determined separately for both the complete RE dataset and the subset of evolutionarily young REs. As in the K562 cell line analysis, REs with an average divergence of 8% or less from their consensus sequence were classified as young, corresponding approximately to the evolutionary split between the human lineage and New World monkeys (Giordano et al., 2007). Notably, in the most comprehensively profiled K562 cell line, 44% of genes showed no contribution from young REs, yielding zero GRE scores.

In contrast, only 1.5% of genes exhibited zero GRE values when all REs were considered. This pattern of reduced young RE involvement was consistent across all analyzed cell lines.

3.2.3. Comparison of RE-associated TFBS distributions across the cell lines

We subsequently analyzed and compared NGRE scores - reflecting RE-linked TF binding - for all individual human genes across the different cell lines included in this study (Figure 32). When compared with previously reported NGRE profiles of the K562 leukemia cell line (Nikitin et al., 2018), we observed strong correlations across cell lines, with Pearson's r ranging from 0.6 to 0.95 and a median around 0.9 (Figure 32B). A similar pattern was observed for the pathway-level NPPII scores, which showed significant correlations as well (r from 0.75 to 0.95, median approximately 0.85; Figure 32C). These correlations were calculated based on all REs, given that most human genes had non-zero TFBS enrichment scores.

Importantly, the strength of the correlations between K562 and the other cell lines did not reflect tissue specificity - no distinct tissue-type clustering was evident in the correlation coefficient distributions (Figure 32A–C). For instance, at the NGRE level, K562 cells showed equally high correlation ($r \approx 0.95$) with GM12878 transformed lymphoblasts, HEK293 kidney cells, A549 lung adenocarcinoma cells, and HepG2 liver carcinoma cells (Figure 32B). Likewise, the highest pathway-level correlations (NPPII) with K562 were observed for the same cell lines and also included MCF-7 mammary carcinoma cells, with Pearson's r values ranging from 0.9 to 0.95 (Figure 32C).

When all pairwise combinations of the 13 analyzed cell lines were considered, we found unimodal distributions of Pearson correlation values ranging from ~ 0.5 to 0.95, with a median of 0.88 at both the gene (NGRE) and pathway (NPPII) levels (Figure 32D and 32E, respectively).

Altogether, these results indicate a high level of consistency in RE-linked TFBS regulatory patterns across diverse human cell types, suggesting a broadly conserved role for REs in shaping transcriptional regulation of genes and pathways.

3.2.4. Genes and molecular pathways enriched or depleted in RE-linked TFBS regulation in 13 human cell lines

We next aimed to identify individual genes and molecular pathways that are either enriched or depleted in regulatory input from RE-linked TFBS (designated here as RE-enriched and RE-deficient, respectively). To do this, we analyzed 24,389 human genes and 3,123 pathways using scatter plot visualizations. For genes, GRE scores were plotted along the x-axis and NGRE scores along the y-axis (Figure 33), while for pathways, the x-axis reflected PII values and the y-axis displayed corresponding NPII scores (Figure 34).

This two-dimensional representation allows for visual detection of relative enrichment or deficiency: among genes or pathways with comparable absolute scores (GRE or PII), those showing higher normalized enrichment scores (NGRE or NPII) are considered RE-enriched. Conversely, those with relatively lower NGRE or NPII values are classified as RE-deficient. This strategy formed the foundational principle of the newly introduced RetroSpect method for identifying genes and molecular pathways that are either enriched or deficient in RE-linked transcriptional regulation (Nikitin, Sorokin, et al., 2019).

Figure 33. Comparison of GRE and NGRE scores across cell lines for all REs. (A) Mean GRE and NGRE scores plotted per gene, with each dot representing an individual gene score averaged across all cell lines. Genes classified as enriched in RE-linked regulation

(RE-enriched) are marked in red, while RE-deficient genes are marked in green. (B) Same GRE and NGRE comparison averaged across cell lines, with color intensity indicating local density of data points (i.e., number of genes per plotting grain). Marginal plots show the univariate distributions of GRE and NGRE scores. (C) GRE vs. NGRE score comparison shown separately for individual cell lines.

Figure 34. Comparison of PII and NPII scores across cell lines for all REs. (A) Mean PII and NPII scores plotted per pathway, with each dot representing an individual pathway score averaged across all cell lines. Pathways enriched in RE-linked regulation (RE-enriched) are highlighted in red, while RE-deficient pathways are shown in green. (B) Same comparison of mean PII and NPII scores averaged across cell lines, with color intensity reflecting the density of data points (i.e., number of pathways per plotting grain). Marginal histograms display the univariate distributions of PII and NPII values. (C) PII versus NPII score comparison shown separately for each cell line.

Across both types of analyses - gene-level (GRE vs NGRE) and pathway-level (PII vs NPII) ones - we detected consistent distributional patterns among the diverse human cell lines under investigation (Figure 33 and Figure 34). At the molecular pathway scale, PII and NPII scores exhibited statistically significant positive correlations across all tested cell lines, with an average Pearson correlation coefficient of approximately 0.58 (Figure 34). Similarly, at the level of individual genes, GRE and NGRE values were strongly correlated; however, in 12 out of 13 cell lines, we observed an intriguing and recurrent V-shaped distribution (Figure 33). This pattern was characterized by two diverging linear branches emanating from the origin, which tended to cluster separately into subsets of genes showing relative enrichment or depletion in RE-associated transcriptional regulation (RE-enriched and RE-deficient, respectively).

These observations collectively suggest that distinct human cell lines display highly convergent profiles in terms of RE-associated TFBS activity, both at the gene and pathway levels - an inference further substantiated by the high degree of inter-cell line correlation reported in the preceding section. To enable cross-cell line comparisons using unified metrics, we generated aggregated scores by calculating the mean GRE, NGRE, PII, and NPII values across all 13 cell lines (Figure 33A–B and Figure 34A–B). The resulting composite distributions closely mirrored those observed within individual cell lines.

To systematically classify genes and pathways that were markedly enriched or deficient in RE-linked TFBS regulation, we applied a regression-based analytical framework. For gene-level data, we constructed 1,000 random samples, each comprising 500 genes, and fitted linear regression lines (first-degree polynomials) using the least squares method (Charnes et al., 1976). From these, we selected the two extreme regression lines - those with the highest and lowest slopes - as benchmarks for delineating outliers. Genes positioned furthest above

the steepest slope (top 5%, $n = 1,219$) were defined as RE-enriched, while those falling furthest below the shallowest slope (bottom 5%, $n = 1,219$) were designated RE-deficient (Figure 33).

A comparable approach was implemented for the 3,123 molecular pathways. A single regression line was fitted to the entire dataset, and the 5% of pathways with the greatest perpendicular (Euclidean) distance above this line ($n = 156$) were classified as RE-enriched, while the bottom 5% ($n = 156$), located furthest below the line, were identified as RE-deficient (Figure 34). Through this methodology, we robustly identified 1,219 top-ranking and 1,219 bottom-ranking genes, along with 156 highly enriched and 156 highly deficient pathways, all defined by their degree of aggregated RE-associated transcriptional regulation across the 13 human cell lines profiled in this study (see Supplementary Datasets 9 and 10 in (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019)).

3.2.5. Functional profiling of top RE-enriched and RE-deficient genes (all RE classes)

To investigate the biological significance of the 1,219 genes identified as most enriched and the 1,219 genes most deficient in RE-associated transcriptional regulation, we performed GO enrichment analysis using the DAVID bioinformatics platform (Charitou et al., 2016; Huang et al., 2009b). This analysis aimed to uncover overrepresented functional categories among these gene subsets based on established biological process annotations. GO terms with a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$ were retained, and the results are provided in Supplementary Dataset 11 in (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019).

The RE-enriched gene set yielded 141 significantly enriched GO terms, whereas the RE-deficient gene group was associated with a markedly larger number of enriched terms - 1,022 in total, approximately sevenfold more. This striking disparity may reflect an underlying evolutionary principle, namely that a greater number of biological functions in human cells are subject to strong evolutionary constraint and conservation, rendering them less susceptible to regulation via transposable element-derived TFBSs.

Following manual curation of the enriched GO terms, we categorized them into 27 overarching functional groups (Table 9). Genes enriched in RE regulation were

predominantly associated with metabolic processes - including those involving amino acids, lipids, and metal ions - as well as cellular detoxification pathways, xenobiotic responses, sensory perception, neurotransmitter activity, and fertilization.

In contrast, the RE-deficient gene set encompassed a broader and more diverse spectrum of biological functions. These included key regulatory systems such as protein biosynthesis, RNA transcription, intracellular signaling pathways, intercellular adhesion and communication, cell cycle control, apoptotic mechanisms, nucleic acid and carbohydrate metabolism, post-translational protein modification, cellular stress responses, antiviral defense, chromatin structure maintenance, mitochondrial energy production, and electron transport chain activity. Together, these findings highlight a clear functional dichotomy between RE-enriched and RE-deficient genes. The former group is enriched for processes that may tolerate or even benefit from the regulatory influence of RE-derived TFBSs, whereas the latter comprises core cellular processes likely under selective pressure to remain insulated from such regulatory variation.

Table 9. Intracellular processes significantly enriched or depleted in RE-linked regulation based on GO and molecular pathway enrichment analyses (all REs by evolutionary time).

ID	Group of processes	RE enrichment by pathway analysis		RE enrichment by GO analysis		Overall status
		Enriched pathways	Deficient pathways	Enriched GO terms	Deficient GO-terms	
1	Posttranscriptional silencing by small RNAs	1	0	1	0	RE enriched
2	DNA repair	2	0	5	0	RE enriched
3	Amino acids, peptides and polyamines metabolism	20	5	13	8	RE enriched
4	Lipid metabolism	14	7	11	0	RE enriched
5	Detoxication, metabolism of xenobiotics and rare molecules	13	0	4	0	RE enriched
6	Sensory perception and neurotransmission	7	0	10	0	RE enriched
7	Fertilization	1	0	9	0	RE enriched
8	Cellular immune response (T cells and NK cells)	11	0	7	6	RE enriched
9	Nucleic base, nucleosides and	6	9	0	24	RE deficient

	nucleotides metabolism					
10	DNA metabolism and chromatin structure	0	4	0	151	RE deficient
11	Translation and protein quality control	0	12	8	130	RE deficient
12	Intracellular signaling	22	94	5	48	RE deficient
13	Response to viruses	0	3	0	17	RE deficient
14	Vitamin metabolism	4	0	0	0	RE enriched
15	Hormones	6	0	0	0	RE enriched
16	Molecular transport	10	0	0	0	RE enriched
17	Sulfur metabolism and linked redox reactions	5	0	0	0	RE enriched
18	Metal metabolism	0	0	6	0	RE enriched
19	Response to phorbol acetate	0	0	0	3	RE deficient
20	Electron transfer reactions	0	0	5	17	RE deficient
21	Mitochondria	0	0	5	17	RE deficient
22	RNA synthesis and degradation	0	0	0	139	RE deficient
23	Cell adhesion and interaction	0	0	0	15	RE deficient
24	Cell cycle and mitosis	0	0	0	55	RE deficient
25	Cell death	0	0	0	41	RE deficient
26	Protein localization and modification	0	0	0	19	RE deficient
27	Response to physical and chemical stress	0	0	0	24	=RE deficient
28	Carbohydrates metabolism	5	3	0	9	Ambiguous Pattern
29	Immunity	36	16	23	45	Shown separately
30	Other/too general terms	0	0	13	17	N/A

Fifty GO annotation terms were associated with immune-related functions and demonstrated distinct distribution patterns depending on their specific roles. Notably, processes such as immune cell migration and activation, along with cellular immune responses mediated by T cells and natural killer (NK) cells, exhibited enrichment in RE-linked regulation, whereas pathways related to B cell function were predominantly depleted in RE signals (Table 10).

Table 10. Immunity-associated biological processes enriched or depleted in RE-linked TFBS regulation, as identified through GO annotation and molecular pathway analysis (all REs by evolutionary ages considered).

Group of Processes	RE Enrichment by Pathway Analysis		RE Enrichment by GO Analysis		Overall Status
	Enriched pathways	Deficient pathways	Enriched GO terms	Deficient GO-terms	
Autoimmunity	4	0	0	0	RE enriched
Blood clotting	2	0	0	0	RE enriched
Innate immunity	8	0	0	5	Ambiguous
Inflammation	3	5	0	0	Ambiguous
Cellular immune response (T cells and NK cells)	11	0	7	6	RE enriched
Activation of antigen-presenting cells by T-helper cells	2	7	0	0	RE deficient
Other/Too general terms	6	1	8	11	Ambiguous
Immune cells migration and activation	0	0	7	0	RE enriched
Activity and maturation of B cells	0	0	0	6	RE deficient

Additionally, a complementary GO enrichment analysis conducted with the GOrilla tool (Eden et al., 2009), which applies a more stringent significance threshold, identified a limited set of highly robust associations. Notably, an exceptionally significant RE-enriched functional cluster ($p < 10^{-9}$; Figure 35A) was linked to the biological process of gene silencing mediated by microRNAs. In contrast, the most prominent RE-deficient categories were associated with the regulation of the stress-activated MAPK cascade and regulation of the JNK cascade, both reaching statistical significance at $p < 10^{-3}$ (Figure 35B).

Figure 35. Hierarchical arrangement of GO annotation terms identified using GOrilla analysis for RE-enriched (A) and RE-deficient (B) gene sets based on all RE-linked TFBS data.

We subsequently assessed the representation of microRNA genes within the RE-enriched and RE-deficient gene subsets (Table 11). The RE-enriched group contained 177 microRNA genes, compared to only 72 in the RE-deficient set. Given the total of 1,865 annotated microRNA genes in the human genome, this supports the interpretation that microRNA genes are significantly overrepresented in the RE-enriched category ($p < 10^{-17}$ by hypergeometric distribution), while showing significant depletion in the RE-deficient group ($p = 0.01$). A comparable pattern was observed for lncRNA genes: the RE-enriched group

included 150 lncRNA genes, whereas the RE-deficient group contained only 18. With the total number of human lncRNA genes estimated at 1,505, these results further support significant overrepresentation in the RE-enriched group ($p < 10^{-16}$), and a marked underrepresentation in the RE-deficient one ($p < 10^{-15}$). Collectively, these observations suggest that RE-linked TFBS regulatory mechanisms were particularly co-opted during mammalian evolutionary history to govern the expression of non-coding RNA genes, including both microRNAs and lncRNAs.

Table 11. microRNA and lncRNA genes identified as enriched or deficient in RE-linked TFBS regulation (all RE evolutionary ages).

Gene set	microRNAs	Genes in the set, totally	Hypergeometric p-value	Hypothesis tested
RE-enriched	177	1219	2.416×10^{-18}	microRNA are enriched
RE-deficient	72	1219	0.0138	microRNA are not enriched
Totally - 1865 microRNA genes in 25,075 genes of the human genome				
Gene set	lncRNAs	Genes in the set, totally	Hypergeometric p-value	Hypothesis tested
RE-enriched	150	1219	1.9500×10^{-17}	lncRNA are enriched
RE-deficient	18	1219	2.42×10^{-16}	lncRNA are not enriched
Totally - 1505 lncRNA genes in 25,075 genes of the human genome				

3.2.6. Functional features of the most RE-enriched and RE-deficient molecular pathways under regulation by RE-associated TFBS (all RE categories) in 13 human cell lines.

We further analyzed the 156 most RE-enriched and 156 most RE-deficient molecular pathways identified based on the aggregated NPII scores, as detailed in Supplementary File 10 in (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019). Similar to the gene-level analysis, the selected pathways were manually reviewed and grouped into broader functional categories (Table 9).

RE-enriched pathways predominantly involved metabolic processes including those for amino acids, vitamins, lipids, sulfur, and carbohydrates, as well as molecular transport, hormonal signaling and biosynthesis, detoxification mechanisms, xenobiotic response, sensory processing, neurotransmission, and reproductive functions such as fertilization. In contrast, the RE-deficient pathways were largely associated with translational machinery, intracellular signaling pathways - particularly those mediating cell adhesion and intercellular interactions - cell cycle regulation, apoptosis, nucleic acid metabolism, chromatin remodeling, and broad antiviral defense systems. Overall, ~74% of these functional categories overlapped with those derived from the gene-level RE-enrichment analysis, underscoring a consistent regulatory signature across types of analysis (Table 9).

As observed previously (Feschotte, 2008; Nikitin et al., 2018), numerous pathways with divergent RE associations were linked to immune function. RE-enriched immune-related pathways prominently featured cellular immune responses mediated by T and NK cells (Table 10), along with mechanisms involved in hemostasis, innate immune responses, and autoimmunity. Meanwhile, RE-deficient immune pathways were associated with general inflammatory signaling and the activation of antigen-presenting cells by T-helper lymphocytes.

The five most strongly RE-enriched and RE-deficient pathways, ranked by NPPII score, are illustrated in Figure 36.

Top 5 pathways by NPII

reactome Miscellaneous substrates Main Pathway

KEGG Linoleic acid metabolism Main Pathway

KEGG Staphylococcus aureus infection Main Pathway

reactome Interaction With The Zona Pellucida Main Pathway

reactome Xenobiotics Main Pathway

Bottom 5 pathways by NPII

biocarta multi step regulation of transcription by pitx2 Main Pathway

biocarta segmentation clock Main Pathway

ILK Signaling Pathway Induced Cell Proliferation

KEGG Circadian rhythm Main Pathway

NCI Canonical Wnt signaling Main Pathway

Figure 36. Top five molecular pathways exhibiting the highest and lowest degrees of RE-association, as determined by aggregated NPPII scores across REs of all revolutionary ages and across the cell lines.

3.2.7. Concordant molecular functions identified through gene- and pathway-level analyses of RE-associated regulation (all REs).

A comparative assessment of outcomes derived from gene-level and pathway-level analyses is summarized in Table 9. As outlined previously, both approaches demonstrated a high degree of concordance in the identification of functional categories under RE-associated TFBS regulation. Several molecular processes exhibited consistent regulatory patterns across both analytical frameworks. Among the processes with elevated RE-associated regulatory signatures were: (1) post-transcriptional gene silencing by small RNAs; (2) DNA repair mechanisms; (3) amino acid metabolism; (4) lipid metabolic pathways; (5) detoxification and xenobiotic metabolism; (6) sensory perception and neurotransmitter signaling; (7) fertilization-associated processes; and (8) T- and NK-cell mediated immune responses.

Specifically, the post-transcriptional regulation by small RNAs (1) was captured by a singular pathway and one GO term referring to microRNA-mediated gene silencing. Notably, microRNA regulation emerged as the most statistically enriched annotation cluster in the RE-enriched subset, according to GO analysis. Moreover, the content of both microRNA and long lncRNA genes was significantly overrepresented within this subset ($p < 10^{-16}$).

The DNA repair (2) cluster comprised both the pathway involving protein kinases in nonhomologous end-joining repair and several GO terms, including mitotic recombination, DNA synthesis during repair, meiosis, and strand displacement.

Amino acid metabolism (3) was represented by multiple biochemical routes, including the metabolism of D-arginine, D-ornithine, aspartate, asparagine, lysine, diphthamide, carnitine, cysteine, proline, hydroxyproline, beta-alanine, tryptophan, and L-kynurenine, alongside folate-mediated glutamate removal and glycine conjugation with salicylate and benzoate. Associated GO terms included proline metabolic and tryptophan catabolic processes.

In the lipid metabolism (4) domain, identified pathways encompassed bile secretion, SLC-mediated transport of bile salts and organic anions, fatty acid cycling, acyl-CoA hydrolysis, alpha-linolenic acid metabolism, alpha-oxidation of phytanate, beta-oxidation of unsaturated fatty acids, biosynthesis of lipoxins and eicosanoids, ether lipid metabolism, and phosphatidylinositol acyl remodeling. Related GO terms included lipid catabolism, carboxylic ester hydrolase activity, arachidonic acid metabolism, epoxygenase, monooxygenase and lipase activity.

Detoxification and xenobiotic metabolism (5) were reflected in pathways involving CYP2E1-mediated reactions, cytochrome P450-dependent drug metabolism, nicotine, heme, bupropion, caffeine degradation, FMO-mediated oxidation, formaldehyde clearance, S-reticuline metabolism, and aflatoxin biotransformation. Corresponding GO annotations highlighted xenobiotic response and metabolic processes, including the epoxygenase P450 pathway.

The sensory perception and neurotransmission (6) category included olfactory and visual signal transduction, GABA A (rho) receptor activation, dopamine signaling, and mechanisms underlying acetaminophen response and toxicity (the latter processes are also close to the xenobiotic metabolism). GO terms in this category involved odorant binding, olfactory receptor activity, and sensory detection.

Fertilization (7) was captured through a singular pathway (interaction with the zona pellucida) and several GO terms, including sperm-egg recognition, flagellar function, motility regulation, and zona pellucida binding.

For T- and NK-cell immunity (8), regulatory pathways included CD3 and TCR zeta chain phosphorylation, naive CD8 T-cell signaling, and CD28 co-stimulatory pathways. Enriched GO terms described leukocyte-mediated cytotoxicity and NK cell activity.

Conversely, processes exhibiting deficient RE-associated regulation included: (9) nucleotide and DNA metabolic functions; (10) chromatin structure maintenance and remodeling; (11) protein biosynthesis and ribosomal biogenesis; (12) intracellular signaling mechanisms; and (13) host antiviral defense pathways.

In detail, nucleotide and DNA metabolism (9) involved pathways for purine salvage, purine degradation, UMP and GDP-L-fucose biosynthesis, and NADH repair from hydrates. GO

terms included ATP and adenine metabolism, GTP binding, and purine/pyrimidine processing.

Chromatin structure regulation (10) incorporated pathways for PRC2-mediated histone and DNA methylation, histone deacetylase (HDAC) activity, histone arginine methylation, G2/M checkpoint, and HDAC degradation. GO terms addressed centromere assembly, telomere maintenance, chromatin remodeling, and histone modifications.

Protein translation and ribosome biogenesis (11) covered transcription of rRNA and tRNA, RNA modifications (e.g., wybutosine biosynthesis), spliceosome assembly, ribosomal construction, tRNA aminoacylation, translational initiation, elongation, termination, and nonsense-mediated decay. These pathways were aligned with directly matching GO terms.

Intracellular signaling (12) represented the most extensive functional category, comprising 94 pathways and 48 GO terms, encompassing a comprehensive array of intracellular communication networks (see Table 9).

Antiviral response (13) pathways included host-viral interactions such as APOBEC3-mediated resistance to HIV-1. GO terms encompassed viral capsid formation, transcription, translation, and cap-independent initiation via internal ribosome entry sites.

These functional domains were composed of varying numbers of individual pathways and GO terms (Table 9). An integrated summary of these enriched or depleted processes, along with the corresponding number of components, is depicted in Figure 37. Notably, 14 additional functional categories (~50%) exhibited RE-regulatory bias in only one analytical domain (gene- or pathway-based), and one category (~4%) - carbohydrate metabolism - demonstrated conflicting trends between the two approaches.

Posttranscriptional silencing by
small RNAs

DNA repair

Metabolism of
amino acids

Metabolism of
lipids

Detoxication and
metabolism of xenobiotics

Sensory
perception and
neurotransmission

Fertilization

T- and NK-
cellular immune
response

Nucleotide and DNA
metabolism

Maintaining and
modulation of
chromatin structure

Protein translation
and ribosome
biogenesis

Intracellular
signaling
pathways

Cellular
mechanisms of
antiviral response

Figure 37. Molecular processes exhibiting RE-enriched (green) and RE-deficient (red) regulatory patterns across REs of all evolutionary ages in 13 human cell lines.

3.2.8. Evaluation of randomness in GRE- and NGRE-derived results.

To evaluate the robustness of the identified RE-associated intracellular process patterns, we performed a permutation-based randomness test (Guo et al., 2009). Specifically, we generated 500 random permutations of GRE and NGRE values across all genes by shuffling gene identifiers, while preserving value distributions and averaging across all cell lines. For each permutation, a GRE–NGRE scatter plot was constructed, and the top 1,219 and bottom

1,219 genes were selected using the same criteria as in the original analysis. These randomly derived gene sets were subsequently analyzed using DAVID, and the top 100 GO terms were extracted for each permutation based on the lowest p-values.

We then compared the p-value distributions of GO enrichment between the actual and randomized gene sets (Figure 38A for RE-enriched, Figure 38B for RE-deficient genes). The results demonstrated that the RE-deficient processes were highly non-random, as their GO term p-value distributions did not overlap with those from the randomized sets (Figure 38B). In contrast, a substantial portion of the GO terms associated with RE-enriched genes overlapped with those observed in random permutations (Figure 38A). Nonetheless, a distinct subset of ten GO terms in the RE-enriched category exhibited significantly lower p-values than any of those derived from the random sets.

Importantly, across all 500 permutations, none produced GO terms with p-values more extreme than those observed in the original RE-enriched or RE-deficient gene sets. This supports an estimated q-value below 0.002 for both groups, indicating a high level of statistical confidence in the biological relevance of the identified molecular processes.

Figure 38. Enrichment of GO terms in RE-enriched (A) and RE-deficient (B) gene sets compared to randomized controls (all evolutionary ages REs). Distributions of GO term p-values derived from actual gene sets are compared against those obtained from 500 randomized permutations.

3.2.9. Functional profiles of top RE-enriched and RE-deficient genes associated with evolutionary young REs

We applied the same analysis pipeline to evaluate the top RE-enriched and deficient molecular processes influenced by evolutionary young human REs. A total of 673 top RE-enriched and 673 top RE-deficient genes were selected, with a smaller gene count compared to the full RE dataset due to only 44% of genes showing non-zero GRE scores for evolutionary recent RE insertions. GO term enrichment was performed using DAVID software, and the top annotation clusters with p-values < 0.05 are provided in Supplementary Dataset 12 in (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019). This analysis identified 55 GO terms for the enriched gene set, versus 730 terms - approximately 13 times more - for the deficient set. As observed for all REs, the majority of evolutionarily stable intracellular processes were found in the RE-deficient group.

The GO terms were manually grouped into 24 major functional categories (Table 12). As with the analysis of all REs, the RE-enriched categories included processes related to sensory perception and neurotransmission, immune function, lipid metabolism, detoxification, and xenobiotic response. Conversely, the RE-deficient categories involved protein synthesis, RNA transcription, intracellular communication, cell adhesion and interaction, cell cycle regulation, apoptosis, nucleic acid and carbohydrate metabolism, protein modifications, stress response, antiviral defense, chromatin organization, oxidative phosphorylation, and mitochondrial activity. Immune-related processes displayed mixed regulatory trends and were represented by 15 distinct GO terms (Table 13).

Table 12. Intracellular processes enriched or depleted in RE regulation based on GO and molecular pathway analysis for evolutionary young REs.

ID	Group of processes	RE enrichment by pathway analysis		RE enrichment by GO analysis		Overall status
		Enriched pathways	Deficient pathways	Enriched GO terms	Deficient GO terms	
1	Lipids metabolism	22	8	2	0	RE enriched
2	Signaling	28	40	8	31	RE deficient

3	Immune System	18	14	3	12	Shown separately
4	Cell cycle	1	6	0	62	RE deficient
5	Cell death	7	6	0	35	Ambiguous pattern
6	Amino acids and polyamines metabolism	13	5	0	0	RE enriched
7	Metabolism and detoxication of xenobiotics	8	0	2	0	RE enriched
8	Sulfur-linked reactions	6	0	0	0	RE enriched
9	Vitamins metabolism	10	0	0	0	RE enriched
10	Carbohydrates and related molecules metabolism	9	5	0	6	Ambiguous pattern
11	Nucleic base, nucleotides and nucleosides metabolism	5	3	0	14	Ambiguous pattern
12	Transport of small molecules	4	0	0	0	RE enriched
13	Blood clotting	3	0	0	0	RE enriched
14	Cytoskeleton, cell adhesion and migration	0	18	0	16	RE deficient
15	Endocytosis	0	4	0	0	RE deficient
16	Translation and protein quality control	0	23	0	105	RE deficient
17	Viruses	0	7	0	18	RE deficient
18	Signal perception and neurotransmission	0	0	22	0	RE enriched
19	RNA synthesis and degradation	0	0	0	80	RE deficient
20	DNA metabolism and chromatin	0	0	0	66	RE deficient
21	Protein localization and modification	0	0	0	20	RE deficient
22	Response to physical and chemical stress	0	0	0	15	RE deficient
23	Oxidative phosphorylation in mitochondria	0	0	0	19	RE deficient
24	Other/too general terms	18	12	18	231	N/A

Table 13. Immunity-associated processes showing RE enrichment or deficiency based on GO and molecular pathway analysis (evolutionary young REs).

Group of processes	RE enrichment by pathway analysis	RE enrichment by GO analysis	Overall status
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	Enriched pathways	Deficient pathways	Enriched GO terms	Deficient GO terms	
Innate immunity	5	2	0	9	Ambiguous pattern
Inflammation	3	3	0	0	Ambiguous pattern
T-cells mediated immunity	4	3	0	0	RE enriched
Other/Too general terms	5	0	3	3	N/A

A complementary analysis performed using Gorilla software revealed a distinct annotation network exclusively among RE-deficient genes, encompassing processes related to the development of the nervous system and reproductive organs. In contrast, no statistically significant enrichment ($p < 10^{-3}$) was observed for RE-enriched genes (Figure 39).

Figure 39. Hierarchically organized GO annotation terms identified by Gorilla software for RE-deficient genes associated with evolutionary young REs.

3.2.10. Functional features of top RE-enriched and RE-deficient molecular pathways (evolutionary young REs)

The analysis and manual classification of the top 152 RE-enriched and 152 RE-deficient molecular pathways for evolutionary young REs (listed in Supplementary File 13 in (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019) and summarized in Table 12) revealed results consistent with those obtained for the complete RE set.

Pathways enriched for REs were mainly associated with the metabolism of amino acids, polyamines, vitamins, lipids, sulfur, and carbohydrates; small molecule transport; xenobiotic detoxification and response; blood coagulation; as well as regulation of the cell cycle and programmed cell death. Conversely, RE-deficient pathways were linked to protein translation and post-translational modifications, intracellular signaling (including cell adhesion and interaction), cell cycle regulation and apoptosis, metabolism of nucleotides and nucleic acid bases, amino acids, polyamines, lipids, carbohydrates, and viral replication mechanisms. The overlap between gene-level (GO term) and pathway-level results was approximately 50%, lower than that observed for the full RE dataset (see Table 9 and Table 12).

Interestingly, immune-related pathways associated with innate immunity, T-cell responses, and inflammation were found in both RE-enriched and RE-deficient groups. In the first two categories, a greater number of pathways were RE-enriched than RE-deficient (Table 13).

3.2.11. Shared molecular processes identified via gene- and pathway-level analyses (evolutionary young REs)

A comparative assessment of RE-enriched and RE-deficient biological process groups identified through GO and molecular pathway analyses (Table 12, Table 13, and 40) revealed several consistent patterns. Among the RE-enriched processes, the following were highlighted: (1) lipid metabolism and (2) detoxification and xenobiotic metabolism. In contrast, the RE-deficient processes included: (3) cell cycle control, (4) cytoskeletal organization, cell adhesion, and migration, (5) protein synthesis and ribosomal biogenesis, (6) intracellular signaling, and (7) viral life cycle-related mechanisms.

Metabolism
of lipids

Detoxication and
metabolism of
xenobiotics

Protein translation
and ribosome
biogenesis

Intracellular
signaling pathways

Viral processes

Cell cycle

Cytoskeleton, cell
adhesion and
migration

Figure 40. RE-associated molecular processes identified for evolutionary young REs, classified as either enriched (left) or deficient (right) in RE-linked TFBS regulation.

The composition of these functional groups largely mirrored those identified for all REs, with the exception of an additional RE-deficient category, “cytoskeleton, cell adhesion, and migration”. This newly defined group comprised pathways related to cellular adhesion, cell-cell junctions, migration, myoblast fusion, and actin cytoskeleton remodeling.

Each group was supported by varying numbers of associated pathways and GO terms (Table 12). A schematic overview of these intracellular processes, as influenced by RE enrichment or deficiency among evolutionary young REs, is presented in Figure 40, along with the corresponding number of features. Twelve additional functional categories (~50%) were identified as either RE-enriched or RE-deficient using only one of the two analytical approaches (gene-based or pathway-based), while four groups (~17% of all considered) displayed inconsistent trends across both methods (Table 12). Similarly, the analysis of immunity-related processes did not yield a consistent pattern between GO term and pathway-based results (Table 13).

3.2.12. Discussion of main findings from the RE-linked TFBS analysis across 13 human cell lines

In this part of the analysis, we conducted a novel integrative analysis of REs associated with TFBS to explore their impact on molecular processes across 13 human cell lines representing eight tissues. As in the case of the previously described K562-only analysis, this investigation spanned two evolutionary timescales and utilized two independent analytical strategies: (i) GO-based annotation for gene-level insights and (ii) high-throughput pathway analysis using the Oncobox molecular pathway database. These complementary approaches allowed us to identify a diverse set of intracellular pathways that are either enriched or deficient in RE-linked TFBS regulation, which was a step forward compared to the K562-only analysis and formed the scaffold of the RetroSpect methodology (Nikitin, Sorokin, et al., 2019).

To examine the regulatory effects across evolutionary time, we followed the K562-only analysis framework and stratified REs into two categories based on sequence divergence from consensus: (1) all REs, representing the broader scale of mammalian radiation, and (2) evolutionary young REs, corresponding to more recent divergence, including the split of human evolutionary lineage and New World monkeys. For the full RE dataset, 46% of processes showed concordance across both analysis methods, 50% were identified uniquely by one approach, and 4% showed conflicting patterns. Among the consistently regulated processes, those enriched in REs included: posttranscriptional silencing by small RNAs, DNA repair, amino acid and lipid metabolism, detoxication/xenobiotic processing, sensory perception, neurotransmission, fertilization, and T/NK-cell immune responses. In contrast, RE-deficient processes were mainly associated with nucleotide and DNA metabolism, chromatin regulation, protein biosynthesis, intracellular signaling, and intracellular antiviral mechanisms.

At the level of evolutionary young REs, concordance between gene- and pathway-level results dropped to 33%, indicating that this analytical framework may be more robust for identifying conserved regulatory effects over longer evolutionary timescales. The observed variability at the shorter evolutionary timescale may reflect a more dynamic and less stable regulatory influence of young REs that was not yet shaped by long-term selection pressures.

The molecular processes impacted by RE-linked TFBSs reflect cumulative changes in gene regulation over time. Unlike single nucleotide variants, which typically produce gradual effects (M. Lynch et al., 2016), RE insertions can rapidly introduce large, non-homologous and non-orthologous DNA segments that harbor functional TFBSs (Burns & Boeke, 2012), potentially reshaping regulatory networks near genes and altering gene regulatory networks (Cheatle Jarvela & Hinman, 2015), being the one of the major sources of novel TFBS in the human genome (Cordaux & Batzer, 2009; Lander et al., 2001; Suntsova et al., 2015) and even protein-coding genes, as it was discussed earlier (Lavialle et al., 2013). These RE-derived sequences can further evolve through mutations and epigenetic changes, altering TFBS profiles and contributing to regulatory innovation (Garazha et al., 2015; Ito et al., 2017). Thus, a higher density of RE-linked TFBSs may serve as an indicator of accelerated regulatory evolution.

In several key respects, the findings of the current 13 human cell lines analysis concerning the regulatory evolution of human molecular pathways align well with prior research employing distinct methodologies. Core biological processes such as ribosome biogenesis, protein synthesis, and nucleotide and DNA metabolism are among the most evolutionarily conserved functions across all domains of life, with purine nucleotide metabolic enzymes (containing P-loop hydrolase fold) being the most ancient, whereas more recent pathways such as amino acids and carbohydrates metabolism recruited later forming the palimpsest of metabolic pathways (Caetano-Anollés et al., 2009; Fox, 2010). Our analyses indicate that the regulatory evolution of these processes has also proceeded at a comparatively slow rate within the human lineage, reinforcing their status as functionally constrained systems. In contrast, pathways associated with DNA repair exhibit a markedly higher rate of regulatory evolution, consistent with the intrinsic redundancy and divergent evolution of DNA repair enzyme systems (O'Brien, 2006). Such systems, particularly in long-lived organisms, are subject to stringent regulatory control to mitigate the risk of proliferative pathologies (Hoeijmakers, 2009).

Intriguingly, divergent evolutionary trajectories were observed within the immune system. Specifically, regulatory networks underpinning T cell- and NK cell-mediated (intercellular) antiviral responses appear to be evolving more rapidly, whereas the intracellular antiviral defense mechanisms exhibit greater regulatory stability. This dichotomy is concordant with the understanding that the adaptive T cell immune response represents a more recent

evolutionary acquisition (Boehm & Swann, 2014), potentially allowing greater latitude for regulatory innovation and higher rate of regulatory evolution. Similarly, regulatory elements associated with amino acid and lipid metabolism also demonstrate accelerated evolution, possibly reflecting adaptive shifts in dietary regimes over evolutionary time (Caetano-Anollés et al., 2009).

Of particular note is the pronounced evolutionary dynamism of pathways involved in posttranscriptional gene silencing mediated by small RNAs. This regulatory mechanism is critical for the suppression of newly integrated REs and viruses (Moazed, 2009), and its rapid evolution is likely driven by an ongoing intragenomic conflict among host genes, REs, and exogenous pathogens - effectively constituting an evolutionary arms race within the genome.

The present analyses - comprising both the single-cell line investigation in K562 and the broader analysis across 13 distinct human cell lines - were specifically focused on examining the evolutionary dynamics of gene regulation at the level of TFBSs. Nonetheless, investigations that incorporate additional epigenomic features - such as covalent histone modifications, DNA methylation profiles, and nucleosome positioning - could further elucidate the regulatory roles and evolutionary consequences of transposable elements. Because histone modifications can exert either activating or repressive effects on gene expression, dissecting the contribution of REs to regulatory evolution through specific histone marks could yield a more nuanced, integrative model of epigenetic dynamics. To a certain degree, this objective has been achieved, and the corresponding findings are presented in the following sections on covalent histone modification analyses.

A significant methodological limitation of both analyses discussed is the aggregation of TFBS data from hundreds transcription factors into a single composite score for each gene. While this provides a useful global estimate of regulatory load, it likely obscures functionally relevant variation linked to tissue-specific TF activity or mechanistic diversity. Stratifying TFs based on such criteria in future analyses may yield more granular insights into RE-mediated regulatory evolution. Ultimately, the broader application of the computational strategy introduced here across a range of epigenomic tracks is expected to contribute substantially to our understanding of the principles governing the evolution of complex regulatory networks in the human genome.

3.3. RE-linked enhancer chromatin modification H3K4me1 analysis in five human cell lines

3.3.1. Genes and pathways modulated by RE-linked enhancer histone modification marks

Advances in high-throughput ChIP-seq protocols have facilitated genome-wide identification of functional enhancers (Blinka et al., 2017). The monomethylation of histone H3 at lysine 4 (H3K4me1) serves as a key epigenetic signature marking both active and poised enhancer elements (Calo & Wysocka, 2013). Genome-scale spatially-resolved maps of H3K4me1 distribution have been generated (Deng et al., 2022) and are routinely employed in studies of transcriptional regulation (Dvoretzkova et al., 2024). When examined through an evolutionary lens, these epigenomic datasets reveal a dynamic enhancer landscape subject to continual turnover and diversification (Long et al., 2016). In particular, enhancers derived from transposable elements can drive animal phenotypic innovation (Rubinstein & de Souza, 2013), contribute to the emergence of novel regulatory elements via retro-copies (Carelli et al., 2018), and even underpin the development of lineage-specific structures such as the mammalian neocortex (Emera et al., 2016), as it was described in greater details in the Literature review section.

To quantify the influence of REs on gene regulation via H3K4me1 histone marks, we computed GRE and NGRE scores for 24,070 human genes (Supplementary Table S4 in (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019)) across five cell lines - MCF-7, K562, HepG2, HeLa S3, and GM12878 - representing four distinct tissue types. In total, 2,841,853 H3K4me1 ChIP-seq peaks were retrieved from the ENCODE repository, with 482,894 peaks for MCF-7, 1,075,569 for K562, 705,632 for HepG2, 339,874 for HeLa S3, and 237,884 for GM12878.

Next, we assessed the relationship between these H3K4me1 enrichment profiles and corresponding RNA-seq gene expression data (Figure 41). RNA sequencing was selected due to its status as the gold standard for transcriptome profiling (Kukurba & Montgomery, 2015; Nagalakshmi et al., 2010; Palomares et al., 2019). At the ENCODE repository we used six RNA-seq experiments for GM12878, ten for HepG2, and twenty-two for K562; data were not available for MCF-7 or HeLa S3 at the time of the analysis. We observed a positive correlation between H3K4me1 signal and transcript abundance (Figure 41). Correlations

were strongest for lncRNAs (Figure 41D), weakest for microRNAs (Figure 41C), and intermediate for protein-coding genes (Figure 41B). The highest correlation coefficients occurred when matching histone and expression datasets from the same cell line (Figure 41), confirming that the ENCODE H3K4me1 profiles accurately reflect their anticipated regulatory roles.

Figure 41. Correlation between H3K4me1 enrichment and transcript abundance across matched RNA-seq datasets. H3K4me1 ChIP-seq signal intensity (y-axis) was plotted against normalized gene expression values (x-axis) for six GM12878, ten HepG2, and twenty-two K562 RNA-seq experiments. Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated for (A) the complete set of annotated genes, (B) protein-coding genes, (C) microRNA genes, and (D) lncRNA genes.

We next evaluated the consistency of gene-level RE-linked regulatory enrichment scores (GRE and NGRE) across the five cell lines. To this end, we computed pairwise Pearson correlation coefficients of GRE (Figure 42A) and NGRE (Figure 42B) values on a per-gene basis for all cell line combinations.

Figure 42. Pairwise comparison of RE-linked regulatory enrichment metrics across five human cell lines. Each panel displays a heatmap of Pearson correlation coefficients between the indicated score for all gene or pathway pairs, with cell lines labeled on both axes. (A) GRE (gene-level enrichment), (B) NGRE (normalized gene-level enrichment), (C) PII (pathway involvement index), and (D) NPPI (normalized pathway involvement index). The color gradient reflects the magnitude of the correlation coefficient.

The gene-level enrichment metrics exhibited strong concordance across all five cell lines, with pairwise Pearson correlation coefficients ranging from 0.53 to 0.74 for GRE and from 0.68 to 0.83 for NGRE. Likewise, the pathway-level indices (PII and NPPI) demonstrated similarly high intercell line correlations (Figure 42C, D). These results confirm that the RE-linked enrichment scores are consistent among the examined cell lines, justifying the use of gene-wise arithmetic means across cell lines for subsequent RetroSpect analyses.

To pinpoint genes with disproportionately high or low RE impact, we performed linear regression on the aggregated GRE and NGRE values using least squares (Charnes et al.,

1976), constraining the intercept to zero (Figure 43). Genes situated above the resulting trend line - where normalized enrichment (NGRE) exceeds absolute enrichment (GRE) - were classified as RE-enriched, whereas those lying below the line were designated RE-deficient.

Figure 43. Scatterplot of gene-level RE-linked enrichment metrics, with GRE on the x-axis and NGRE on the y-axis. Each point corresponds to an individual gene, colored according to its RE classification: red for RE-enriched, blue for intermediate, and green for RE-deficient. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) and associated p -value are displayed in the plot.

We then selected the top and bottom 5% of genes based on their perpendicular distance from the NGRE–GRE regression line; these sets were defined as RE-enriched and RE-deficient, respectively (see Supplementary Table S5 in (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019)). An analogous procedure was applied to the molecular pathway data (Figures 42C, D and 44). For each of the 3,095 pathways, we computed both the absolute involvement index (PII) and its normalized counterpart (NPII) across the same five cell lines (Supplementary Table S6 in (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019)). Pairwise Pearson correlations of PII scores between cell lines

ranged from 0.53 to 0.66, while NPII correlations ranged from 0.44 to 0.69 (Figures 42C, D). Given these high levels of concordance, we proceeded with analyses using the cell-line averaged PII and NPII values.

Figure 44. Scatterplot of molecular pathway RE-linked enrichment metrics, with PII on the x-axis and NPII on the y-axis. Each point corresponds to a single pathway, colored by its RE classification: red for RE-enriched, blue for intermediate, and green for RE-deficient pathways. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) and the associated p-value are indicated on the plot.

Consistent with the gene-level analysis, we constructed a linear regression model for molecular pathways and selected the top and bottom 5% of pathways exhibiting the greatest deviations from the trend line. These were classified as RE-enriched and RE-deficient pathways, respectively (see Supplementary Table S7 in (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019)).

3.3.2. Functional characterization of RE-enriched and RE-deficient genes

To elucidate the biological roles of genes exhibiting extreme regulatory enrichment or depletion by RE-linked enhancer histone modification H3K4me1, we conducted GO enrichment analyses using the DAVID platform. GO terms spanning the categories of Molecular Function, Biological Process, and Cellular Component were retrieved (T. G. O. Consortium et al., 2023; Pitarch et al., 2025), and subsequently grouped into biologically meaningful categories through manual curation.

3.3.2.1. RE-enriched genes by H3K4me1

Within the RE-enriched gene set (Supplementary Table S5 (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019)), a total of 32 significantly enriched GO terms ($p < 0.05$) were identified using DAVID (Supplementary Table S8 in (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019)), which were categorized into nine functional clusters. These included: (i) six terms associated with RNA synthesis and degradation; (ii) four terms related to DNA-associated and chromatin-remodeling processes; (iii) three terms pertaining to translational machinery; (iv) three terms involved in lipid metabolism; (v) three terms linked to metal ion homeostasis and transport; (vi) two terms implicating immune system processes; (vii) two terms related to sensory perception and neurotransmission; and (viii) two terms associated with cell cycle regulation. An additional category labeled “Other and general terms” comprised seven unique GO terms representing discrete biological functions not captured in the above categories.

3.3.2.2. RE-deficient genes by H3K4me1

Analysis of the RE-deficient gene set (Supplementary Table S5 in (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019)) revealed a broader spectrum of functional categories compared to the RE-enriched set. In total, 169 GO terms passed the statistical significance threshold and were classified into 16 distinct biological categories (Supplementary Table S8 in (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019)). These included: (i) 45 terms associated with morphogenetic processes; (ii) 23 terms linked to RNA synthesis and degradation; (iii) 15 terms pertaining to various molecular signaling pathways; (iv) four terms related to hormonal signaling; (v) 11 terms involved in programmed cell death; (vi) eight terms connected to immune-related processes; (vii) two terms associated with protein ubiquitination and proteolysis; (viii) seven terms related to protein aggregation and intracellular import; (ix) 12 terms of cell adhesion, migration, and intercellular interactions; (x) six terms associated with mitotic and cell cycle regulation; (xi)

four terms linked to ion transport mechanisms; (xii) three terms associated with chromatin remodeling and DNA-related processes; (xiii) two terms related to cellular stress responses; and (xiv) two terms describing intracellular antiviral responses. The remaining 18 GO terms were grouped under the “Other and general terms” category, reflecting a diverse array of biological functions not encompassed by the previous categories (Table 15).

3.3.3. Alternative GO annotation analysis

As an independent validation, we also performed functional enrichment analysis using the GOrilla platform and the Gene Ontology Biological Process database (Eden et al., 2009). In the case of RE-enriched genes (Supplementary File S9 in (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019)), this approach highlighted gene silencing by microRNAs and RNA catabolic processes as the primary biological themes. For the RE-deficient gene set (Supplementary File S10 in (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019)), the predominant processes identified were (i) protein ubiquitination and (ii) negative regulation of TORC1 signaling.

3.3.4. Enrichment of non-coding RNA genes

Given the regulatory functions of non-coding RNA molecules such as microRNAs and lncRNAs, we assessed their representation within the RE-enriched and RE-deficient gene sets. Using a hypergeometric probability model, we quantified the likelihood of observing the actual number of microRNA and lncRNA genes in each set under random sampling assumptions. The statistical results of this enrichment analysis are presented in Table 14.

Table 14. Assessment of RE-associated H3K4me1 regulatory enrichment in human non-coding RNA genes.

Group	Non-coding RNA class	Observed number of non-coding RNA genes	Expected number (random model)	Hypergeometric p-value (overrepresentation)	Hypergeometric p-value (underrepresentation)	Conclusion
RE-enriched	lncRNA	145	74	2.22×10^{-8}	0.99999998	lncRNAs are overrepresented
RE-deficient	lncRNA	54	74	0.9951	0.0049	lncRNAs are underrepresented

RE-enriched	microRNA	145	90	3.49×10^{-8}	0.99999997	microRNAs are overrepresented
RE-deficient	microRNA	94	90	0.33	0.67	microRNAs are neither over- nor underrepresented

Our results demonstrated a marked overrepresentation of both microRNA and lncRNA genes within the RE-enriched gene group, with corresponding p -values of 2.22×10^{-8} and 3.49×10^{-8} , respectively. Additionally, lncRNA genes were significantly underrepresented among RE-deficient genes ($p = 0.0049$), whereas no such underrepresentation was observed for microRNA genes ($p = 0.33$).

3.3.5. Significance assessment of RE-based functional annotations

To assess the statistical relevance of the functional annotations derived from RE-based gene classification, we performed 500 random permutations of gene names and their associated GRE or NGRE values. For each permutation, 1204 genes from the top and bottom extremes were randomly selected, mirroring the size of the actual RE-enriched and RE-deficient gene sets. These surrogate gene sets were subjected to the same GO enrichment analysis using the DAVID tool (*DAVID Functional Annotation Bioinformatics Microarray Analysis*, n.d.), and the top 100 GO terms were retained based on lowest p -values.

We then compared the distributions of p -values obtained from the real data with those from the random permutations (Figure 45A and 45B for RE-enriched and RE-deficient genes, respectively). The analysis revealed that functional annotations for RE-deficient genes were largely robust, as indicated by a distribution peak (mode) of p -values that was lower in the actual data than in the random sets (Figure 45B). In contrast, the GO terms associated with RE-enriched genes showed substantial overlap with the random distribution (Figure 45A), although a few terms exhibited distinctly lower p -values than any found in the random sets.

Importantly, across all 500 permutations, none produced GO terms with p -values lower than those observed in the real RE-enriched or RE-deficient gene groups. Consequently, the empirical q -values for both gene categories were estimated to be below 0.002 as in the case

of TFBS analysis (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019), confirming the high statistical confidence in the biological processes identified.

Figure 45. Randomized validation of GO term enrichment for RE-enriched (A) and RE-deficient (B) gene sets.

3.3.6. Functional characterization of top RE-enriched and RE-deficient molecular pathways

To investigate the biological roles of molecular pathways identified as most RE-enriched and RE-deficient, we performed manual classification of these pathways into functional categories based on their known biological activities.

3.3.6.1. RE-enriched pathways

Among the top 5% of pathways (155 in total; Supplementary Table S7 in (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019)), we assigned 14 distinct functional categories. Specifically, 33 pathways were categorized as general signaling cascades, 22 were linked to cell cycle regulation and mitotic processes, 7 were associated with programmed cell death, 16 were related to morphogenesis, 12 were involved in lipid metabolism, 13 reflected processes of cell adhesion, migration, and intercellular communication, and 11 were immune-related.

Additional categories included DNA metabolism and chromatin remodeling (7 pathways), cytoskeleton organization (7), endocytosis (5), RNA synthesis and degradation (3), amino acid metabolism (2), and sensory perception and neurotransmission (3). Fourteen pathways that did not fit into these categories were grouped under “Other pathways”.

3.3.6.2. RE-deficient pathways

For the bottom 5% of pathways (also 155), we identified 17 functional categories (Supplementary Table S7 in (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019)). General signaling pathways made up the largest group (38), followed by immune-related pathways (22), apoptosis-associated pathways (13), and those involved in the cell cycle (3). Additional categories included: cell adhesion, migration and interaction (15), protein aggregation and intracellular transport (5), translation and protein folding (3), lipid metabolism (8), xenobiotic detoxification (8), morphogenesis (8), DNA-related processes (6), amino acid metabolism (4), hormone signaling (3), metal ion metabolism and transport (3), endocytosis (4), and cytoskeleton organization (2). 10 unique pathways were grouped as “Other pathways”.

3.3.7. Concordance between gene- and pathway-based RE functional profiles

We next compared the functional categories identified as RE-enriched or RE-deficient through both gene-level (GO-based) and pathway-level analyses, as summarized in Table 15.

Table 15. Functional enrichment of molecular processes based on RE status inferred from GO term and pathway-level analyses.

Group of Processes	Pathway analysis		GO Analysis		Overall status
	Enriched	Deficient	Enriched	Deficient	
Posttranscriptional silencing by small RNAs	1	0	1	0	enriched

DNA metabolism and chromatin structure	7	6	4	3	enriched
Sensory perception and neurotransmission	3	0	2	0	enriched
Lipids metabolism	12	8	3	0	enriched
Endocytosis	5	4	0	0	enriched
Immune system	11	21	2	8	deficient
Protein ubiquitination and degradation	0	5	0	2	deficient
Cell adhesion, migration and interaction	13	15	0	12	deficient
Metals metabolism and ion transport	0	3	3	4	deficient
Cell death	7	13	0	11	deficient
General signaling pathways	33	38	0	15	deficient
Hormones signaling pathways	0	3	0	4	deficient
Stress response	0	0	0	2	deficient
Response to viruses	0	0	0	2	deficient
Amino acids metabolism	2	4	0	0	deficient
Detoxication of xenobiotics	0	8	0	0	deficient
Protein aggregation and import	0	0	0	7	deficient
Morphogenesis	16	9	0	45	ambiguous

Cytoskeleton	7	2	0	7	ambiguous
RNA synthesis and degradation	3	0	6	23	ambiguous
Translation, protein export and folding	0	3	3	0	ambiguous
Cell cycle and mitosis	22	3	2	6	ambiguous
Other processes	14	10	7	18	ambiguous

Among the functional groups annotated during both pathway and GO analyses, three were found to be RE-enriched, seven were RE-deficient, and five displayed conflicting classification: four appeared RE-enriched in pathway analysis but RE-deficient in GO annotation, while one group exhibited the opposite trend. The overall agreement between these two approaches, as measured by the Matthews correlation coefficient (Chicco & Jurman, 2020), was 0.342, reflecting a moderate level of consistency. The overlapping functional categories across analyses included the following biological pathways and regulatory mechanisms.

3.3.7.1. RE-enriched functional categories

1. Post-transcriptional gene silencing by small RNAs

Identified via GOrilla-based enrichment analysis of RE-enriched genes, this group was primarily composed of processes involving microRNA-mediated suppression of gene expression.

2. DNA metabolism and chromatin dynamics

This category encompassed pathways involved in double-strand break repair, transcription-coupled nucleotide excision repair, DNA strand displacement activity, and chromatin remodeling.

3. Sensory function and neurotransmitter signaling

This group included olfactory receptor activity - especially metabotropic glutamate receptors (class C3) related to pheromone detection - and the cone cells retinoid cycle, which is essential for color vision in primates.

4. **Lipid metabolism**

This group comprised biosynthesis and desaturation of fatty acids, β -oxidation, phospholipase A2 activity, and sterol modification via cytochrome P450 enzymes.

3.3.7.2. **RE-deficient functional categories**

1. **Immune response pathways**

A diverse set of immune-related processes including dendritic cell chemotaxis, cytokine (IL-1, IL-3, IL-4) production, signaling via TLR and PD-1, asthma-related pathways, and RAS GTPase activation in B-cells.

2. **Protein ubiquitination and degradation**

Included functions related to ubiquitin ligase activity, recognition of K63-linked polyubiquitin chains (often non-degradative), proteasomal protein degradation, and autoubiquitination of E3 ligases.

3. **Cell adhesion, motility, and intercellular communication**

Covered tight junction formation, E-cadherin-mediated adhesion, interactions with the extracellular matrix (including hyaluronidase activity, laminin binding, and matrix metalloproteinase inhibition), as well as processes related to angiogenesis via MMIF and platelet aggregation.

4. **Metal ion homeostasis and transport**

Included pathways involving zinc and calcium binding, as well as the activity of chloride and potassium ion channels.

5. **Cell death pathways**

Encompassed multiple pro-apoptotic signaling cascades, including those mediated by p53, MEF2D-driven apoptosis in T cells, BAD translocation to mitochondria, PTEN-induced cell cycle arrest, caspase activation, and mitochondrial outer membrane permeabilization.

6. **General signaling networks**

This diverse group included several core signaling pathways such as NF- κ B, VEGF, EGF, IGF, and mTOR.

7. **Hormonal signaling mechanisms**

Included signaling responses to steroid hormones like estrogen and testosterone, as well as regulation of estrogen receptor activity via PELP1.

3.3.8. Overview and discussion of the results derived from the RE-linked H3K4me1 tags analysis

In the current H3K4me1 analysis, we investigated genome-wide enrichment patterns of the H3K4me1 histone modification to assess the extent to which RE-associated enhancers influence the regulation of human genes and biological pathways. Data for this analysis were obtained from the ENCODE database and encompassed five human cell lines derived from various tissues (MCF-7, K562, HepG2, HeLaS3, and GM12878), which were processed using the RetroSpect analytical framework (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019; Nikitin, Sorokin, et al., 2019). Due to limited availability of high-throughput epigenomic datasets from normal human tissues, we relied on established cell lines as a proxy. These lines collectively represented four distinct tissue types. Notably, enrichment profiles for histone marks showed high inter-line correlation, implying that tissue-specific differences had only a limited influence on the overall signal.

Enhancers are distal cis-regulatory elements that exert long-range control over gene expression, playing a pivotal role in defining cell-type- and cell-state-specific transcriptional landscapes (Heintzman et al., 2009). The human genome is estimated to contain over one million enhancer elements (Pennacchio et al., 2013). The chromatin architecture of enhancers is marked by a diverse array of epigenetic features, including specific histone modifications (Heintzman et al., 2009), TFBS (Spitz & Furlong, 2012), DNase I hypersensitive regions (Gross & Garrard, 1988), 3D interactions (Schoenfelder et al., 2018), and the production of enhancer-associated non-coding RNAs (eRNAs) (Inukai et al., 2017a; Natoli & Andrau, 2012).

The functional output of enhancers is largely dictated by the cooperative and combinatorial binding of transcription factors to densely clustered TFBS, including both lineage-determining factors and transcriptional effectors downstream of signaling pathways. This facilitates the integration of intrinsic developmental cues and extrinsic stimuli in the regulation of gene activity (Inukai et al., 2017a). In the previously described work employing the RetroSpect approach, we examined the contribution of RE-associated TFBS to gene regulation in humans, identifying a set of conserved molecular pathways that were either significantly enriched or underrepresented in such RE-linked regulation (A. Buzdin et al., 2018; Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019).

Although TFBS represent important elements of gene regulation, they are not exclusive to enhancers (Inukai et al., 2017a). The histone modification H3K4me1, however, is widely accepted as a hallmark of both active and poised enhancer elements (Bogdanović et al., 2012; Bonn et al., 2012). Rather than marking specific enhancer states, H3K4me1 delineates a broader enhancer-associated regulatory landscape - encompassing enhancers in active, poised, or deactivated states (Calo & Wysocka, 2013). Other enhancer-associated chromatin marks, such as H3K27ac, are typically superimposed on pre-existing H3K4me1-marked regions and are lost upon enhancer deactivation (Bogdanović et al., 2012; Bonn et al., 2012; Calo & Wysocka, 2013). Based on this, we employed H3K4me1 as a representative marker to identify genes and molecular pathways exhibiting enrichment or depletion of RE-associated enhancer regulation - thus serving as an indicator of regulatory evolutionary influence mediated by REs.

Our analysis revealed a striking overrepresentation of non-coding RNA genes - specifically microRNAs and lncRNAs - within the set of genes enriched in RE-associated enhancer regulation. Additionally, the GO term “gene silencing by microRNA and RNA degradation” emerged as the most significantly enriched RE-associated biological process, as identified by Gorilla software analysis. Notably, a similar enrichment pattern was previously reported in our earlier study focusing on RE-associated TFBS regulation (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019), reinforcing the idea that non-coding RNAs constitute a central conduit through which REs mediate regulatory evolution. The deep interconnection between non-coding RNAs and REs is well established, as RE insertions can give rise to novel non-coding RNA genes with the potential to acquire functional relevance through evolutionary selection (Ganesh & Svoboda, 2016). Furthermore, the role of non-coding RNAs in regulatory innovation is evolutionarily ancient - exemplified by piRNAs, which emerged during early metazoan evolution and contributed to the establishment of multicellular regulatory complexity (Gaiti et al., 2017). Epigenetic silencing mechanisms involving small non-coding RNAs, such as RNA interference, have also co-evolved in response to selective pressures imposed by REs and retroviruses, exemplifying a broader host-pathogen arms race (Hartmann, 2017). Collectively, our findings - now supported at both TFBS and enhancer (H3K4me1) levels - underscore the pivotal role of non-coding RNAs in facilitating RE-driven regulatory innovation.

Using the RetroSpect annotation framework, we identified consensus groups of biological processes that are either enriched or depleted in RE-associated enhancer regulation. Compared to the previous TFBS-based RetroSpect analysis, which identified eight RE-enriched process groups (described in the previous sections and in (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019)), the present enhancer-based analysis yielded three such groups. This reduction is likely attributable to the lower number of independent data tracks incorporated in the current protocol (one per cell line) versus the extensive dataset of over 4000 profiles used in the earlier TFBS-focused study. In addition, the discrepancy may reflect intrinsic biological differences in the regulatory mechanisms assessed. Specifically, while REs can exert influence through long-range enhancer elements, they also impact regulation via promoter-proximal TFBS located near TSS (Gogvadze & Buzdin, 2009). Thus, the regulatory scope of RE-associated TFBS is likely broader than that mediated solely by enhancer activity, potentially accounting for the more limited set of processes identified in this enhancer-focused analysis.

Despite differences in the molecular mechanisms assessed, the overall pattern of biological processes affected by RE-associated enhancers is broadly consistent with the previous findings. Notably, the strong enrichment of RE-linked enhancers within the “Sensory perception and neurotransmission” category aligns with the previous observations of similar enrichment based on RE-associated TFBS analysis (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019). This recurring enrichment supports the hypothesis that sensory systems and the nervous system have undergone accelerated regulatory evolution in mammals. Indeed, much of the mammalian forebrain is dedicated to processing sensory input and has demonstrated rapid evolutionary development (Kaas, 1989).

A similar evolutionary trend is evident for lipid metabolism, which also emerged as RE-enriched in the current enhancer-focused analysis. This corroborates earlier TFBS-based results (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019), and is further supported by independent lipidomic studies that suggest accelerated evolution of lipid profiles in primates - possibly linked to the increasing complexity of the central nervous system, for which lipid composition is critical (Khrameeva et al., 2018). Furthermore, positive selection and coevolution among enzymes involved in lipid metabolism have been reported in primates (Lin et al., 2012), likely as part of adaptive responses to evolving energy demands and thermoregulation (Hulbert & Else, 1989).

The third prominent RE-enriched functional group, “DNA metabolism and chromatin structure”, mainly encompasses DNA repair pathways. This finding is also consistent with previous TFBS-based analyses (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019) and may reflect the inherent redundancy and functional flexibility (catalytic promiscuity) of DNA repair mechanisms (O’Brien, 2006).

Conversely, several RE-deficient (i.e., evolutionarily conserved) biological processes identified here mirror earlier results based on TFBS analysis (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019) and are in line with broader evolutionary principles. The “Protein ubiquitination and degradation” group, for instance, represents a highly conserved set of core intracellular processes (Allan & Phillips, 2017). Similarly, the “General signaling pathways” group again emerged as relatively conserved, likely due to the intrinsic complexity and interdependence of key intracellular signaling mechanisms. In multicellular organisms with extended lifespans, such as primates, disruptions in these signaling systems can result in severe developmental or proliferative disorders (van Dam et al., 2011). While TFBS and enhancers may both contribute to regulatory evolution, it is important to note that alterations in signaling pathways can also arise through point mutations, structural changes in regulatory regions (e.g., duplications, deletions, or translocations), and increased network complexity over time (Signor & Nuzhdin, 2018; Soyer & Bonhoeffer, 2006).

Interestingly, while our previous TFBS-based study presented a mixed picture for immune-related processes - with enrichment in cellular immune responses but depletion in antiviral defense mechanisms (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019) - the current enhancer-based analysis identified the “Immune system” group primarily as RE-deficient. This discrepancy may stem from the reduced resolution of the enhancer analysis, which involved a smaller dataset (based on H3K4me1 marks) relative to the more comprehensive TFBS dataset analyzed previously. Additionally, we observed three RE-deficient groups in the current study - “Cell adhesion, migration, and interaction”, “Cell death”, and “Hormone signaling pathways” - that were not identified as significant in the TFBS-based analysis (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019). Of note, “Hormone signaling pathways” were previously found to be RE-enriched only in the pathway-based segment of that study. One plausible explanation for this divergence is that RE-linked regulatory activity in these categories may be more promoter-proximal rather than enhancer-mediated. Although further statistical validation is necessary, this asymmetry could be biologically grounded. Enhancers typically exert long-range effects

that depend on both cis-acting elements (e.g., insulators, anchor elements) and trans-acting factors (e.g., CTCF proteins, co-activators) for appropriate promoter interaction (Ko et al., 2017; Zabidi & Stark, 2016). As such, the de novo emergence of an RE-associated enhancer may introduce higher levels of regulatory noise than a TFBS insertion near an existing promoter. In biological contexts that demand precise gene expression control - such as developmentally crucial processes - the most disruptive RE insertions may be subject to purifying selection or epigenetic silencing (Hancks & Kazazian, 2016). Notably, a similar regulatory conservation pattern was observed for the “Metals metabolism and ion transport” group.

Despite substantial concordance between the present results and the earlier TFBS-based analysis (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019), several differences remain. Specifically, ten functional groups identified in the TFBS analysis were not recovered here, while three novel groups - “Endocytosis”, “Morphogenesis” and “Cytoskeleton” - emerged exclusively in the enhancer-based assessment, which could reflect long-range regulatory interactions mediated by distal enhancers rather than proximal elements. Among the groups annotated in both studies, six ones displayed consistent RE enrichment or deficiency across both GO and pathway annotations, five showed agreement based on a single annotation type (in either study), and eight were assigned divergent statuses. A summary of these comparative statistics is presented in Table 16.

Table 16. Comparative analysis of distinct functional process groups identified in the present study and in the TFBS-based analysis (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019).

Group of processes	Current study		TFBS study		Comment
	Overall status	Type of analysis	Status	Type of analysis	
		(Pathways/GO /Consensus)		(Pathways/GO /Consensus)	
Consensus match					
Sensory perception and neurotransmission	enriched	consensus	enriched	Consensus	

Lipids metabolism	enriched	consensus	enriched	consensus	
Protein ubiquitination and degradation	deficient	consensus	deficient	consensus	
Posttranscriptional silencing by small RNAs	enriched	consensus	enriched	consensus	Identified by Gorilla software and validated using hypergeometric enrichment in both studies
DNA metabolism and chromatin structure	enriched	consensus	enriched	consensus	Corresponds to “DNA repair” in the TFBS study
General signaling pathways	deficient	consensus	deficient	consensus	
Match by Overall Status					
Stress response	deficient	GO	deficient	GO	
Cell adhesion, migration and interaction	deficient	consensus	deficient	GO	
Cell death	deficient	consensus	deficient	GO	
Protein aggregation and import	deficient	GO	deficient	GO	Corresponds to “Protein localization and modification” in the TFBS study
Response to viruses	deficient	GO	deficient	consensus	
Does not Match					
Immune system	deficient	consensus	ambiguous	-	

Metals metabolism and ion transport	deficient	consensus	enriched	GO	
Hormones signaling pathways	deficient	consensus	enriched	pathways	Corresponds to “Hormones” in the TFBS study
Amino acids metabolism	deficient	pathways	enriched	consensus	
Detoxication of xenobiotics	deficient	pathways	enriched	consensus	
RNA synthesis and degradation	ambiguous	-	deficient	GO	
Translation, protein export and folding	ambiguous	-	deficient	consensus	Corresponds to “Translation and protein quality control” in the TFBS study
Cell cycle and mitosis	ambiguous	-	deficient	GO	
Group Appears Only in one of the Studies					
Endocytosis	enriched	pathways	-		
Morphogenesis	ambiguous	-	-	-	
Cytoskeleton	ambiguous	-	-	-	
Cellular immune response (T cells and NK cells)	-	-	enriched	consensus	
Fertilization	-	-	enriched	consensus	
Vitamin metabolism	-	-	enriched	pathways	
Molecular transport	-	-	enriched	pathways	

Sulfur metabolism and linked redox reactions	-	-	enriched	pathways	
Response to phorbol acetate	-	-	deficient	GO	
Electron transfer reactions	-	-	deficient	GO	
Mitochondria	-	-	deficient	GO	
Nucleic base, nucleosides and nucleotides metabolism	-	-	deficient	consensus	
Carbohydrates metabolism	-	-	ambiguous	-	

The identification of eight functional groups with divergent RE-enrichment statuses across the two studies may be explained by heterogeneous evolutionary trends within each group. For instance, the “Cell cycle and mitosis” category may encompass both rapidly evolving regulatory circuits - such as those modulating the cell cycle via growth factor signaling - and highly conserved processes - such as mitotic spindle assembly. Although this hypothesis remains speculative, previous work has demonstrated that the eukaryotic cell cycle incorporates both evolutionarily stable and dynamic components (Harashima et al., 2013). Further investigation is needed to elucidate the evolutionary trajectories of regulatory processes in categories such as “Immunity”, “Metals metabolism and ion transport”, “Hormone signaling pathways”, “Amino acid metabolism”, “Detoxification of xenobiotics”, “RNA synthesis and degradation”, “Translation”, “Protein export and folding”, and “Cell cycle and mitosis”.

As in the case of the described earlier TFBS analyses, this study employed data derived from human cell lines rather than primary tissues, primarily due to the broader public availability of high-throughput datasets encompassing both histone modification profiles

and transcriptomic measurements for cultured lines. The five selected cell lines represent a spectrum of human tissue origins. Importantly, we observed a high degree of correlation in histone modification patterns across these cell lines, suggesting that tissue-specific effects may have only a limited influence on the results. Nevertheless, the availability of comprehensive epigenomic datasets from primary human tissues would substantially enhance the potential for future RetroSpect-based analyses.

In this work, the RetroSpect analytical framework was extended to the H3K4me1 histone mark in the context of RE-associated transcriptional regulation and its evolutionary implications. These results support the utility of RetroSpect for the analysis of diverse functional genomic elements. We anticipate that applying RetroSpect to additional regulatory features will contribute to a more comprehensive model of regulatory evolution in the human genome, and this hypothesis will be tested later in the next chapters.

3.4. RE-linked H3K4me3, H3K9ac, H3K27ac, H3K27me3 and H3K9me3 analysis in five human cell lines

3.4.1. Overview of the new histone modifications added to the analysis

In the previous analysis, functional genomic features beyond human TFBS and the single enhancer chromatin mark H3K4me1 have not been systematically analyzed using the RetroSpect methodological framework. In the current analysis, we extended the application of the RetroSpect pipeline to encompass additional key regulatory marks, epigenetic histone modifications. We focused on five principal histone marks involved in transcriptional regulation, encompassing both methylation and acetylation: H3K4me3, H3K9ac, H3K27ac, H3K27me3, and H3K9me3. Among these, H3K4me3 is strongly enriched at active promoter regions proximal to TSS and is widely recognized as a hallmark of transcriptional activation (Howe et al., 2017). Likewise, H3K9ac and H3K27ac are associated with actively transcribed chromatin and reflect permissive transcriptional states (Roth et al., 2001).

In contrast, H3K27me3 and H3K9me3 are characteristic of transcriptionally repressive chromatin, marking facultative and constitutive heterochromatin, respectively (Saksouk et al., 2015). Their presence typically correlates with silencing of nearby genomic regions. Taken together, these five histone modifications can be broadly categorized into two functional classes: those linked to transcriptional activation (H3K4me3, H3K9ac, and H3K27ac) and those associated with transcriptional repression (H3K27me3 and H3K9me3).

3.4.2. The initial data extraction and analysis

We retrieved datasets of histone modifications from the ENCODE project for five human cell lines, extracting a total of 200,889 H3K4me3, 593,717 H3K9ac, 373,112 H3K27ac, 302,267 H3K27me3, and 86,197 H3K9me3 chromatin tags. These tags were mapped within ± 5 kb of gene TSS. Of these, 28.0%, 20.0%, 22.4%, 20.3%, and 29.0%, respectively, overlapped with clearly annotated human RE sequences. The five analyzed cell lines included K562, GM12878, HepG2, MCF-7, and HeLa-S3, representing hematologic (K562 and GM12878), hepatic, mammary, and cervical origins, respectively.

To evaluate RE-associated regulatory contributions, we applied four previously developed scoring metrics - GRE, NGRE, PII, and NPII - originally designed for TFBS datasets (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019). While the mathematical definitions of the scores were preserved, their interpretations were adapted to quantify histone mark enrichment instead of transcription factor binding.

Subsequently, GRE, NGRE, PII, and NPII values were computed for each gene and pathway across all five cell lines. To obtain a general overview applicable across tissues, we averaged each score across all lines. The complete set of individual and averaged GRE, NGRE, PII, and NPII values is presented in Supplementary Table S2 in (Igolkina et al., 2019).

RE-linked histone marks accounted for relatively small fractions of total chromatin modification tags. Depending on the specific cell line, these proportions ranged between 21–31% for H3K4me3, 13–29% for H3K9ac, 14–33% for H3K27ac, 15–26% for H3K27me3, and 22–35% for H3K9me3 (Supplementary Table S3 in (Igolkina et al., 2019)). These findings contrast with earlier reports where RE-linked TFBS constituted the majority of binding site hits (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019).

The highest contribution to RE-linked histone mark content originated from SINE elements, accounting for 17–25% (H3K4me3), 10–24% (H3K9ac), 11–28% (H3K27ac), 8–14% (H3K27me3), and 7–14% (H3K9me3), depending on the cell line. Corresponding values for LINE elements were 9–14%, 5–13%, 6–16%, 6–13%, and 11–19%, respectively. For HERV retrotransposons, the respective proportions were 3–4%, 2–4%, 2–6%, 3–6%, and 7–13%. It is important to note that the sum of hits across individual RE classes may exceed the total number of RE-overlapping histone tags, as individual tags can intersect multiple REs simultaneously (Roth et al., 2001; Saksouk et al., 2015).

Previously, Estecio et al. reported that the presence of B1 SINE elements in rodent gene promoters was associated with repressive histone modifications (Estécio et al., 2012). In contrast, our analysis did not reveal a similar association between promoter-proximal SINEs and either H3K27me3 or H3K9me3 in human genes.

3.4.3. Correlation among histone tag profiles based on GRE/NGRE and PII/NPII scores

We began by assessing the variability of histone mark profiles across different cell lines. To do this, we extracted 25 individual profiles from the ENCODE dataset - corresponding to five histone modifications across five human cell lines - and computed pairwise correlation coefficients between all profile combinations. These correlation values were then organized into a symmetric matrix and subjected to biclustering analysis (Figure 46).

The results indicated that, for each specific histone modification, the profiles were consistently similar across all examined cell lines. This high degree of correlation suggests that the influence of cell line (i.e., tissue origin) on the distribution of histone marks is limited. Given this consistency, we proceeded with the analysis using GRE, NGRE, PII, and NPII scores averaged across the five cell lines, thereby capturing a more generalized pattern of regulatory influence independent of specific tissue context.

Figure 46. Correlation matrix of GRE scores calculated by five histone modification profiles (H3K4me3, H3K9ac, H3K27ac, H3K27me3, and H3K9me3) across five human cell lines (K562, GM12878, HepG2, MCF-7, and HeLa-s3).

Furthermore, we identified two distinct clusters of histone modifications based on the similarity of their gene distribution profiles (Figure 46). The first cluster comprised promoter-associated and active chromatin marks (H3K4me3, H3K9ac, H3K27ac), while the second cluster included repressive modifications characteristic of constitutive and facultative heterochromatin (H3K9me3 and H3K27me3, respectively). Notably, clustering within the active chromatin group was primarily driven by cell line identity, followed by modification type, whereas the repressive chromatin group exhibited the opposite pattern - initial clustering occurred by modification, then by cell line.

The functional divergence between these two histone mark groups was further supported by their correlation with gene expression data obtained from the same cell lines (Figure 47). To perform this analysis, we retrieved RNA sequencing data from the ENCODE repository,

which included six expression profiles for GM12878, ten for HepG2, and twenty-two for K562. No RNA-seq datasets were available for MCF-7 and HeLa-s3 cell lines at the time of the analysis. Microarray data were excluded from the analysis, as RNA sequencing is currently considered the gold standard in transcriptomic research due to its superior accuracy and resolution (“A Comprehensive Assessment of RNA-Seq Accuracy, Reproducibility and Information Content by the Sequencing Quality Control Consortium,” 2014; Nault et al., 2015). As expected, active chromatin marks showed a positive correlation with gene expression levels, whereas repressive histone marks displayed negative correlations with transcriptional activity (Figure 47). These observations support the expected functional roles of the respective histone modifications as annotated in the ENCODE dataset.

Figure 47. Correlation analysis between histone modification profiles and RNA sequencing-based gene expression data retrieved from the ENCODE repository at the level of individual genes.

We subsequently examined the GRE, NGRE, PII, and NPII scores associated with each histone modification. By generating pairwise scatterplots for all histone mark combinations, we once again identified two distinct clusters characterized by strong internal correlations (Figure 48). As observed previously, the histone modifications segregated into two major categories: active/open chromatin-associated marks (H3K4me3, H3K9ac, H3K27ac) and repressive marks linked to constitutive or facultative heterochromatin (H3K9me3, H3K27me3).

Figure 48. Scatterplot matrices illustrating (A) normalized gene-level RE-linked enrichment scores (NGRE) and (B) normalized pathway involvement indices (NPII) across five histone modifications, aggregated from 5 human cell lines. Each point corresponds to an individual gene, averaged across the five cell lines. Pearson correlation coefficients (denoted as c) are displayed within each panel, with all correlations reaching statistical significance (p -value < 0.001). Green boxes indicate pairs of histone marks exhibiting strong correlations ($c > 0.75$).

3.4.4. Genes and molecular pathways with enrichment or deficiency in RE-linked regulation

To identify genes and molecular pathways whose regulation is either enriched or deficient in RE-linked histone modifications (referred to as RE-enriched or RE-deficient), we analyzed the relationships between GRE/NGRE and PII/NPII scores. Specifically, scatterplots were constructed for 25,075 human genes and 3,121 molecular pathways, where the x-axis represented either GRE (for genes) or PII (for pathways), and the y-axis represented NGRE (for genes) or NPII (for pathways). These scatterplots allowed us to distinguish genes and

pathways under strong or weak influence of RE-linked regulatory elements (Figure 49). We fitted a one-parameter linear regression model to each scatterplot and calculated the Euclidean distance of each point from the regression line. Genes or pathways that fell within the top 5% or bottom 5% of distances from the trend line were categorized as RE-deficient or RE-enriched, respectively.

Figure 49. Scatterplots showing the relationships between NGRE and GRE scores (top panels) and between NPPI and PPI scores (bottom panels) for five histone modifications, aggregated across five human cell lines. Each point corresponds to an individual gene or molecular pathway. Red and green data points indicate genes or pathways identified as enriched or deficient, respectively, in RE-associated epigenetic regulation.

3.4.4.1. GO annotation of top RE-enriched and RE-deficient genes

To functionally characterize the gene sets enriched or deficient in RE-linked regulation, we conducted GO analysis using the DAVID platform for ten gene groups (top and bottom 5% of genes across five human histone modifications). This analysis yielded EASE enrichment p-values (Hosack et al., 2003) for 826 GO direct terms. Next, we classified these terms into sixteen broader functional categories, following the grouping strategy previously introduced in our earlier study (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019). For each functional category, the corresponding p-values were combined using Fisher’s method to produce aggregated enrichment values. The resulting enrichment landscape across all functional categories is visualized as a heatmap in Figure 50.

Figure 50. Heatmap of aggregated p-values indicating association of functional categories with up- or downregulation by RE-linked regulatory marks across histone modifications. "Up" and "Down" refer to enrichment and deficiency of RE-linked regulation, respectively, for each functional category and histone tag.

The two previously defined classes of histone modifications - those associated with active and inactive chromatin - exhibited clearly distinguishable patterns across the functional annotation data. Analysis of p-values revealed consistent enrichment trends within each group. Specifically, in the group of histone marks associated with transcriptionally active chromatin, the categories “Lipid metabolism”, “Electron transfer chain reactions”, and “Catabolism of xenobiotics” were enriched for RE-upregulated genes (i.e., genes with

elevated RE-linked regulatory signals). In contrast, categories such as “Cytoskeleton organization and cell adhesion-related pathways”, “DNA metabolism and chromatin structure-related processes”, “Nucleic base metabolism”, “Translation and protein maturation” and “RNA synthesis” were predominantly RE-downregulated (i.e., enriched for genes with deficient RE-linked regulation). The categories “Mitochondria-related pathways” and “Infection” displayed mixed trends, while six additional categories did not show statistically significant up- or downregulation.

Within the group of histone modifications associated with transcriptionally inactive chromatin, we observed RE-enrichment for the following categories: “RNA synthesis”, “Translation and protein maturation”, “Nucleic base metabolism”, “Intracellular signaling”, “Mitochondria-related pathways”, “Electron transfer chain reactions”, “DNA metabolism and chromatin structure”, “Cell cycle regulation and apoptosis”, and “Amino acid and polyamine metabolism”. The remaining categories either showed ambiguous trends or lacked significant enrichment or deficiency (Figure 50).

Notably, we also observed an apparent anti-correlated pattern of enrichment between the two histone mark groups (Figure 50, Table 17). For instance, categories such as “Infection”, “DNA metabolism and chromatin structure”, “Translation and protein maturation”, “Nucleic base metabolism”, “Mitochondria-related pathways” and “RNA synthesis” were RE-enriched in the inactive chromatin group but simultaneously RE-deficient in the active chromatin group. Conversely, categories such as “Electron transfer chain reactions”, “Infection”, “Catabolism of xenobiotics” and “Cytoskeleton organization and cell adhesion” exhibited RE enrichment in both histone modification groups.

Table 17. Interpretation of regulatory evolution pattern of molecular processes by their active and inactive chromatin RE-enrichment status.

Enrichment and chromatin status	Enriched by active chromatin RE-associated marks	Deficient by active chromatin RE-associated marks
Enriched by inactive chromatin RE-	Recently integrated RE insertions often result in transcriptional disruption; however, the elevated rate	Conserved core molecular processes exhibit slow regulatory evolution and

associated marks	of regulatory evolution facilitates the rapid co-option of those insertions that confer a selective advantage. This dynamic may reflect the presence of intense evolutionary arms race processes acting over recent evolutionary timescales.	remain largely resistant to evolutionary arms race dynamics or other runaway evolutionary scenarios. These processes are subject to strong purifying selection and experience limited positive selection.
Deficient by inactive chromatin RE-associated marks	This group of molecular processes experienced substantial RE insertional activity in a relatively distant evolutionary past. Over time, many of these insertions were co-opted into host regulatory networks. The group appears to have been markedly influenced by evolutionary arms races or other episodes of accelerated regulatory evolution.	These molecular processes exhibit an absence of both RE-associated activating and repressive chromatin marks, likely due to either the mutational decay of previously inserted RE or a general paucity of such insertion events. They represent genomic regions that can be considered deserts of regulatory evolution.

3.4.4.2. Top RE-enriched and RE-deficient molecular pathways

Molecular pathways identified as RE-enriched or RE-deficient were further grouped into the same sixteen functional categories for each type of histone modification assessed. As with the gene-based analysis, the two histone modification groups displayed distinct and characteristic patterns of enrichment (Figure 51).

Figure 51. Heatmap of EASE scores (modified Fisher exact p-values) indicating the association of each functional category with RE-linked upregulation or downregulation across five investigated histone modifications. "Up" and "down" denote enrichment and deficiency, respectively.

Nonetheless, five functional categories exhibited consistent enrichment patterns across both histone modification groups: “carbohydrate metabolism”, “electron transfer chain reactions”, “xenobiotic catabolism”, “cell cycle regulation and apoptosis” and “cytoskeleton organization and cell adhesion”. In contrast, six categories demonstrated opposing regulatory trends between the two groups: “sensory perception and neurotransmission”, “RNA synthesis”, “translation and protein maturation”, “lipid metabolism”, “immune-

related pathways” and “DNA metabolism and chromatin structure”. The remaining five categories displayed unclear or inconsistent patterns of enrichment across the two chromatin mark groups (Figure 51).

3.4.4.3. Integrated analysis of gene-level and pathway-level RE-enrichment patterns

For most of the functional categories analyzed, gene-based and pathway-based pipelines produced congruent enrichment profiles. To unify these two analytical approaches - gene-level GRE/NGRE metrics and pathway-level PII/NPII scores - we employed Fisher’s method to combine the p-values obtained from gene and pathway enrichment analyses (Figure 50 and Figure 51) and visualized the aggregated significance levels accordingly (Figure 52). Due to the multi-layered nature of the statistical workflow, a strict significance threshold was not applied. Instead, we focused on identifying overarching trends across the two major histone modification groups. As in previous observations, these two groups consistently exhibited distinct and diverging RE-associated regulatory profiles.

Figure 52. Heatmap illustrating the results of the integrated analysis of RE-associated enrichment and deficiency across the two histone modification groups. "Up" and "Down" indicate functional category enrichment or deficiency, respectively. Each cell corresponds to an individual aggregated p-value.

We identified two out of sixteen molecular categories that were enriched for RE-associated regulation within the first group of histone modifications linked to active/open chromatin, while remaining unaffected in the second group related to condensed/inactive chromatin. These categories were “lipid metabolism” and “carbohydrates metabolism”. The

“cytoskeleton organization and cell adhesion” category exhibited enrichment in the active chromatin group but displayed a divergent trend in the inactive group.

Three categories - “electron transfer chain reactions”, “catabolism of xenobiotics” and “amino acids and polyamines metabolism” - were consistently enriched across both histone groups. In contrast, “perception and neurotransmission” and “immunity linked pathways” were enriched in the active chromatin group but showed RE deficiency in the inactive chromatin group. Conversely, “RNA synthesis”, “translation and protein maturation”, “DNA metabolism and chromatin structure” and “cell cycle regulation and apoptosis” were deficient in the active group yet enriched in the inactive group.

Two categories - “infection” and “intracellular signaling” - displayed neutral trends in the first group but enrichment in the second. The “mitochondria-linked pathways” category was oppositely regulated: deficient in the first group and enriched in the second. Finally, the “nucleic base metabolism” category exhibited no clear or consistent trends across either group.

In summary, we observed three categories with consistent enrichment and six ones with opposing enrichment/deficiency patterns between the two histone modification groups. These findings underscore the distinct regulatory dynamics of REs associated with active versus inactive chromatin states that correspond to different modes of regulatory evolution of human molecular processes (Table 17). Notably, while three categories showed enrichment across both groups, no category exhibited consistent deficiency in both. These observations align with our previous TFBS-based analysis, reinforcing that the sixteen functional categories considered here are subject to substantial regulation by REs (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019; Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019), albeit with four possible distinct modes of regulation and evolutionary trajectories (Table 17).

3.4.5. Discussion of the major RE-linked chromatin modification trends obtained from the 5 modifications in 5 cell lines analysis

In the current analysis, we investigated genome-wide features of gene regulation mediated by multiple RE-linked histone modifications. Epigenetic control of gene expression is widely recognized as a major mechanism for repressing transposable elements (Hurst & Magiorkinis, 2017; P. Yang et al., 2017). However, here we aimed to systematically analyze the reciprocal influence of transposable elements on the functionality and evolutionary dynamics of human epigenetic regulatory systems. Prior research has established that transposable elements contribute significantly to the evolution of epigenetic regulatory networks. For instance, studies on human gene duplication have revealed that the presence of transposable elements plays a critical role in shaping the epigenetic regulatory landscape (Lannes et al., 2019).

As in previous analyses, our focus was on quantifying gene regulation features associated with RE-linked histone modifications. Although DNA transposons represent a minor fraction of the human genome - approximately 3% - and are believed to have been largely inactive since the early stages of mammalian evolution (Lander et al., 2001; Mills et al., 2007), they can still influence gene expression regulation. Notably, thousands of copies of the HsMar1 element's terminal inverted repeats are present in the human genome, where they affect nearby gene expression via epigenetic mechanisms (Jursch et al., 2013; Palazzo et al., 2019; Renault et al., 2019). Some of these elements also contain functional silencers capable of modulating the transcription of adjacent genes (Bire et al., 2016). Despite these roles, DNA transposons have limited analytical utility in the RetroSpect pipeline when applied to the human genome due to their relatively low abundance and sparse distribution near gene TSS, making quantitative assessment of their regulatory impact challenging. Consequently, our analysis centered on REs, which are more prevalent and tend to represent more recent insertional events. However, in non-mammalian species - where DNA transposons may still be active and more abundant - these elements could become informative markers within the RetroSpect framework.

We utilized publicly available data from the ENCODE project, incorporating chromatin immunoprecipitation data for five human cell lines. In total, we examined 1,556,182 histone modification tags corresponding to five histone marks representative of open/active chromatin (H3K4me3, H3K9ac, H3K27ac) and condensed/inactive chromatin (H3K27me3, H3K9me3). Gene-level characteristics derived from these tags were then aggregated into quantitative scores representing regulatory enrichment at the level of molecular pathways, which allowed for the identification of genes and pathways enriched or deficient in RE-linked histone regulatory signals.

We relied on cell line data, rather than normal human tissues, due to the broader availability of high-throughput histone modification and RNA-seq datasets for the former at the time of analysis. The selected cell lines represent diverse tissue origins. Notably, the histone modification profiles were highly correlated across the five cell lines, suggesting only a limited contribution of tissue-specific effects. Nonetheless, the availability of high-resolution epigenetic data for normal tissues would enhance future applications of the RetroSpect pipeline.

Each histone mark was associated with two gene sets - RE-enriched and RE-deficient - which we functionally annotated using GO direct terms. We implemented a semi-automated annotation approach and mapped 826 GO terms into sixteen broader functional categories as defined in previous studies (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019; Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019). This same annotation framework was applied to pathway-level analyses, encompassing 3,121 molecular pathways.

The results enabled us to assess RE enrichment or deficiency across the sixteen functional categories previously shown to be subject to substantial RE regulation based on TFBS data (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019). Interestingly, the two distinct groups of histone modifications (active versus inactive chromatin) exhibited contrasting RE enrichment patterns across these categories. This finding supports earlier evidence of coordinated behavior among histone modifications associated with gene expression variability (Ha et al., 2011), and further

implies that RE-linked histone modifications cluster into functionally coherent groups based on chromatin state.

The first group - comprising H3K4me3, H3K9ac, and H3K27ac - displayed RE patterns largely consistent with prior TFBS-based analyses. Specifically, these histone marks were enriched in categories such as “amino acids and polyamines metabolism”, “lipid metabolism”, “catabolism of xenobiotics”, “sensory perception and neurotransmission” and “immunity-linked pathways.” Conversely, they showed RE deficiency in categories including “DNA metabolism and chromatin structure”, “nucleic base metabolism” and “translation and protein maturation.”

The second group - repressive marks H3K27me3 and H3K9me3 - exhibited RE trends that diverged more substantially from previous TFBS-based results. This observation suggests that histone marks with similar regulatory roles (activation or repression) may evolve in a coordinated fashion, while marks with opposing functionalities likely reflect divergent evolutionary pressures across functional categories. Despite these differences, three categories - “electron transfer chain reactions”, “catabolism of xenobiotics” and “amino acids and polyamines metabolism” - were enriched for REs in both histone groups and were similarly identified in earlier TFBS-focused studies (Nikitin et al., 2018; Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019).

Overall, our results indicate that histone modifications introduce a more nuanced layer of RE-mediated gene regulation compared to TFBS alone. This complexity highlights the need for further investigation into the full spectrum of functional genomic features shaped by RE insertions, as well as direct comparative analyses, to better understand the evolutionary role of REs in shaping the regulatory architecture of the human genome.

3.5. Joint analysis of RE-linked H3K4me1, H3K4me3, H3K9ac, H3K27ac, H3K27me3 and H3K9me3 analysis in five human cell lines

3.5.1. Overview of the analysis

Although considerable advances have been made in the described analysis, the field of RE-linked chromatin regulation remained largely underexplored. Chromatin modifications function within a complex and dynamic regulatory system involving readers, writers, and erasers that collectively orchestrate gene expression programs (Ueberheide et al., 2024). In previous studies, we quantified the RE-associated regulatory impact at the gene level for several key chromatin marks:

- **H3K4me1** – associated with active enhancers (Rada-Iglesias, 2018)
- **H3K27ac** – also linked to active enhancers (Creyghton et al., 2010)
- **H3K4me3** – a promoter-specific mark (Liang et al., 2004)
- **H3K9ac** – another promoter-associated modification (Karmodiya et al., 2012)
- **H3K27me3** – indicative of Polycomb-mediated repression (Ku et al., 2008)
- **H3K9me3** – characteristic of constitutive heterochromatin (Nicetto et al., 2019)

In the present analysis, we conducted a joined analysis of RE-linked chromatin marks representing active promoters, enhancers, and heterochromatic regions. This was based on the principle that RE insertions can lead to both activation and repression of nearby genes, depending on the chromatin context. Importantly, such dual regulatory potential is relevant in human pathology - for instance, in disorders like X-linked dystonia parkinsonism, where RE-induced heterochromatinization plays a functional role (Horváth et al., 2024).

By applying a comprehensive intersectional approach through the RetroSpect analytical framework, we were able to uncover more robust and biologically meaningful functional signatures of RE activity across six distinct chromatin modifications (Nikitin, 2025). This joint evaluation provides an expanded view of the diverse regulatory consequences of RE insertions within the human genome.

3.5.2. Dimensionality reduction and key data characteristics

To assess the extent of variation attributable to cell type and chromatin modification in the dataset comprising NGRE and GRE scores across six chromatin marks and five distinct cell lines, we applied PCA employing a centroid-based approximation method (Figure 53).

Figure 53. Principal component analysis of GRE and NGRE scores.

- (A) PCA of GRE values, color-coded by cell line.
- (B) PCA of GRE values, color-coded by histone modification.
- (C) PCA of NGRE values, color-coded by cell line.
- (D) PCA of NGRE values, color-coded by histone modification.

Centroid approximations are depicted for each group, accompanied by 95% confidence intervals. Consistent color palettes were applied to cell lines in panels A and C, and to chromatin modifications in panels B and D to facilitate visual comparison.

The projections of different cell lines with the same histone modifications showed substantial overlap (Figure 53B, 53D). Within this shared structure, heterochromatin-associated marks exhibit distinct, more compact clustering patterns compared to those associated with active chromatin, for both GRE (Figure 53B) and NGRE scores (Figure 53D), which is in contrast with the earlier findings about RE-linked tissue specific chromatin modifications (Ali & Liang, 2024) but closely resembles the clustering in the

previous 5 chromatin modifications analysis by RetroSpect methodology (Igolkina et al., 2019). Notably, H3K4me1 - an active enhancer-associated modification - forms a separate cluster in both datasets, while H3K27ac, another enhancer-related mark, displays the greatest degree of cell line-specific divergence.

In contrast, the separation of cell lines themselves is relatively modest, despite their origin from diverse tissues and organs (Figure 53A, 53C). This observation highlights the dominant role of chromatin mark-specific variation over cell type-specific differences in shaping the structure of the dataset.

3.5.3. Identification of RE-Enriched and RE-Deficient Genes

Following the RetroSpect methodology (Nikitin, Sorokin, et al., 2019), we computed correlations between NGRE scores and gene expression to identify RE-enriched and RE-deficient genes for each of the five cell lines across all six chromatin modifications (Figure 54).

Figure 54. Correlation patterns between NGRE and GRE scores across cell lines and chromatin modifications. Each panel displays the relationship between NGRE (y-axis) and GRE (x-axis) scores for a specific combination of cell line and chromatin modification. Cell lines are arranged by rows, with labels on the left margin, while chromatin modifications are organized by columns and labeled along the bottom of the grid. A linear regression line was fitted to each plot using the least squares method. Genes falling within the top 10% of residuals above the regression line - indicating relative RE enrichment - are highlighted in green. Genes in the bottom 10% - indicating RE deficiency - are shown in red. The remaining 80% of genes are represented in blue.

Among the 30 possible combinations of cell lines and chromatin modifications, five exhibited negative correlations between NGRE and GRE scores. These cases correspond to divergent linear trends observed for H3K27ac, H3K4me3, and H3K9ac in HeLa-S3, and for H3K4me3 and H3K9ac in MCF-7. Notably, the two heterochromatin-associated modifications - H3K27me3 and H3K9me3 - as well as the enhancer-associated mark H3K4me1, did not display negative correlations, consistent with previously reported patterns. (Igolkina et al., 2019).

A key distinction of the current methodology lies in the extraction of RE-enriched and RE-deficient gene sets specific to each individual cell line and chromatin modification. This contrasts with earlier approaches, in which GRE scores were averaged across multiple cell lines and epigenomic features, such as transcription factor binding profiles (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019). At this stage, the biological relevance of the identified RE-enriched and RE-deficient genes remains uncertain; therefore, further analyses involving data intersection and GO enrichment were conducted, as described in the following sections.

3.5.4. Intersection analysis of RE-enriched and RE-deficient genes across cell lines and histone modifications

To investigate the influence of REs on human gene regulation in the context of various histone modifications and across distinct cellular backgrounds, we performed intersection analyses of RE-enriched and RE-deficient gene sets across different chromatin marks. This procedure was independently applied within each of the five cell lines (Figure 55), allowing us to assess the extent of overlap and specificity in RE-associated regulatory patterns.

A

Figure 55. Supervenn plots illustrating intersections of RE-enriched and RE-deficient genes across histone modifications and cell lines. Panels A–E correspond to individual cell lines: GM12878 (A), HeLa-S3 (B), HepG2 (C), K562 (D), and MCF-7 (E). Each row within a panel represents a specific histone modification, displaying intersections between RE-enriched gene sets (denoted as ‘top’) and RE-deficient gene sets (denoted as ‘bottom’). Distinct colors are used to represent individual gene sets, while grey rectangles indicate shared genes (i.e., successful intersections). White and light grey rectangles denote the absence of overlap. Intersection groups containing more than 500 genes are annotated with their corresponding gene counts at the bottom of each panel.

The intersection analysis revealed that the interplay between RE-associated active and repressive chromatin modifications varies considerably across cell lines. For instance, in K562 cells (Figure 55D), a prominent cluster comprising 1,161 genes is enriched for active

promoter and enhancer marks (H3K27ac, H3K4me3, H3K9ac) while lacking any repressive (heterochromatic) modifications. This pattern suggests a set of genes under active regulation by REs.

In contrast, MCF-7 cells (Figure 55E) exhibit a much smaller cluster of such genes (<500) and instead display a notable group of 692 genes marked both by active (H3K27ac, H3K4me3, H3K9ac) and repressive histone modifications, indicating a more complex or ambiguous regulatory relationship between REs and host gene expression. A similar dual-pattern cluster is observed in HepG2 cells (716 genes, Figure 55C).

In GM12878 (Figure 3A) and HeLa-S3 (Figure 3B), both regulatory patterns are evident: one cluster enriched solely with active marks and another enriched with both active and repressive marks (notably H3K9me3 in GM12878 and H3K27me3 in HeLa-S3). These differences may reflect varying intensities of RE-mediated evolutionary pressure across tissue types. Previous studies have identified tissues such as placenta (M. Yu et al., 2023) and neocortex (Garza et al., 2023) as being particularly affected by RE activity, with extensive RE integration contributing to their rapid evolution in the human lineage.

3.5.5. Identification of promoter- and enhancer-level RE-enriched genes across cell lines

Using GRE and NGRE data across five cell lines and six histone modifications, we generated 12 distinct sets of RE-enriched and RE-deficient genes for each cell line. To identify genes enriched for REs specifically at promoters and enhancers, we applied the following criteria for each cell line:

- **Enhancer-associated RE-enriched genes** were defined as the intersection of RE-enriched genes marked by H3K4me1 and H3K27ac. Genes that were also RE-enriched for repressive marks (H3K9me3 and H3K27me3) were excluded from this set.
- **Promoter-associated RE-enriched genes** were defined as the intersection of RE-enriched genes marked by H3K4me3 and H3K9ac, similarly excluding those also enriched with repressive histone marks.

This approach yielded a variable number of promoter- and enhancer-specific RE-enriched genes for each cell line. We then performed cross-cell line intersection analyses to determine the extent of cell line specificity in RE-mediated gene regulation and to assess the divergence of regulatory networks across cell types (Figure 56).

Figure 56. Supervenn plot depicting intersections of enhancer- and promoter-specific RE-enriched genes across five cell lines. This figure illustrates the overlap of RE-enriched genes associated with enhancer regions (*enhancers_top*) and promoter regions (*promoter_top*) across the five cell lines analyzed in this study. Each colored segment represents a distinct gene set, while grey-shaded rectangles indicate shared genes between sets (i.e., intersections). White and light grey rectangles denote the absence of overlap. Gene counts for individual sets are shown along the right-hand side of the plot. Intersection groups containing more than 100 genes are annotated with their respective gene counts at the bottom of the panel. The numbers displayed at the top indicate how many gene sets contribute to each intersection group (only shown for intersections involving more than 100 genes).

The intersection patterns presented in Figure 56 highlight the extent of overlap in RE-enriched gene regulation at promoter and enhancer regions across the five cell lines studied. A total of 92 promoter-associated RE-enriched genes were found to be common to all five cell lines, despite the individual sets ranging from 548 to 1,745 genes per cell line. In contrast, only three enhancer-associated RE-enriched genes were shared across all cell lines, with individual enhancer-associated sets ranging from 194 to 566 genes.

This marked difference likely reflects the higher variability of enhancer-linked histone modifications, such as H3K4me1 and H3K27ac (see Figure 55), and is consistent with previous findings that promoter-associated transcriptional regulation is generally more conserved across tissues than enhancer-mediated regulation (Razin & Ulianov, 2020).

Additionally, within each cell line, the overlap between promoter- and enhancer-specific RE-enriched gene sets was minimal. This observation suggests that distinct subsets of REs - possibly corresponding to different RE families - may preferentially influence gene regulation at either the promoter or enhancer level. Further integrative analyses and experimental validation will be necessary to clarify the mechanistic basis of this divergence.

3.5.6. Functional annotation of consensus promoter- and enhancer-level RE-enriched genes

The consolidated sets of RE-enriched genes at promoter and enhancer regions, shared across multiple cell lines, are presented in Table 18 below.

Table 18. Consensus set of RE-enriched genes at promoter and enhancer regions. This table presents the list of genes consistently identified as RE-enriched at promoter or enhancer regions across all five cell lines examined in this analysis.

Promoter RE-enriched genes									
<i>MRPL23</i>	<i>ASMT</i>	<i>MYC</i>	<i>ELMO3</i>	<i>ZBTB46</i>	<i>EPC2</i>	<i>SMIM15</i>	<i>SNORD91A</i>	<i>EIF1B</i>	<i>MRPL43</i>
<i>TMEM50A</i>	<i>TMEM60</i>	<i>PLD6</i>	<i>SMIM15-AS1</i>	<i>KLLN</i>	<i>GADD45A</i>	<i>RNF214</i>	<i>MIR4795</i>	<i>RNF5P1</i>	<i>TRAPPC1</i>
<i>CRYZL1</i>	<i>ACD</i>	<i>MTMR11</i>	<i>RPL7</i>	<i>IP6K1</i>	<i>POLB</i>	<i>DNASE1L1</i>	<i>MYNN</i>	<i>CHD7</i>	
<i>ATP1B1</i>	<i>HMGB1</i>	<i>LAMB2</i>	<i>RAP2A</i>	<i>PSMA7</i>	<i>TTC30B</i>	<i>C5orf34</i>	<i>LZTS2</i>	<i>CNPPD1</i>	
<i>CTRL</i>	<i>CHMP2B</i>	<i>VAPA</i>	<i>MIR5587</i>	<i>AKAP17A</i>	<i>WASHC2C</i>	<i>USF2</i>	<i>KDM6A</i>	<i>RDH10</i>	
<i>WASHC2A</i>	<i>ZBTB7B</i>	<i>PTEN</i>	<i>ATP11B</i>	<i>ANKIB1</i>	<i>CHUK</i>	<i>PKP4</i>	<i>SLC25A5-AS1</i>	<i>OGT</i>	
<i>JADE1</i>	<i>RNF5</i>	<i>PET100</i>	<i>MIR6833</i>	<i>ARF1</i>	<i>TAPT1-AS1</i>	<i>MIR548H4</i>	<i>TXNDC17</i>	<i>ATR</i>	
<i>NAA38</i>	<i>ETV3</i>	<i>C3orf58</i>	<i>CGGBP1</i>	<i>HYAL3</i>	<i>SLC25A5</i>	<i>ATP13A1</i>	<i>ERBIN</i>	<i>CNIH3</i>	
<i>HECTD2</i>	<i>CTC1</i>	<i>CDK5</i>	<i>ST3GAL3</i>	<i>TTC21A</i>	<i>EIF4A1</i>	<i>CDKN2C</i>	<i>MIR1282</i>	<i>HNRNPD</i>	
<i>CAPN15</i>	<i>MLF2</i>	<i>CPEB2</i>	<i>HNRNPA0</i>	<i>PTMS</i>	<i>LENG9</i>	<i>MCUB</i>	<i>CASC11</i>	<i>SNORD131</i>	

Enhancer RE-enriched genes									
<i>MIR4674</i>	<i>NALTI</i>	<i>LINC01132</i>							

To explore the functional roles of the identified promoter-associated RE-enriched genes, we conducted GO (G. O. Consortium et al., 2023) enrichment analysis using the ShinyGO platform (Ge et al., 2020), applying no background gene set. Enriched biological processes were filtered based on a False discovery rate (FDR) threshold of 0.1 (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995) to ensure statistical significance. The resulting enriched GO terms for the consensus promoter-level RE-enriched genes are summarized in Table 19.

Table 19. Enriched biological processes for promoter-associated RE-enriched genes. This table lists the GO biological processes significantly enriched among the promoter-level RE-enriched genes identified across all five cell lines.

Enrichment FDR-corrected p-value	Number of genes from RE-enriched promoters in the process	Number of genes in the process	Fold Enrichment	The process with the GO knowledgebase hyperlink
0.02	4	92	12.6	Small cell lung cancer
0.064	3	76	11.4	Chronic myeloid leukemia
0.044	4	126	9.2	Cell cycle
0.016	6	222	7.8	Human T-cell leukemia virus 1 infection
0.064	4	156	7.4	Cellular senescence

GO analysis (Table 19) revealed that promoter-level RE-enriched genes are significantly associated with transcriptional activation of pathways involved in two major cancer types - small cell lung cancer and chronic myeloid leukemia - as well as genes upregulated during infection by human T-cell leukemia virus type 1 (HTLV-1), a retrovirus that, like HIV, targets CD4⁺ T lymphocytes (Hirons et al., 2021). These findings suggest that RE-mediated gene regulation and evolutionary selection may act, at least partially, by co-opting pre-existing host defense mechanisms - a phenomenon previously observed in the context of placental evolution (Imakawa et al., 2022).

Additional enriched biological processes included regulation of the cell cycle and cellular senescence, both of which are recognized as fundamental hallmarks of cancer (Hanahan, 2022). These results further support the hypothesis that promoter linked RE activity contributes to oncogenic regulatory programs. In contrast, no statistically significant functional enrichment was identified among the three enhancer-associated RE-enriched genes (MIR4674, NALT1, and LINC01132), two of which are non-coding RNAs.

3.5.7. Overview of the results of joint analysis of six chromatin modifications in five human cell lines

In this analysis (Nikitin, 2025), we investigated the regulatory impact of REs on human gene expression by analyzing ChIP-seq profiles of promoter-, enhancer-, and heterochromatin-associated histone modifications across five human cell lines. Clustering and intersection analyses revealed a pronounced degree of cell type specificity in RE-associated regulatory activity at enhancer regions, underscoring the potential for REs to contribute to tissue-specific regulatory evolution. In contrast, promoter-level RE-mediated regulation appeared more conserved across different cellular contexts.

Importantly, functional enrichment analysis showed that promoter-associated RE-enriched genes are involved in pathways related to oncogenesis, including cell cycle control and cellular senescence, and are also implicated in host antiviral responses, particularly to HTLV-1. These findings point to a dual role for REs in both evolutionary innovation and disease-related gene regulation. Collectively, this work advances our understanding of how REs have shaped the human regulatory genome, with implications for both evolutionary biology and cancer research.

3.6. Comparison of the main results gained from the RE-linked TFBS and chromatin modifications analysis with the available public evidence

The research program outlined in the preceding chapters was designed to capture the complex, multimodal, and multidimensional landscape of RE-associated regulatory influence, focusing on TFBS and six key epigenetic modifications across a variable number of human cell lines. Specifically, analyses were performed on the K562 cell line in (Nikitin et al., 2018), an expanded set of 13 cell lines in (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019), and five cell lines in the three most recent investigations (Igolkina et al., 2019; Nikitin, 2025; Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019).

Observed patterns of RE enrichment and deficiency varied across regulatory modalities (TFBS vs. histone modifications), evolutionary age categories, and methodological frameworks - including GRE/NGRE correlation analysis (Nikitin et al., 2018), the original RetroSpect approach (Igolkina et al., 2019; Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019; Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019; Nikitin, Sorokin, et al., 2019), and post-RetroSpect intersection analysis (Nikitin, 2025). In this concluding section, we integrate and compare these findings to identify overarching trends and consensus mechanisms underlying the evolution of RE-driven regulatory networks in the human genome.

Table 20. Comparative summary of RE-enriched and RE-deficient molecular processes and key findings across five independent analyses of RE-associated regulatory activity in the human genome. This table synthesizes core results from five analyses, highlighting shared and distinct biological processes, regulatory features, and methodological insights into the role of REs in shaping gene regulation.

Study	RE-enriched molecular processes	RE-deficient molecular processes	Qualitative and other findings
(Nikitin et al., 2018)	Long-term evolutionary horizon: Response to pathogens, cytokine signaling, cell adhesion, Notch, Wnt, and integrin signaling, neuronal development and sensing, chondroitin sulfate and heparin metabolism, cAMP metabolism, endocytosis, IGF1R signaling. Short-term evolutionary	Transcription and processing of RNA, ribosome assembly and protein translation regulation, regulation of apoptosis, proteasomal degradation, steroid receptor signaling.	Within the more recent evolutionary timeframe, SINEs were approximately four times more active than LINEs and LTR elements, including HERV, in contributing functional TFBS. Notably, SINE-derived TFBS were disproportionately enriched in promoter-proximal regions relative to those associated with LINEs and HERVs.

	<p>horizon: cell cycle progression and apoptosis attenuation, PDGF, TGF beta, EGFR, and p38 signaling, histone deacetylation and DNA methylation interplay, structure of nuclear lumen, metabolism (primarily catabolism) of phospholipids and heterocyclic nitrogen-containing molecules, insulin and AMPK signaling, retrograde Golgi-ER transport, estrogen signaling, oocyte maturation.</p>		<p>Overall, 17% of TFBS located within promoter-proximal regions overlapped with REs.</p>
<p>(Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019)</p>	<p>Long-term evolutionary horizon: Posttranscriptional silencing by small RNAs, DNA repair, amino acids and lipids metabolism, detoxification of xenobiotics, sensory perception and neurotransmission, T- and NK-cellular immune response. Short-term evolutionary horizon: Lipid metabolism, detoxification and metabolism of xenobiotics.</p>	<p>Long-term evolutionary horizon: Nucleotide and DNA metabolism, chromatin structure, translation and ribosome biogenesis, intracellular signaling, intracellular antiviral response. Short-term evolutionary horizon: Translation and ribosome biogenesis, intracellular signaling pathways, viral processes, cell cycle, cytoskeleton, cell adhesion and migration.</p>	<p>microRNA and lncRNA genes are significantly overrepresented in gene sets enriched by RE-linked TFBS and underrepresented in the RE-deficient gene sets. GRE and NGRE joint distribution shows two linear clouds of points for all cell lines, these clouds correspond to RE-enriched and RE-deficient genes. The pattern observed was not found for molecular pathways. 72% of promoter proximal TFBS were overlapping with REs.</p>
<p>(Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019)</p>	<p>Long-term evolutionary horizon: Posttranscriptional silencing by small RNAs, DNA repair and chromatin structure, sensory perception and neurotransmission, lipid metabolism.</p>	<p>Long-term evolutionary horizon: Immune system, protein ubiquitination and degradation, cell adhesion, migration and interaction, metals metabolism and ion transport, cell death, general and hormone signaling pathways.</p>	<p>NGRE scores showed the highest correlation between cell lines (0.68 - 0.83) compared to GRE (0.53 - 0.74), PII (0.53 - 0.66) and NP II (0.44 - 0.69) scores. Similarly, there were two distinct diagonal clouds of points as in (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019). lincRNA and microRNA are overrepresented in RE-enriched genes, and lincRNA genes are underrepresented in RE-deficient genes.</p>

(Igol kina et al., 2019)	<p>Long-term evolutionary horizon, activating chromatin modifications: Perception and neurotransmission, lipid metabolism, immunity linked pathways, electron transfer chain, catabolism of xenobiotics, amino acids and polyamines metabolism.</p> <p>Long-term evolutionary horizon, repressing chromatin modifications: Infection processes, RNA synthesis, translation and protein maturation, nucleic base metabolism, mitochondria linked pathways, electron transfer chain, DNA metabolism and chromatin structure, cell cycle regulation and apoptosis.</p>	<p>Long-term evolutionary horizon, activating chromatin modifications: RNA synthesis, translation and protein maturation, nucleic base metabolism (with minor processes RE-enriched in activation chromatin modifications), mitochondria linked pathways (they are also enriched by H3K27ac), DNA metabolism and chromatin structure.</p> <p>Long-term evolutionary horizon, repressing chromatin modifications: Perception and neurotransmission, immunity linked pathways, cytoskeleton organization and cell adhesion.</p>	<p>RE-linked active and inactive chromatin tags form two distinct clusters of gene and pathway level regulation. 20-29% of histone modification peaks in the promoter proximal region were overlapping with RE coordinates. For repressive chromatin marks, the basal clustering was by chromatin modification and the low-level clustering was by cell line, the reverse being true for the active chromatin marks, indicating that they are more cell type specific.</p>
(Nikit in, 2025)	<p>Long-term evolutionary horizon, promoter chromatin modifications: small cell lung cancer, chronic myeloid leukemia, cell cycle, cellular senescence, HTLV1 infection</p>	<p>Not studied</p>	<p>H3K4me1 shows a separate clustering from other active and repressive chromatin modifications both by GRE and NGRE, whereas clustering by cell lines is less pronounced compared to the histone modifications clustering. Active chromatin modifications for some cell lines showed a negative linear trend between GRE and NGRE cell lines, suggesting higher cell type variability of RE-regulatory impact in active chromatin modifications. Promoter level RE impact (H3K4me3 and H3K9ac) is more consistent between cell lines than the enhancer one (H3K9me13 and H3K27me3)</p>

In the passages below we are discussing each molecular process evolution in context of the previously described analyses and the available public literature.

3.6.1. Response to pathogens / Infection / Immune processes

This category of biological processes was identified as enriched in RE-linked TFBS in the initial study of the K562 cell line (Nikitin et al., 2018), as well as in the broader analysis involving 13 cell lines (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019). Specifically, RE-enrichment was observed in pathways related to T and NK cells mediated immune responses. In contrast, processes associated with the intracellular antiviral response - particularly those involving TLRs - were found to be RE-deficient in the same analyses. Moreover, enhancer-associated REs, as defined by H3K4me1 enrichment, were generally depleted in immune-related functions (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019).

Interestingly, other promoter- and enhancer- associated histone modifications such as H3K4me3, H3K9ac, and H3K27ac revealed RE-enrichment in immune pathways, whereas repressive heterochromatin-associated marks (H3K9me3 and H3K27me3) consistently marked these same pathways as RE-deficient (Igolkina et al., 2019). Separately, infection processes were RE-enriched in heterochromatin modifications in the same study. Finally, HTLV1 infection was found among RE-enriched promoter regulated processes that were consistent between the cell lines analyzed in (Nikitin, 2025). These findings collectively point to a nuanced evolutionary trajectory of immune system regulation: while the intracellular antiviral response appears to be evolutionarily conserved and largely devoid of RE-linked regulatory elements, pathways governing T cell and NK cell responses show signs of more rapid regulatory evolution mediated by REs.

The literature on the evolution of the human immune system over the past 100 million years is extensive. With regard to intracellular antiviral defense, multiple lines of evidence suggest that modern humans inherited key immune adaptations - including variations in OAS (oligoadenylate synthetase), TLR1, TLR6, TLR10, and components of the HLA complex - from archaic hominins such as Neanderthals and Denisovans (Dannemann et al., 2016). These introgressed variants significantly impact innate immunity, particularly TLR-mediated responses, and are associated with altered susceptibility to immunological conditions such as allergies (D.-A. J & Mg, 2019; Patin & Quintana-Murci, 2025). Notably, these adaptations appear to involve protein-coding changes rather than alterations in regulatory regions, including those linked to REs.

Support for the protein-coding-centric evolution of antiviral immunity also comes from comparative genomic studies across 37 deuterostome taxa, which reveal that the vertebrate ancestor possessed a set of immune signaling components highly similar to modern mammalian TLR pathways. In many lineages, TLR genes underwent species-specific expansions that played a central role in shaping antiviral and innate immune responses (Tassia et al., 2017). These results suggest that the core architecture of antiviral immunity has evolved primarily through changes in coding sequences.

Conversely, regulatory divergence has played a more prominent role in other branches of the immune response. For example, interspecies comparisons have demonstrated that gene expression in antiviral pathways is highly divergent between humans and mice, with over 500 orthologous genes showing differential expression due to regulatory, rather than coding, differences (Schneor et al., 2025).

Recent immune system evolution within primates, especially in NK cell-mediated responses, is closely tied to the energetic costs of immune defense. Comparative transcriptomic analyses of humans, chimpanzees, macaques, and baboons have shown that apes exhibit stronger and less specific early innate immune responses compared to monkeys, engaging approximately 40% more genes at the transcriptional level (Hawash et al., 2021). At a broader taxonomic scale, structural and comparative analyses have identified significant lineage-specific expansions and deletions within NK cell receptor gene complexes. For instance, cattle, goats, and primates differ markedly in the content and organization of their NK gene clusters, with ruminants in particular evolving novel activating receptors. These expansions and contractions are believed to have occurred at the time of divergence of major mammalian clades (Carrillo-Bustamante et al., 2016; J. C. Schwartz et al., 2017).

Together, these observations suggest that the evolution of immune system regulation is highly modular. While intracellular antiviral responses have evolved largely through changes in protein-coding genes and are generally resistant to RE-mediated regulatory influence, other components - particularly those involved in adaptive and NK-mediated immunity - are more dynamically regulated by RE-linked elements. Integrating these findings with data on structural evolution of key immune gene families provides a more comprehensive view of how different parts of the immune system have evolved in response to both internal and external selective pressures and under the neutral mechanisms.

3.6.2. Cellular migration / adhesion / cell cycle / cell death / cytoskeleton

Cellular processes such as migration, adhesion, the cell cycle, programmed cell death, and cytoskeletal organization were consistently represented across studies investigating the regulatory impact of REs. In the original analysis of the K562 cell line (Nikitin et al., 2018), cell adhesion and endocytosis processes were found to be enriched in RE-linked regulatory activity on the long-term evolutionary horizon, while processes related to cell cycle progression, the attenuation of apoptosis and retrograde Golgi-ER transport showed RE enrichment on the short-term horizon. However, the broader study involving 13 cell lines (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019) identified processes such as cell cycle regulation, cytoskeleton organization, cell adhesion, and migration as RE-deficient on the short-term horizon.

It is important to note that short-term RetroSpect analyses may have lower resolution due to the relatively small number of evolutionarily young REs (those with sequence divergence <8%). Nevertheless, the discrepancy in findings between studies warrants further examination. Additional support for RE-deficiency in these processes comes from the H3K4me1 enhancer landscape analysis (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019), where cell adhesion, migration, interaction, and cell death were also found to be RE-deficient on the long-term horizon - corroborating the earlier TFBS-based findings.

Conversely, in the study analyzing five histone modifications (Igolkina et al., 2019), cell cycle and apoptosis pathways were found to be RE-enriched specifically in heterochromatin specific marks. However, within the same dataset, cytoskeleton organization and cell adhesion were RE-deficient in heterochromatin-associated modifications, and none of these processes showed consistent RE enrichment or depletion in association with activating histone marks (H3K4me3, H3K9ac, H3K27ac).

In the integrative consensus intersection study (Nikitin, 2025), RE-associated promoter-level chromatin modifications were found to consistently activate cell cycle-related pathways - and, unexpectedly, those associated with cellular senescence. As with immune processes, the regulatory evolution of these pathways appears multifaceted and, in some cases, contradictory:

- **Cell adhesion** exhibited conflicting signals: it was found to be RE-deficient in heterochromatin regions, enriched in activating histone modifications (H3K4me3,

H3K9ac, H3K27ac), and simultaneously depleted in the enhancer-associated H3K4me1 mark, which could be a sign of promoter-specific regulation.

- **Cell cycle** pathways showed ambiguous results in TFBS-based studies but were consistently RE-enriched in heterochromatin regions and activated by promoter-associated chromatin marks across multiple cell lines.
- **Cell migration** was RE-deficient in both the short-term TFBS study and in the H3K4me1 enhancer analysis.
- **Cell death** was RE-enriched in short-term TFBS data and in heterochromatin marks yet deficient in the H3K4me1 enhancer context.
- **Cytoskeleton organization** was consistently RE-deficient, both in TFBS (short-term) and heterochromatin-linked analyses.

Except for cell migration, which showed consistent signals of RE-deficiency, none of the other categories exhibited a clear, unidirectional pattern of enrichment or depletion across all modalities. This complexity reflects the evolutionary trajectories of these pathways under diverse and often opposing selective pressures and run-away evolutionary scenarios.

Public literature supports this interpretation of multifaceted evolutionary dynamics. For example, immune-related cell migration molecules - such as integrins and chemokines - have evolved under strong positive selection in primates, driven by the need to fine-tune immune responses and interactions with viral envelope proteins, including adaptations in genes like *ITGA4* (Byrareddy et al., 2015; Gulati et al., 2017; D. M et al., 2012). Focal adhesion complexes have continued to evolve even in the recent evolutionary horizon, with species-specific phenotypic differences observed between humans and chimpanzees (Advani et al., 2016). In stark contrast, cadherin genes such as *CDH2* (N-cadherin) and *CDH4* (R-cadherin), essential for neuronal migration and axon guidance, are subject to strong purifying selection in the primate lineage (Petersen et al., 2024).

The evolution of cell cycle regulation in vertebrates and mammals has been shaped primarily by gene duplications that led to increasing complexity in the cyclin-CDK network (Nieduszynski et al., 2002) and conferred new primate-specific CDK activators in the Speedy/RINGO family (Chauhan et al., 2012). Moreover, humans and great apes exhibit a higher rate of interspersed segmental duplications than adjacent clades (Marques-Bonet et al., 2009), potentially contributing to the increased complexity of cell cycle control. The RE enrichment observed in heterochromatin-associated regulatory regions may indicate that

many RE insertions within these essential pathways are selectively silenced through heterochromatinization.

Cell death pathways in mammals - and particularly in primates - have been extensively shaped by positive selection. This evolutionary pressure is thought to arise from the dual demands of increased brain complexity and constant exposure to pathogens (Green & Fitzgerald, 2016; Tummers & Green, 2022). As with cell cycle genes, apoptotic regulators have undergone lineage-specific gene duplications, especially in vertebrates and mammals. The *BCL-2* gene family, for instance, contains around 10 orthology groups in birds and amphibians and approximately 13 in mammals (Aouacheria et al., 2005; Banjara et al., 2020). Some of these genes have been co-opted by viruses to manipulate host cell death pathways (Gallo et al., 2017). The human *BCL2* gene itself shows evidence of recent positive selection (within the last 100,000 years) in African populations, likely driven by viral threats (Banjara et al., 2020; L. Gu et al., 2023). Furthermore, genes associated with intrinsic, caspase-mediated apoptosis - such as *APAF1*, *CASP9*, and *CASP3* - exhibit strong signatures of positive selection in the human lineage following divergence from macaques. These genes are known to regulate neuronal cell numbers during brain development (Vallender & Lahn, 2006).

The cytoskeleton has evolved in mammals and primates through a highly divergent and dynamic process. While the actin gene is one of the most conserved in the human genome due to its extensive interaction interfaces, it belongs to a large family with 233 functional genes and over 330 pseudogenes (Zhu et al., 2013). This genomic architecture is the hallmark of a "birth-and-death" model of gene family evolution, where functionally redundant genes frequently arise through duplication events that relax the negative selection (Vedula & Kashina, 2018). Moreover, tropomyosin isoforms, which interact with tissue-specific actins, contribute to muscle diversity and body plan complexity, particularly in vertebrates (Erickson, 2007; Gunning et al., 2015).

Microtubules show a similar evolutionary trajectory. While core structural proteins (e.g., α - and β -tubulin) are highly conserved, microtubule-associated proteins (MAPs) evolve more rapidly (Erickson, 2007). For example, the *MAPT/MAP2/MAP4* gene family, which encodes proteins crucial for neuronal structure and function (including the well-known Tau protein, encoded by *MAPT*), has a complex history of splicing and regulation in vertebrates, allowing for functional diversification (Sündermann et al., 2016). Moreover, MAP encoding

genes such as *ASPM* (Abnormal spindle-like microcephaly-associated) and *CDK5RAP2* show strong and consistent signatures of positive selection across mammals, including primates, with evolutionary rates correlated to brain size in multiple lineages (Montgomery & Mundy, 2014).

In summary, the evolutionary trajectories of cellular adhesion, migration, cytoskeleton organization, cell cycle regulation, and cell death are shaped by a combination of purifying and positive selection, gene duplication events, functional diversification, and co-evolution with pathogenic pressures. The intricate and sometimes contradictory RE-linked regulatory patterns uncovered in this research reflect the underlying biological complexity and the heterogeneous selective landscapes that have shaped these processes.

3.6.3. Signaling pathways

A third group of pathways, characterized by divergent patterns of RE-linked regulatory association, comprises signaling cascades that do not exhibit clear functional overlap with cellular migration, adhesion, cell cycle, cell death, cytoskeleton organization, or immune processes. In the initial TFBS analysis performed on the K562 cell line (Nikitin et al., 2018), several pathways - namely Notch, Wnt, IGF1R, and integrin signaling - were identified as RE-enriched over long evolutionary timescales. In contrast, PDGF, TGF- β , EGFR, insulin, AMPK, p38, and estrogen signaling pathways exhibited enrichment in RE-linked TFBS over shorter evolutionary timescales, whereas other steroid receptor-mediated pathways were found to be RE-deficient.

In contrast to these observations, the broader TFBS analysis across 13 human cell lines (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019) identified intracellular signaling pathways as RE-deficient at both evolutionary depths. This conclusion was further supported by the analysis of H3K4me1-marked enhancers (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019), which also reported a general depletion of RE-associated regulation in signaling-related gene sets. Subsequent analyses - including the five-chromatin-mark study (Igolkina et al., 2019) and the integrative consensus intersection study (Nikitin, 2025) - did not yield conclusive patterns regarding the evolutionary dynamics of signaling pathway regulation.

This composite regulatory profile may reflect a mechanistic preference: the essential components of many signaling pathways appear to be primarily regulated at promoter-

proximal regions, rather than through distal enhancer elements marked by H3K4me1. Additionally, the essential nature of intracellular signaling genes likely subjects them to strong purifying selection, reducing the tolerance for disruptive RE insertions. Nonetheless, a subset of pathways - particularly those identified as enriched in the initial K562 TFBS dataset - may be undergoing more rapid evolution and regulatory expansion, potentially facilitated by RE-linked activating TFBS in promoter contexts.

- **Notch signaling.** A pivotal event in recent human evolution of this ancient pathway was the segmental duplication of the *NOTCH2* gene, which gave rise to a family of human-specific paralogs, *NOTCH2NL* (Stein, 2024). These genes are highly expressed in neural stem cells (radial glia) and appear to enhance Notch signaling. By interacting with NOTCH receptors, they delay the differentiation of neuronal progenitors into neurons (Fiddes et al., 2018). This mechanism is hypothesized to have been a key contributor to the evolutionary expansion of the human neocortex, illustrating how a primate-specific modification to an ancient pathway can drive significant phenotypic change.
- **Wnt signaling.** This pathway is another ancient system whose core gene subfamilies were established through extensive duplication events early in metazoan evolution (Sidow, 1992). It plays a conserved and fundamental role in patterning the primary embryonic axis (Schubert & Holland, 2013). While the protein components of the pathway are largely conserved across primates, its regulation has been a clear target of recent adaptive evolution. A study of human neural progenitor cells revealed that Wnt-responsive regulatory elements are significantly enriched in loci that have undergone positive selection specifically in the human lineage (Matoba et al., 2024). This suggests that adaptive evolution in humans has fine-tuned how, when, and where Wnt signaling is deployed, linking the evolution of this pathway's control mechanisms to the development of the human brain. The current study shows that, in part, this adaptive regulatory evolution was driven by human REs.
- **IGF1R signaling.** The insulin-like growth factor 1 receptor (IGF1R) signaling system has deep evolutionary roots. The structure and regulatory regions of the *IGF1R* gene have been highly conserved since before the divergence of primates over 85 million years ago (Rotwein, 2017), but in New World Monkeys both the *IGF1R* gene and the gene for its ligand, *IGF1*, underwent accelerated evolution driven by positive

selection (Wallis, 2015). The RE-driven regulatory evolution scenarios require further investigation here.

- **Integrin signaling.** Integrin major subfamilies were established before the divergence of deuterostomes and protostomes and expanded via gene duplication early in vertebrate evolution (A. L. Hughes, 2001). Evidence suggests that the functional divergence of different integrin classes was driven by positive, directional selection, particularly in the central region of the beta subunits, which helps determine which alpha subunits they can partner with (A. L. Hughes, 1992). This long history of duplication and selection created the versatile molecular toolkit for cell-matrix interaction that was later fine-tuned within mammalian and primate lineages to support complex tissue structures and immune functions.
- **PDGF signaling.** The platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF) pathway is an ancient system vital for blood vessel formation, early hematopoiesis and embryonic development (Andrae et al., 2008). While PDGF signaling is conserved throughout the animal kingdom, and there is no clear evidence of recent primate-specific evolution of this signaling pathway, and indirect lines of evidence exist. For instance, genes involved in the epidermal differentiation complex, which is critical for skin barrier function and wound healing - a process where PDGF is a key player - show multiple instances of positive selection across primate branches (Goodwin & de Guzman Strong, 2017).
- **TGF- β Signaling.** The transforming growth factor beta (TGF- β) pathway is a fundamental signaling system that emerged with the first metazoans (Huminiacki et al., 2009). Its complexity increased significantly during vertebrate evolution through whole-genome duplications that expanded its repertoire of ligands, receptors, and Smad signaling molecules (Hinck et al., 2016). In mammals, the three primary isoforms - TGF β 1, TGF β 2, and TGF β 3 - have diverged to take on distinct and essential roles in development, as shown by unique knockout phenotypes in mice, and the total of 33 family members are known (P.-Y. Chen et al., 2023). This functional specialization, which occurred after ancient duplication events, created a sophisticated and versatile system for regulating cell fate that has been largely conserved across mammals (P.-Y. Chen et al., 2023). No evidence for the recent primate-specific evolution of this pathway is found, although two primate-specific TGF- β like pseudogenes with low level of CNS-specific expression were reported (Eketjäll et al., 2004).

- **EGFR Signaling.** The epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) pathway is an ancient metazoans signaling system that has been dynamically shaped by gene duplication and loss (being lost in cnidarians and placozoans) throughout animal evolution (Barberán et al., 2016). Studies in teleost fishes point to a pattern of lineage-specific co-evolution between the receptor and its ligands, indicating the pathway is highly prone to subfunctionalization and neofunctionalization under whole genome duplications (Laisney et al., 2010). Within the primate lineage, and particularly in great apes, there is evidence of positive selection on genes that are functionally linked to EGFR signaling, albeit without direct evidence about EGFR genes themselves. A comparative genomic analysis identified five genes under positive selection exclusively in the great ape lineage, including genes involved in tumor suppression (*IRF3*) and metastasis (*DIAPH2*, *GASK1B*) - processes in which EGFR activity is a central modulator (Tejada-Martinez et al., 2021). This suggests that the functional network surrounding the EGFR pathway has been adaptively modified during recent primate evolution. Interestingly, the same study showed that genes that are related to increased lifespan and are differentially expressed in great apes, are enriched in enhancers that are associated with evolutionary young Alu elements
- **Insulin signaling.** The insulin signaling pathway is an evolutionarily conserved mechanism crucial for metabolism and growth (B. M et al., 2003). This system has been actively shaped by gene duplication and positive selection within the vertebrate lineage (Jin Chan & Steiner, 2000). A key example of primate-specific evolution is the relaxin gene (*RLN*), a member of the insulin-like gene family (Arroyo et al., 2014). This gene duplicated in the common ancestor of catarrhine primates (Old World monkeys and apes) around 30–44 million years ago. Following this duplication, the resulting gene copies were shaped by natural selection, with evidence for positive selection driving convergent evolution between the *RLNI* gene in apes and the single-copy *RLN* gene in New World monkeys. This points to functional tuning of this reproductive and neuroendocrine signaling system within primates.
- **AMPK Signaling.** The AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) pathway is a master regulator of cellular energy that is deeply conserved across all eukaryotes (Trefts & Shaw, 2021). The system's complexity increased in vertebrates through gene duplications that gave rise to multiple isoforms for each of its three subunits (α , β , γ) (Ross et al., 2016). In mammals, this diversification moved further and allowed for at least 12 distinct AMPK complexes with tissue-specific expression patterns, such as

in the brain and skeletal muscle (Smiles et al., 2024). This framework, which enables specialized, context-dependent energy sensing, has been largely conserved throughout recent primate evolution.

- **p38 signaling.** The p38 MAPK pathway is an ancient cellular stress response system with origins tracing back to a common ancestor of animals and fungi, where it orchestrated the osmotic stress response (Shabardina et al., 2025). In mammals, the pathway is mediated by four homologous p38 kinases (*p38 α* , *β* , *γ* , and *δ*), that arose via gene duplication and subsequently acquired distinct tissue expression patterns (Du et al., 2025). This family of highly conserved kinases serves as a central hub for transducing signals from environmental stress and inflammation into cellular responses, and its fundamental architecture has been maintained throughout mammalian evolution.
- **Estrogen signaling.** The estrogen signaling pathway, essential for reproduction since chordates last common ancestor (Callard et al., 2011), has been a direct target of adaptive evolution within the primate lineage. A compelling case is the evolution of the estrogen receptor β gene (*ESR2*). By computationally resurrecting and functionally testing the ancestral anthropoid receptor, it was shown that the gene underwent an episode of positive selection along the stem lineage of New World monkeys (Weckle et al., 2017). This adaptive evolution resulted in a receptor that is a significantly more potent transcriptional activator than both its ancestral and modern human counterparts. This functional shift demonstrates how positive selection has actively tuned the sensitivity of this key endocrine pathway during primate evolution.

The above brief overview of the major RE-enriched signaling pathways reveals that many have undergone multiple rounds of gene duplication, followed by functional specialization of the resulting paralogs. In several cases, this diversification has been accompanied by episodes of positive selection within mammalian or primate lineages. However, it is important to recognize that much of the existing literature is predominantly focused on adaptive changes at the level of protein-coding sequences. In contrast, neutral evolutionary mechanisms (Muñoz-Gómez et al., 2021) and the contributions of non-coding genomic regions (Leypold & Speicher, 2021) have been comparatively underexplored. The present study, alongside future investigations, offers an opportunity to illuminate these less well-

characterized dimensions of signaling pathway evolution, particularly with respect to regulatory changes mediated by REs.

3.6.4. Nervous and sensory systems

This heterogeneous group of molecular processes exhibited a consistent and recognizable pattern across multiple analyses of RE-associated regulatory activity. In the initial K562 TFBS study (Nikitin et al., 2018), processes related to neuronal development and sensory functions were identified as RE-enriched over the long-term evolutionary timescale. Similarly, the broader TFBS study encompassed 13 cell lines (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019) showed sensory perception and neurotransmission as RE-enriched in the long-term evolutionary horizon. These findings were further supported by enhancer-associated chromatin signatures (H3K4me1) (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019) and activating histone marks such as H3K4me3, H3K9ac, and H3K27ac (Igolkina et al., 2019), while corresponding heterochromatin-associated modifications (H3K9me3, H3K27me3) indicated RE-deficiency. Collectively, this consistent enrichment across independent datasets suggests that REs have played a particularly prominent role in shaping the regulatory architecture of the neural system during mammalian evolution, as outlined in the Literature Review. In support of this interpretation, recent reviews have underscored the multifaceted influence of REs on nervous system development - particularly the capacity of LINE elements to introduce transcriptional variability during neurogenesis, contributing to increased neuronal diversity within the human neocortex (Erwin et al., 2014; Larsen et al., 2018; Suarez et al., 2018; Talley & Longworth, 2024; X. Zhang et al., 2020).

Beyond the central nervous system, processes related to sensory perception emerged as strongly RE-enriched in the present study - an observation not previously elaborated upon. Literature evidence supports a pivotal role for REs in the evolutionary refinement of human sensory systems, most notably vision. The acquisition of routine trichromatic vision in Old World primates - a defining characteristic of the human lineage - was directly facilitated by an Alu-mediated NAHR event. This recombination resulted in the duplication of an ancestral opsin gene and gave rise to the OPN1LW and OPN1MW opsin gene array on the X chromosome (Dulai et al., 1999). This evolutionary innovation was selectively advantageous as it allowed to detect ripe fruits (that are reddish against the green background) and enhanced socio-sexual signaling via detecting skin coloration (Hiramatsu et

al., 2017), whereas early mammalian ancestors, adapted for nocturnal life, were dichromatic (Carvalho et al., 2017).

This sensory innovation fundamentally reshaped primate ecological interactions, reinforcing a shift toward visual dominance. In parallel, expansion of cortical regions within the temporal and occipital lobes accompanied the processing demands of enriched visual input (Kaas, 2008). Notably, the extensive proliferation of Alu elements in primate genomes provided the necessary homologous sequences to enable such recombination-driven gene duplications. In the absence of this RE-mediated substrate, the evolution of primate vision would likely have proceeded at a slower pace, profoundly altering hominin evolutionary trajectories (Kawamura, 2016).

This enhanced visual capacity in primates was paralleled by a marked decline in olfactory function (Cooper, n.d.; Dong et al., 2009; Gilad et al., 2004). This evolutionary trade-off - where one sensory modality evolves at the expense of another - is reflected in the structure of the primate genome (Niimura & Nei, 2007). The olfactory receptor (OR) gene superfamily, the largest in the mammalian genome, has experienced widespread pseudogenization in the human lineage. Whereas mice retain approximately 1,400 OR genes with only 20–25% being pseudogenes, humans possess a reduced repertoire of ~800 OR loci, with over 60% being non-functional (Dong et al., 2009; Gilad et al., 2003). This progressive loss of olfactory gene function, which increased from New World monkeys to Old World monkeys and apes, culminates in humans having one of the highest proportions of OR pseudogenes (Rouquier et al., 2000).

REs, particularly LINEs and Alu elements, likely accelerated this genomic attrition. Their dense presence between OR loci created recombination hotspots that promoted genomic instability, facilitating both individual gene deletions and the loss of entire OR gene clusters via NAHR (Redaelli et al., 2024; Song et al., 2018). Indirect support for this mechanism is provided by the composite LTR-retrotransposon-like element *Xiao*, found at 30 genomic loci across 12 chromosomes, which incorporates sequence fragments from the decaying OR7E gene cluster. This element likely emerged after the divergence of apes from Old World monkeys, further illustrating how REs can repurpose degenerated genomic material into new mobile elements (Ji & Zhao, 2008).

While the roles of REs in the evolutionary histories of vision and olfaction are now well-supported, their influence on other sensory modalities - such as audition, gustation, and somatosensation - remains underexplored. These systems may be more subtly shaped by cumulative regulatory rewiring rather than large-scale structural events. However, applying

the mechanistic principles established for RE exaptation - particularly their capacity to function as regulatory elements - provides a foundation for formulating testable hypotheses regarding RE contributions to the fine-tuning of these systems. Future research will be essential to elucidate their evolutionary impact.

3.6.5. Metabolic pathways

A variety of metabolic pathways were represented among both RE-enriched and RE-deficient groups across the analyses conducted in the present study. In the initial K562 cell line TFBS study (Nikitin et al., 2018) chondroitin sulfate and heparin metabolism, together with cAMP metabolism, were identified as RE-enriched within the long-term evolutionary horizon, whereas the catabolism of phospholipids and heterocyclic nitrogen-containing compounds was enriched on the short-term scale; no metabolic process in this dataset was classified as RE-deficient. In the broader 13 cell lines TFBS study (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019), amino acid metabolism, lipid metabolism, and xenobiotic detoxification were RE-enriched in the long-term horizon, while lipid metabolism and xenobiotic detoxification (the same pathway group) were enriched on the short-term scale; again, no metabolic process group was annotated as RE-deficient. Lipid metabolism also emerged as RE-enriched in the H3K4me1 enhancer-associated chromatin modification analysis, whereas in this dataset, metal metabolism and ion transport were classified as RE-deficient (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019). Furthermore, lipid metabolism, along with the electron transfer chain, xenobiotic catabolism, amino acid metabolism, and polyamine metabolism, appeared among RE-enriched processes in the analysis of activating and repressing chromatin modifications (Igolkina et al., 2019). Conversely, nucleic base metabolism and DNA metabolism were enriched for RE-linked heterochromatin marks while being simultaneously RE-deficient in active chromatin contexts, and mitochondria related pathways were also RE-deficient in active histone modifications.

The pattern emerging from these results is, in its broad outlines, as straightforward as that observed for the sensory and nervous system group:

- Lipid metabolism, amino acid metabolism, and xenobiotic detoxification exhibit an elevated rate of regulatory change in mammals, with xenobiotic detoxification evolving at an accelerated pace in the short-term horizon (Old World Monkey evolution).
- Nucleic base metabolism and DNA metabolism remain conserved across both evolutionary horizons.

- Chondroitin sulfate metabolism, heparin metabolism, cAMP metabolism, polyamine metabolism, metal metabolism, catabolism of heterocyclic compounds, and the electron transfer chain yield inconsistent signals across different datasets, suggesting that their regulatory evolutionary trajectories are more complex and require further investigation.

The available literature provides general support for the first two conclusions derived from the present series of analyses.

First of all, compared to other primates, humans allocate a disproportionately large share of their daily energy budget to brain metabolism, a demand that could only be met through radical shifts in dietary quality, particularly an increased reliance on energy-dense foods rich in lipids and protein accompanied with massive fire usage since 1 mya (Berna et al., 2012; Leonard et al., 2010). This dietary transition, in turn, necessitated adaptations in the metabolic pathways responsible for nutrient processing and energy storage, which has led to the modern human phenotype being characterized by a uniquely high level of adiposity compared to other primates (Zihlman & Bolter, 2015), a trait now understood as a critical evolutionary buffer for the energetically demanding brains that also require lipids (such as gangliosides) for phospholipid bilayers of neurons (Sorokin et al., 2020). Importantly, this change in adipose tissue development was mainly achieved by the chromatin landscape transitions, mainly by decreasing the number of regulatory elements that drive beigeing of white adipose tissue and transition of it from fat storage to fat catabolism (Swain-Lenz et al., 2019). The evidence presented here indicates that RE-linked regulatory elements could impact this gene regulatory networks rewiring.

The broader trend of regulatory evolution is corroborated by specific examples of human-lineage adaptations in key lipid and amino acid metabolism related genes:

- **ACSF3 (acyl-CoA synthetase family member 3):** A regulatory variant rs34590044-A elevates the gene's expression in the liver of modern humans compared to other apes, controls amino acids metabolism, correlates with both increased basal metabolic rate and taller stature and is under strong positive selection for the last 20000 years, with especially high signal in the last 5000 years (Y. Zhang et al., 2025).
- **ADH4 (alcohol dehydrogenase 4):** The ancestral sequence reconstruction study showed that ADH4 enzyme, which is involved in first-pass metabolism in the digestive tract, revealed a dramatic gain-of-function for ethanol metabolism that occurred approximately 10 million years ago in the hominin lineage, after the

divergence from orangutans (Carrigan et al., 2015). This adaptation coincides with paleontological evidence for a shift to a more terrestrial lifestyle, where hominins would have encountered fruits that had fallen to the forest floor and undergone natural fermentation.

Concurrently, as primates diversified into new ecological niches, they encountered a vast array of plant secondary metabolites (PSMs) and other environmental toxins. This initiated a co-evolutionary "arms race", driving the rapid evolution of detoxification pathways to neutralize these xenobiotic compounds (Chaney et al., 2024). This evolution was connected with cytochrome P450 (CYP) superfamily: genes that encode xenobiotic-detoxifying enzymes (primarily in families CYP1, CYP2, and CYP3) are characterized by frequent gene duplication and loss, a process known as "birth-and-death" evolution (Kawashima & Satta, 2014; Thomas, 2007). This rapid turnover creates genetic novelty, allowing lineages to expand or contract their detoxification toolkit in response to specific environmental pressures (K. L. Harris et al., 2022). Evidence for accelerated evolution and positive selection on CYP genes is particularly strong in primates, as different feeding strategies expose species to different arrays of PSMs which lead to key functional differences in substrate specificity between humans and non-human primate models like cynomolgus monkeys and marmosets (Uno et al., 2016, 2018).

The arylamine N-acetyltransferase (NAT) gene family, accounting for another pathway of detoxification, diverged in primates into two main paralogs with distinct evolutionary patterns (Hickman et al., 1994). NAT1 is subject to strong purifying selection, suggesting a conserved and critical role in endogenous metabolism. NAT2, however, shows clear evidence of positive selection and diversifying selection, consistent with its primary role in metabolizing environmental and dietary xenobiotics (Sabbagh et al., 2013). The geographic patterns of NAT2 polymorphisms in human populations have been linked to the shift from hunter-gatherer to agricultural lifestyles, which introduced a new suite of dietary toxins and altered the selective regime acting on the gene.

This pattern of high rate of gene duplication, loss, and positive selection in xenobiotic metabolism genes is a hallmark of a co-evolutionary arms race, where there is genetic flexibility for a species to rapidly respond to novel chemical threats, especially in human evolutionary lineage with series of dietary transitions. The evidence presented here shows that RE provided their TFBS to significantly rewire regulatory networks of these genes.

The conserved metabolic pathways (DNA and nitrogenous basis metabolism) are well supported by the available literature, albeit the current understanding of the evolutionary dynamics is more nuanced:

- **DNA metabolism core machinery** is highly evolutionarily conserved across the human lineage, with fundamental enzymes and complexes involved in replication, repair, and recombination showing deep evolutionary roots in eukaryotic-archaeal common ancestors, though specific components and regulatory programs, like replication timing, have evolved and diverged to meet species-specific needs, particularly between humans and chimpanzees (Bracci et al., 2023).
- **Folate metabolism.** Folate is essential for the *de novo* synthesis of purines and thymidine (Y. Zheng & Cantley, 2019). The folate receptor (FOLR) gene family, which is critical for cellular uptake of folate, also shows clear evidence of purifying selection against gene conversions between paralogs in primates (Petronella & Drouin, 2014).
- Several **NHEJ pathway genes**, including XRCC4, NBS1, Artemis and POL λ exhibit recurrent signatures of positive selection during simian primate evolution (XRCC4 was subject to positive selection in modern humans), which could be connected to the ongoing evolutionary arms race between viruses/REs and NHEJ genes (Demogines et al., 2010).

As the last part of the metabolic pathways investigation in the current research, the pathways without the clear signal of RE-enrichment/deficiency show the following complex patterns of their structural and sequence evolution:

- **cAMP metabolism/signaling.** The core intracellular components of the cAMP signaling pathway, including the enzyme adenylyl cyclase and Protein Kinase A (PKA) which is activated by it, are ancient and deeply conserved across all eukaryotes (Nair et al., 2019; Raker et al., 2016; Ritchie et al., 2008). Conversely, the upstream GPCRs that sense extracellular signals and activate the pathway, are subject to the massive, lineage-specific diversification which allows organisms to adapt to new signals (e.g., hormones, neurotransmitters, odorants) by evolving new receptors (De Mendoza et al., 2014).
- **Polyamine Metabolism.** The fundamental enzymes of the pathway, such as spermidine synthase (SPDS), are ancient and derive from a common ancestor

preceding the prokaryote-eukaryote split, although later SPDS underwent independent duplications in plants, animals and fungi, leading to neofunctionalization and origin of spermine synthase (SPMS) (Minguet et al., 2008).

- **Electron transfer chain (ETC).** Numerous genes encoding subunits of the ETC, particularly those in Complex III, Complex IV, and the cytochrome c gene (CYC), exhibit significantly accelerated rates of nonsynonymous substitution specifically within the anthropoid primate lineage, which could be connected with massively increased energetic demands of the expanding neocortex (Brand et al., 2022; Grossman et al., 2004). Simultaneously, COX5A gene shows higher levels of gene expression in the human cerebral cortex compared to that of chimpanzees and gorillas (Uddin et al., 2008).
- **Chondroitin sulfate and heparin metabolism.** Glycosaminoglycanes (GAG) metabolism evolved in a mosaic manner across metazoans, as their phyla have different GAG types (hyaluronan, chondroitin, heparan etc) (DeAngelis, 2002). Moreover, an arms race is in place between the host and pathogenic bacteria glycosyltransferases since the latter synthesise bacterial capsule molecules that reduce immune response mimicking the host extracellular matrix (DeAngelis, 2002), although impact of RE at this coevolution is unknown.
- **Metal metabolism.** The fundamental protein families responsible for transporting, storing, and detoxifying essential and toxic metals (e.g., iron, copper, zinc) were established long before the emergence of mammals and are highly conserved across all domains of life (Bradley et al., 2021; Nelson, 1999; Palacios et al., 2025). Nevertheless, there are primate-specific aspects, such as the evolution of host-pathogen interactions involving metal sequestration known as "nutritional immunity" (Antelo et al., 2021).
- **Catabolism of heterocyclic compounds.** Whereas exogenous heterocyclic compounds are catabolised by CYP proteins (Turesky & Le Marchand, 2011), a key enzyme of endogenous heterocycles catabolism, uricase (which breaks down uric acid), was inactivated and became a pseudogene in the common ancestor of hominoids (Chang, 2014). This gene loss, which leads to higher uric acid levels in hominoids, is thought to be an adaptation, possibly because uric acid is a potent antioxidant that could substitute for the lost ability to synthesize vitamin C in this lineage.

The overarching theme among the reviewed metabolic pathways with various RE status is profound evolutionary modularity: a deeply conserved core of enzymatic machinery is regulated by a highly plastic and rapidly evolving network of control elements, allowing for swift adaptation to new ecological pressures without compromising fundamental cellular functions. Table 21 summarises the reviewed evolutionary trajectories of metabolic pathways according to the current RE regulatory analysis and the public literature.

Table 21. The summary of metabolic pathways evolutionary trajectories, summarizing the RE-driven regulatory evolution mode, other dominant evolutionary modes, key genetic players, and selective pressures for each metabolic category.

Metabolic pathway	RE-driven regulatory status according to the current study	Dominant evolutionary mode according to the public literature	Key genes/families	Primary selective pressure	Key timescale of change
Lipid metabolism	RE-enriched	Accelerated regulatory evolution	ACSF3, genes near human-decreased open chromatin regions	Encephalization, high-fat diet	Hominin, human
Amino acid metabolism	RE-enriched	Accelerated regulatory evolution; positive selection	ADH4, ADSL, genes near RE-linked TFBS	Dietary shifts, encephalization	Hominin, human
Xenobiotic detoxification	RE-enriched	Birth-and-death evolution; positive selection	CYP1/2/3, NAT2	Dietary toxins (PSMs)	Mammalian, primate
Nucleic acid metabolism	RE-deficient	Dynamic conservation (purifying selection on core; positive selection on regulation)	FOLR1/2 (purifying); UCEs (decaying)	Genome stability, adaptation to REs	Primate
DNA repair	RE-deficient	Dynamic conservation (purifying selection on core; positive selection on components)	NHEJ pathway genes	Genome stability, adaptation to REs	Simian primate
Electron transport chain	Inconsistent	Positive selection in anthropoids	COX5A, CYC, other ETC genes	Encephalization	Anthropoid primate
cAMP signaling	Inconsistent	Modular evolution (Conserved core, diversified receptors)	PKA (conserved); GPCRs (diversified)	Adaptation to new signals	Eukaryote (core), lineage-specific (receptors)
Polyamine metabolism	Inconsistent	Convergent evolution; purifying selection on core	SPDS (conserved); SPMS (convergent)	Essential cellular functions	Eukaryote (core), independent

					lineages (SPMS)
Metal ion homeostasis	Inconsistent	Deep conservation	Metal transporters, metallothioneins	Biogeochemistry, essential functions	Ancient (pre-mammalian)
Heterocyclic compounds catabolism	Inconsistent	Birth-and-death evolution; pseudogenesation	CYP1/2/3, NAT2, uricase	Dietary toxins (PSMs), antioxidants	Mammalian, primate

3.6.6. Epigenetic processes, gene expression regulation and transcription

This broad functional category of molecular processes was less extensively represented across the current series of epigenomic analyses. In the initial K562 cell line TFBS study (Nikitin et al., 2018), the interplay between histone deacetylation and DNA methylation, together with structural components of the nuclear lumen, was classified as RE-enriched within the short-term evolutionary horizon, whereas transcription and RNA processing were identified as RE-deficient in the same dataset. In the 13 cell lines TFBS analysis (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019), posttranscriptional silencing by small RNAs was RE-enriched in the short-term horizon, while chromatin structure appeared among RE-deficient pathway groups in the long-term horizon. In the H3K4me1 enhancer-associated analysis of RE regulatory influence (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019), both posttranscriptional silencing by small RNAs and chromatin structure were identified as RE-enriched within the long-term timescale. Finally, the analysis of five chromatin modifications (Igolkina et al., 2019), conducted on the long-term evolutionary horizon, revealed that RNA synthesis and chromatin structure were enriched in RE-linked repressive chromatin marks while simultaneously RE-deficient in active chromatin contexts.

While the overall picture remains inconsistent, several emerging trends can be discerned:

- Chromatin structure components display variable and sometimes contradictory evolutionary signals.
- Transcription *per se* is likely conservative, tending toward RE-deficiency.
- Posttranscriptional silencing by small RNAs is likely rapidly evolving and consistently RE-enriched across both evolutionary horizons.
- The interplay between histone deacetylation and DNA methylation, observed as RE-enriched only in the initial K562 analysis, suggests a weak but notable signal of accelerated regulatory evolution on a short-term scale.

Chromatin structure. According to the public literature, the apparent inconsistency of chromatin structure evolutionary trajectory is rather a fundamental signature of a layered evolutionary process. The primate genome maintains a deeply conserved architectural framework while simultaneously experiencing rapid, lineage-specific innovations in regulatory regions, driven almost entirely by the activity of REs. For example, comparative study of human and chimpanzee iPSCs differentiating into osteogenic cells identified hundreds of differentially expressed genes, indicating substantial underlying changes in the regulatory landscape governing skeletal development (Housman et al., 2022). This fast divergence in chromatin architecture is likely driven primarily by REs, as 63% of primate specific open chromatin regions are within REs (Jacques et al., 2013). Moreover, as it was discussed in the Literature Review, Alu elements are significantly enriched within critical architectural features of the genome, including TADs and SE domains, which can fundamentally alter the 3D folding of chromatin, thereby creating new regulatory neighborhoods and possibilities for gene control (Dixon et al., 2012; Glinsky, 2018; Soibam, 2017). Dysregulation of these Alu-associated epigenomic boundaries can lead to various pathologies, including neurodegenerative diseases (Larsen et al., 2017, 2018). Finally, the evolutionary dynamics of TAD-delineating CTCF sites in primate genomes exemplifies and interplay between conservative and quickly evolving aspects of chromatin structure. Importantly, a significant fraction of CTCF binding sites in mammalian genomes are derived from TEs (Azazi et al., 2020; Diehl et al., 2020). Mammalian TAD boundaries are characterized by clusters of both evolutionarily ancient and more recent, lineage-specific CTCF sites (Kentepozidou et al., 2020). This clustered architecture provides a unique combination of stability and evolutionary plasticity. The overall boundary is conserved, but the turnover of individual CTCF sites within the cluster is tolerated, which allows for the gradual rewiring of the regulatory landscape over evolutionary time.

Transcription. The available evidence also supports the general conservation of transcription *per se*: the fundamental transcription machinery components, such as the subunits of RNA Polymerase II and the TATA-binding protein (TBP) family, show profound evolutionary conservation across all eukaryotes (Duttke, 2015). The diversification of this machinery largely occurred through ancient gene duplications that predate the divergence of mammals. This stability extends to the mechanisms that ensure the fidelity of transcription. For instance, factors like the Rpb9 subunit and TFIIS, which are involved in proofreading and enhancing the accuracy of RNAPII, are highly conserved from yeast to humans (Chung et al., 2023). This underscores the intense purifying selection acting to

maintain the precision of this fundamental cellular process. The conserved core of transcription machinery interacts with highly flexible RE-driven regulome: as was discussed earlier in Literature Review and further studied in the main sections, RE exerted enormous impact on human gene regulatory networks, with at least 25% of experimentally confirmed promoters contained RE-derived sequences (Feschotte, 2008). According to the current 13 cell lines TFBS study (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019), 72% of TFBS within the 10 kb TSS neighbourhood are overlapping with RE coordinates which could be an overestimation due to the intersection algorithm used (bedtools), but nevertheless further validates high prevalence of REs in human regulatory elements.

Posttranscriptional silencing by small RNA. Gene expression regulation by small RNA is highly flexible and RE-driven (both through the mechanisms of arms race and co-option) in an evolutionary perspective, which is in stark contrast to the core transcriptional machinery conservation. For example, a large, primate-specific microRNA cluster on chromosome 19 (C19MC) is composed of dozens of microRNA genes that originated directly from Alu SINEs (Lehnert et al., 2009). The genomic architecture of this cluster, where individual microRNA genes are flanked by a characteristic Alu-LINE signature, provides clear evidence of its expansion through retrotransposition-mediated duplication events. Moreover, since thousands of Alu elements are residing in human genes UTRs, the birth of the C19MC cluster - created a vast, primate-specific post-transcriptional regulatory network *de novo* (Hoffman et al., 2013), representing another example of RE domestication. Apart from microRNA based regulation, the continuous emergence of new, primate-specific RE families exerts constant selective pressure on the PIWI pathway to adapt and recognize these new threats, and it is a major driver of the rapid evolution observed in piRNA clusters across primate species (Assis & Kondrashov, 2009; Rajan & Ramasamy, 2014; Rosenkranz et al., 2022; T. Yu et al., 2019).

Histone deacetylation and DNA methylation interplay. The weak signal of RE-driven evolutionary acceleration of these processes points at the ongoing evolutionary arms race between REs and chromatin repressive mechanisms that mitigate their activity. The major example is KRAB-ZNF proteins that were discussed previously in Literature Review and are discussed in the current section. This family, being the largest TF family in tetrapods (P. Yang et al., 2017), has undergone a massive and rapid expansion specifically in primate lineages, resulting in hundreds of primate-specific KRAB-ZNF genes (Jacobs et al., 2014). The primary function of these newly evolved KRAB-ZNFs is to recognize and silence

specific families of REs, whereas disruption of this system can lead to various pathologies including neurodegenerative disorders (Y.-C. Chen et al., 2025).

KRAB-ZNFs execute this function by recruiting the universal co-repressor KAP1 (also known as TRIM28) (Ecco et al., 2017). KAP1, in turn, acts as a scaffold to recruit a host of epigenetic silencing enzymes, including HDACs and the histone methyltransferase SETDB1. SETDB1 deposits the repressive H3K9me3 mark on chromatin, which serves as a platform for the subsequent recruitment of DNA methyltransferases (DNMTs) and the establishment of stable, long-term silencing through DNA methylation. Taken together, these elements also comprise a human silencing hub (HUSH) complex that detects REs by their long intron-less sequences and silences these elements (Lehner, 2025).

As new RE families emerge and spread through the primate genome, new KRAB-ZNF genes evolve to recognize and repress them (P. Yang et al., 2017). Over time, mutations in the REs can alter the KRAB-ZNF binding site, allowing the RE to "escape" repression and begin a new wave of proliferation. This, in turn, creates selective pressure for the evolution of new KRAB-ZNFs that can recognize the escaped variant (Y.-C. Chen et al., 2025; Jacobs et al., 2014). For example, the primate-specific ZNF91 underwent a series of structural changes between 8 and 12 million years ago that enabled it to recognize and repress SVA elements (Jacobs et al., 2014). The older ZNF93 evolved to repress the primate L1 lineage until the L1PA3 subfamily mutated its binding site, escaping ZNF93's control (Forey et al., n.d.). This continuous cycle of RE innovation, host repression, RE escape, and new host repression is the primary engine driving the accelerated evolution of both the REs themselves and the hundreds of primate-specific KRAB-ZNF genes. Moreover, once an RE family becomes ancient and transcriptionally inert, the KRAB-ZNF/KAP1 system that evolved to silence it can be repurposed, or exapted, for the regulation of host genes, particularly those located near now-fixed RE insertions (Ecco et al., 2016; Quenneville et al., 2012). This process is considered a major source for the origin of human-specific gene regulatory networks, especially in the brain (Y.-C. Chen et al., 2025; Imbeault et al., 2017). Taken together, the available evidence supports the accelerated RE-driven evolution of gene regulation by small RNA and epigenetic silencing by histone deacetylation and DNA methylation, whereas transcription *per se* is conserved, and chromatin structure has been evolving in a complex multifaceted manner.

3.6.7. Translation, ribosome biogenesis and protein degradation

The processes of translation, ribosome biogenesis and protein degradation were consistently RE-deficient across the series of studies, demonstrating the unprecedented degree of concordance between the different analyses. The initial K562-only research showed ribosome assembly and protein translation regulation, as well as proteasomal degradation, as RE-deficient processes (Nikitin et al., 2018). The 13 cell lines study of RE-linked TFBS demonstrated translation and ribosome biogenesis RE-deficient at both evolutionary horizons (Nikitin, Garazha, et al., 2019), and the H3K4me1 study confirmed protein ubiquitination and degradation as RE-deficient pathways (Nikitin, Kolosov, et al., 2019). Finally, the analysis of 5 chromatin modifications showed that translation and protein maturation were RE-enriched by repressive histone marks and simultaneously deficient by activating modifications (Igolkina et al., 2019).

The available evidence strongly supports the ancient evolutionary paths of these processes, along with their high level of conservation across mammals and primates. The ribosome is an ancient molecular machine, and its core components - both ribosomal RNAs (rRNAs) and proteins - are under strong and continuous purifying selection (Noller, 2024; Pilla & Bahadur, 2019; Schillewaert et al., 2012; Sultanov & Hochwagen, 2022). This intense conservation extends to the broader machinery, including the universal translation initiation factors that are homologous across all domains of life (Hernández et al., 2010; Kyrpides & Woese, 1998; J. H. Lee et al., 1999) and the enzymes of the ubiquitin multigene family, which are themselves highly conserved and shared by eukaryotes and asgardarchaea (Hatano et al., 2022; Souza et al., 2025; Zaremba-Niedzwiedzka et al., 2017).

However, this conservation is not absolute, and evidence of recent, primate-specific evolution exists:

- The small ribosome subunit assembly protein WDR75 is under strong purifying selection across mammals, but there is a significant diversifying selection specifically among African great apes, which suggests recent adaptive evolution in the ribosome assembly process within the hominid lineage (L. Lee & Whittall, 2025).
- According to comparative ribosome profiling in human, chimpanzee, and macaque cell lines, there are significant differences in ribosome occupancy for hundreds of genes (S. H. Wang et al., 2018). This indicates that the efficiency of protein translation for specific genes has evolved between primate species, with post-

translational buffering (including protein covalent modification) mechanisms emerging as a major factor in determining final protein levels.

- Primate-specific Alu elements have been co-opted into a novel regulatory role in translation: experimental studies have shown that free Alu RNA can stimulate translation, while Alu RNA complexed with its cognate proteins (SRP9/14) acts as a general inhibitor of translation (Bovia et al., 1995; Gussakovsky et al., 2024; Häsler & Strub, 2006b). This primate-specific mechanism, which is often activated under cellular stress, represents a significant, RE-driven layer of regulatory control superimposed on the ancient, conserved translational apparatus.

The protein maturation and degradation pathways are highly conserved too, particularly the ubiquitin-proteasome system (UPS). The ubiquitin molecule itself is one of the most conserved proteins in eukaryotes, with a functionally identical version present in the last eukaryotic common ancestor over two billion years ago (Allan & Phillips, 2017). The genes encoding ubiquitin are part of a multigene family that, despite opportunities for divergence, is maintained in a near-identical state by powerful purifying selection (Nei et al., 2000). Nevertheless, specific components can evolve rapidly in response to strong selective pressures. For example, in laurasiatherian mammals spermatogenesis-related UPS genes underwent positive selection and rapid evolution in lineages that adapted to the thermal stress of abdominal testes (Ding et al., 2021), although this effect is not manifested in primates. Moreover, the precise timing and specific maternal proteins targeted for degradation during preimplantation development exhibit significant species-specific differences, especially between cetartiodactyls and rodents (Kinterova et al., 2025).

In summary, the stable foundation of translation, protein maturation and degradation has been the platform for primate-specific innovations, including the direct regulation of translation by Alu RNAs and the adaptive evolution of specific UPS components in response to unique selective pressures such as brain development and thermal stress. Finally, the “Translation, ribosome biogenesis and protein degradation” group is the last group of processes that received comparable signals throughout the studies. The unclassified processes such as oocyte maturation, small cell lung cancer and chronic myeloid leukemia are not discussed in the current section because of the evidence scarcity. Figure 58 outlines the RE-enrichment/deficiency signals by group of biological processes with the available public evidence cited in this section.

Figure 58. Summary of consensus RE-enrichment/deficiency signals detected in the series of Retrospect studies (colored font) compared with the public evidence cited in the section 3.6 (italics).

3.7. Current limitations of the Retrospect analytical approach and directions for further studies

The series of research analyses described in the current thesis describes the high-level picture of molecular processes and groups of pathways, depicting their evolutionary trajectories at the level of mammalian and primate evolution: all and evolutionary young elements with less than 8% divergence of RE family consensus sequence, corresponding to divergence between the human evolutionary lineage and New World Monkeys (Giordano et al., 2007). The Retrospect method invented and described here has proven effective in identifying broad evolutionary trends in RE-mediated gene regulation across different epigenetic modalities in human cell lines. However, the rapid advancement of genomic technologies opens several new avenues to refine this analysis, enhance its resolution, and move from correlational observations to causal mechanisms. The following research avenues represent logical next steps to expand upon the present work, while simultaneously

addressing its complementary limitations. Broadly, these directions can be categorized into two principal groups:

- **Expanding the scope.** The “broadening” approaches aim to extend the current analytical framework by incorporating additional epigenetic modalities, a wider range of tissues and organs, and comparative data from model organisms, as well as by refining genome assemblies and annotations and applying emerging sequencing technologies. The overarching objective of these efforts remains general: to elucidate RE-driven evolutionary trends at the scale of whole organisms, tissues, or clades.
- **Increasing the resolution.** The “deepening” approaches focus on more targeted investigations, addressing specific RE classes, families, or even individual elements. These directions seek to examine RE dynamics at the level of discrete evolutionary branching events (for instance, the divergence of human and chimpanzee lineages) and to uncover the contributions of RE activity to the regulation of individual molecular processes and genes.

Each potential research direction is inherently connected with the corresponding limitation, so they will be discussed together.

3.7.1. The “broadening” future research directions.

New model organisms. An important direction for future research lies in comparing the evolutionary patterns of gene regulation, as explored herein, with those affecting gene or protein structure. Moreover, the computational framework developed in this study could be extended to a diverse array of model organisms beyond mammals and vertebrates. The feasibility of such comparative applications will depend largely on two factors: (i) the availability of high-resolution epigenomic datasets, including TFBS and histone modification data, and (ii) the availability of well-curated molecular pathway annotations in the species under investigation. While human pathway maps may be transferable to closely related species such as non-human primates, their application to more distantly related mammals would likely require substantial content adaptation (A. Buzdin et al., 2018; Doncheva et al., 2021; Wishart et al., 2024). For instance, comparative analyses between humans and mice may be feasible only with careful mapping of orthologous gene sets.

Extending this framework to more divergent taxa, such as zebrafish, *Drosophila*, or *Arabidopsis*, would necessitate both customized pathway reconstructions and access to comprehensive epigenomic resources.

New organs, tissues, and epigenetic modalities. Since 2018–2019, when the RetroSpect analytical framework was first developed and validated, the universe of available epigenomic data has expanded substantially. This growth is beginning to illuminate the previously uncharted “dark matter” of tissue- and species-specific regulatory patterns. Several major public databases and consortia continue to serve as comprehensive resources for human epigenomic data, including the ENCODE Project (Abascal et al., 2020; E. P. Consortium, 2012), the NIH Roadmap Epigenomics Mapping Consortium (Chadwick, 2012; Satterlee et al., 2019), and the Cistrome Data Browser (containing over 45000 human samples as of 2024) (Taing et al., 2023). Aggregating portals, like the International Human Epigenome Consortium (IHEC) Data Portal, provide access to thousands of reference datasets from over 600 distinct human tissues and cell lines (Bujold et al., 2016). These databases contain genome-wide maps for over a thousand transcription factors and dozens of key epigenetic modifications, such as various histone modifications and DNA methylation (Gershman et al., 2022; Grealley & Drake, 2017; Kundaje et al., 2015; R. Zheng et al., 2019) (Figure 57). The data is generated using multiple high-throughput sequencing modalities, primarily ChIP-seq (for protein binding), DNase-seq and ATAC-seq (for chromatin accessibility), and bisulfite sequencing (for DNA methylation). Co-mapping analysis of these whole genome tracks with REs according to the RetroSpect methodology would build the unambiguous picture of human regulatory evolution at tissue and organ-level resolution.

Figure 57. Histone post-translational modifications constitute the so-called histone code (adapted from (Beacon et al., 2021)). Each modification carries a specific functional role, although redundancies are common. Within the RetroSpect framework, these modifications can be investigated either jointly or in isolation. The four core histones undergo a wide spectrum of modifications, including acetylation (Ac), phosphorylation (P), lysine trimethylation (Me3), arginine symmetric and asymmetric dimethylation (Me2s and Me2a, respectively), ubiquitination (Ub), and poly-ADP ribosylation. The principal chromatin-modifying enzymes are lysine acetyltransferases (KAT), HDACs, protein arginine methyltransferases (PRMT), (KMT), mitogen- and stress-activated protein kinases (MSK), and protein phosphatases (PP). Essential metabolites for enzymatic activity, such as α -ketoglutarate (α -KG) and S-adenosylmethionine (SAM), are denoted by an asterisk. Enzymes whose catalytic activity is enhanced through interaction with a specific histone modification are indicated by a star.

A separate direction of this “widening” approach would be to apply the full RetroSpect pipeline to comparative epigenomic datasets from iPSCs and their differentiated derivatives,

such as cerebral or retinal organoids, from multiple primate species (e.g., human, chimpanzee, macaque). This would enable the direct identification of RE insertions that have become active, lineage-specific regulatory elements associated with human-specific patterns of gene expression within a controlled developmental context, providing direct insight into the evolution of the human regulome.

Integrating 3D chromatin architecture to uncover long-range regulation. Given that REs constitute more than 40% of the human genome and that the majority of these elements (>80%) are located outside the proximal promoter regions, it remains an open question whether these more distal REs contribute to regulatory evolution via alternative mechanisms - such as modulation of higher-order chromatin architecture or non-coding RNA-mediated regulation (Meller et al., 2015; Názer & Lei, 2014). The integration of chromatin 3D structure data (such as Hi-C contact maps (Gjoni et al., 2025)) with RE-linked epigenomic profiles can shed light on the relative importance of promoter-proximal and long-range chromatin interactions in regard to RE-linked regulatory elements function in human gene expression regulation. This approach is particularly relevant as primate-specific REs, such as Alu elements, are known to be enriched at the boundaries of TADs and within SEDs, suggesting they play a key architectural role (Dixon et al., 2012; Z. Gu et al., 2016; Wen & Zhong, 2023). Recent comparative Hi-C studies in primate lymphoblastoid cell lines have begun to map these species-specific interactions, revealing how changes in 3D genome organization may underlie regulatory evolution (García-Pérez et al., 2021).

Refined RE annotation and genome assemblies. Publicly available genome builds and annotations of RE coordinates and their taxonomy are quickly evolving for the recent decade. The complete human genome T2T assembly was released with the non-Y chromosomes in 2022, and the full sequence including the Y chromosome was completed in 2023 (Logsdon et al., 2021; Nurk et al., 2022; Rhie et al., 2023), leading to discovery of 1% more RE of the major classes: LINEs, SINEs and HERVs, as it was discussed before. Furthermore, the Human Pangenome Reference was released in 2023 containing 47 phased, diploid assemblies from a cohort of genetically diverse individuals to increase variant calling accuracy and account for population level structural variability, including RE insertions (Liao et al., 2023). Indeed, the single human genome reference, even the T2T one, inherently misses thousands of RE insertion polymorphisms (RIPs) and complex structural variants (SVs) that are not present in the reference sequence but are common across human

populations (Y. Lee et al., 2020; Taylor et al., 2024). Applying the RetroSpect framework to population-specific RE insertion maps generated from long-read data would facilitate the identification of very recent or ongoing retrotransposition events that have resulted in regulatory activity, directly linking current genomic plasticity to the evolution of human gene regulation and potentially uncovering novel associations with population-specific traits and diseases. These new assemblies and population genome references, being used as a reference for the RetroSpect methodology, could improve the accuracy of the evolutionary trends predictions derived in the current series of studies. Additionally, further refinement of the current results is possible using the novel RE annotation advances: for example, recent reannotation of human HERV elements allowed to find 4 new subfamilies of evolutionary young HERVs, correctly annotating 20% of them (Montserrat-Ayuso & Esteve-Codina, n.d.).

Resolving multimapping sequencing reads from epigenomic datasets. The current RetroSpect methodology relies on co-mapping of signal profiles in the bedGraph format to coordinates of genes and REs using bedtools (Nikitin, Sorokin, et al., 2019). Because RE families consist of thousands to over a million nearly identical copies, a short sequencing read originating from one RE instance often aligns with equal confidence to multiple genomic locations. Standard analytical pipelines typically discard these ambiguous multimapping reads to prevent false positives, but this results in a massive loss of data and a systematic underestimation of regulatory activity within the most abundant and evolutionarily dynamic repetitive regions of the genome, especially the younger families (Jin et al., 2015; Morrissey et al., 2024).

One major advance to face this challenge involves the use of probabilistic models, often based on an Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm, which reassigns multimapping reads to their most likely locus of origin based on the distribution of nearby uniquely mapped reads (Y. Zheng et al., 2019). For example, the recently developed IRescue and LocusMasterTE tools apply this principle to accurately quantify TE expression from single-cell and long-read RNA-seq data, respectively (S. Lee et al., 2025; Polimeni et al., 2024). Building on this, a state-of-the-art method called Allo combines probabilistic allocation with a convolutional neural network (CNN) trained to recognize the distinct "shape" of a true ChIP-seq signal peak (Morrissey et al., 2023). For each possible location of a multimapping read, Allo's CNN generates a score based on how much the surrounding unique reads

resemble a genuine peak; this score is then used to weight the probabilistic assignment, dramatically improving accuracy. These advanced computational approaches were proposed after the earlier methods that relied on realignment to consensus RE sequences (Teissandier et al., 2019), although comparison of their performance is yet to be done.

Machine learning models to predict RE regulatory potential. The current RetroSpect method is descriptive, identifying REs that are already associated with active epigenetic marks. It does not predict which of the millions of "silent" REs have the potential to become regulatory elements (Nikitin, Sorokin, et al., 2019). Future work could leverage machine learning and deep learning frameworks (e.g., Enformer, ChromBPNet) to build models that predict the regulatory potential of RE sequences (Chhibbar & Das, 2025; Pampari et al., 2025; Zeitlinger et al., 2025). By training a model on the DNA sequence and epigenetic features of functionally active REs identified by RetroSpect, the model could learn the sequence context (e.g., specific TF binding site syntax, local DNA shape (Inukai et al., 2017b; Samee, 2023)) that predisposes an RE to be co-opted. This predictive model could then be used to score the regulatory potential of all REs in the genome, including polymorphic and somatically acquired insertions.

3.7.2. The “deepening” future research directions.

High-resolution temporal mapping of RE co-option with refined evolutionary stratification. The current analytical approach is constrained by a notable limitation: its resolution along the evolutionary timescale is relatively coarse, being restricted here to two major divergence events - namely, the radiation of New World monkeys (<8% divergence of individual RE sequence from the consensus one (Giordano et al., 2007)) and the diversification of major eutherian clades. This limits the ability to link specific regulatory innovations to more precise evolutionary periods. Enhancing the temporal resolution of this framework by incorporating additional evolutionary benchmarks - tailored to each taxonomic group - would significantly improve its utility. Comparative studies focused on shared evolutionary horizons, such as the emergence of amniotes, could yield valuable insights into the molecular drivers of phenotypic macroevolution. Additionally, the conceptual framework of a "regulatory evolutionary clock" could be empirically tested by correlating RE regulatory load scores across multiple species with known divergence times.

Such a more granular, multi-tiered temporal stratification could be based on well-defined RE subfamilies (e.g., L1PA1-17, AluJ/S/Y subfamilies, SVA_A-F (Bennett et al., 2008; Boissinot & Furano, 2001)) instead of all human RE as it is studied here. For example, this could test whether the burst of L1PA8 to L1PA3 activity between 40 and 12 million years ago coincides with regulatory changes in specific metabolic or sensory pathways (Cardazzo et al., 2003; Khan et al., 2006). This approach would transform RetroSpect from a two-time point comparison into a more continuous model of regulatory evolution.

Functional validation of candidate RE-regulatory elements via CRISPR-based epigenome editing. As the discussed research shows, RetroSpect identifies strong correlations between RE-associated epigenetic marks and the regulatory status of genes and molecular pathways, but this does not necessarily establish a causal link. The functional role of high-confidence candidate RE-derived regulatory elements could be directly tested using CRISPR-based technologies (Devillars et al., 2024; Lau & Suh, 2018). CRISPR interference (CRISPRi), which uses a catalytically dead Cas9 (dCas9) fused to a repressive domain like KRAB, can be targeted to a specific RE-derived enhancer to epigenetically silence its activity (Klein et al., 2018; Korkmaz et al., 2016). Conversely, CRISPR activation (CRISPRa) can be used to activate it. The resulting change in the target gene's expression can then be precisely measured. In the recent preprint article this approach has been used to validate human-specific SVAs and LTR5Hs as enhancers driving gene expression programs essential for craniofacial development (Deelen et al., 2025). Applying this strategy to top candidates identified by RetroSpect would provide definitive experimental validation of their regulatory function.

High-resolution mapping of RE-derived promoters with CAGE and long-read transcriptomics. While histone marks like H3K4me3 are excellent proxies for promoter activity, they provide a relatively broad view of transcriptional initiation (Howe et al., 2017). Incorporating data from cap analysis of gene expression (CAGE), particularly from large consortia like FANTOM5, would significantly enhance the resolution of promoter analysis (Abugessaisa et al., 2017; Maeng et al., 2023). Intersecting CAGE-defined TSSs with RE annotations allows for the precise identification of which REs are functioning as alternative promoters. This can be further enhanced by long-read RNA sequencing (e.g., PacBio Iso-Seq) to capture full-length chimeric transcripts initiated from RE promoters, definitively linking the RE to the downstream gene structure (S. Lee et al., 2025; Maeng et al., 2023).

Dissecting the co-evolutionary arms race between KRAB-ZNFs and REs. The current RetroSpect framework identifies the downstream consequences of RE insertions but does not explicitly model the evolutionary conflict between REs and the host silencing machinery that precedes co-option (Nikitin, Sorokin, et al., 2019). To address this, a dedicated research program could focus on modeling the co-evolutionary arms race between REs and the rapidly expanding family of primate-specific KRAB-ZNFs (Bruno et al., 2019; Hamilton et al., 2006). By building bipartite networks of expression correlation between specific KRAB-ZNF genes and the RE families they are known to target, it is possible to trace the evolution of these repressive networks. This approach has already revealed a significant increase in network complexity in the human lineage, probably connected with increased brain size (Y.-C. Chen et al., 2025). The RetroSpect framework could then be used to determine if genes located near these "domesticated" REs are subsequently co-opted into novel, host-beneficial regulatory circuits controlled by the very KRAB-ZNFs that once silenced them. The same framework can be applied to other genome defence systems, such as RNAi and APOBEC machineries.

Single-cell multi-omic analysis to resolve cell-type-specific RE activity. The current analyses rely on bulk epigenomic data, which averages regulatory signals across millions of cells and can mask crucial regulatory differences between distinct cell types within a heterogeneous tissue (Philpott et al., 2020). The integration of single-cell multi-omic techniques, particularly paired single-cell ATAC-seq (scATAC-seq) and single-cell RNA-seq (scRNA-seq), offers a transformative approach (Clark et al., 2016; Wu et al., 2024). Applying the RetroSpect logic at the single-cell level would make it possible to directly link the chromatin accessibility of a specific RE-derived regulatory element to the expression of its target gene within a specific, well-defined cell type or developmental state. This would be particularly powerful for dissecting the role of REs in complex tissues like the brain or in dynamic processes like immune cell activation. Public databases with hundreds millions of cells from thousands of immune, nervous and other cell types are available (K. Chen et al., 2024; Y.-Y. Li et al., 2025; Program et al., 2025), which facilitate in silico analyses.

Systematic characterization of RE-derived non-coding RNAs. The RetroSpect framework focuses on REs as *cis*-regulatory DNA elements, but REs are also a major source of functional ncRNAs (Ganesh & Svoboda, 2016). A dedicated analysis pipeline could be developed to systematically identify and characterize lncRNAs and microRNAs that are

transcribed directly from RE sequences. By intersecting comprehensive ncRNA annotations with RE coordinates and expression data across tissues, it would be possible to build a catalog of RE-derived ncRNAs (L. Liu et al., 2025; W. Zhang et al., 2021). Functional studies using antisense oligonucleotides to knock down these ncRNAs could then elucidate their roles in regulating gene expression in *trans*, adding a new dimension to our understanding of RE impact. The primate-specific C19MC microRNA cluster, which originated from Alu elements and created a vast post-transcriptional regulatory network (Donker et al., 2012; Noguer-Dance et al., 2010; Shtam et al., 2018), serves as a compelling paradigm for this type of evolutionary innovation.

Investigating RE impact on post-transcriptional processing. The primary focus of the RetroSpect methodology has been on transcriptional regulation. However, REs, particularly inverted Alu pairs, are known to profoundly influence post-transcriptional events like alternative splicing and RNA editing (Ho et al., 2012; K. Lee et al., 2024). The RetroSpect framework could be adapted to analyze RNA-seq data specifically for RE-mediated effects on RNA processing. This would involve quantifying Alu exonization events and identifying adenosine-to-inosine (A-to-I) RNA editing hotspots within inverted Alu repeats (Daniel et al., 2014; K. Lee et al., 2024; S. Schwartz et al., 2009). Correlating the rates of these events with the epigenetic state of the underlying REs could reveal how chromatin context influences not just transcription, but the subsequent fate of the RNA transcript, a mechanism known to be highly active and specific to primates (Tzelepis et al., 2019).

Linking RE regulatory variation to human phenotypes and disease. The final and arguably the most promising direction is connected to the fact that while the RetroSpect analysis identifies pathways under accelerated evolution, it does not directly link specific RE-driven regulatory changes to organismal traits or disease risk. A powerful translational approach would be to integrate RetroSpect's outputs with data from genome-wide association studies (GWAS) (Uffelmann et al., 2021). By intersecting GWAS loci for human traits and diseases with the coordinates of RE-derived regulatory elements identified by RetroSpect, it may be possible to pinpoint the causal non-coding variants. This could provide a mechanistic explanation for numerous GWAS signals that currently reside in "gene deserts", implicating the co-option of a specific RE as the evolutionary event underlying a particular human phenotype or disease susceptibility. The known association of

an Alu insertion in the *TOMM40* gene with Alzheimer's disease risk provides a compelling precedent for this line of inquiry (Larsen et al., 2017).

These intriguing avenues can be the focus of forthcoming investigations that will shed light onto the dynamic nature of the human genome as the place of the continuous arms race between the parasites and the defense systems, giving rise to ever increasing forms of molecular and phenotypic complexity.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. REs are shown here as a predominant source of regulatory architecture in the human genome, contributing to 61.4% of TFBS in the promoter-proximal regions of genes across 13 diverse human cell lines and 17.1% in the single K563 cell line.
2. SINEs are the primary RE class co-opted for gene regulation, accounting for 33.2% of promoter-proximal RE-linked TFBS, whereas LINEs (13.3%) and HERVs (7.1%) are significantly depleted, reflecting strong selective pressure against their insertion near genes. This is especially true for evolutionarily young elements, where LINEs show a ~32-fold reduction in TFBS density compared to a ~9-fold reduction for SINEs.
3. Core housekeeping processes are evolutionarily conserved and insulated from RE-driven regulatory innovation. Pathways such as "ribosome assembly," "protein translation regulation" and "proteasomal degradation" are consistently deficient in RE-linked activating marks (e.g., H3K4me3, H3K27ac) and are instead enriched for RE-linked repressive marks (H3K27me3, H3K9me3).
4. Molecular pathways that mediate interaction with the environment show accelerated, RE-driven regulatory evolution. Processes including "amino acid metabolism" (e.g., aspartate, asparagine, lysine, diphthamide, carnitine, cysteine, proline metabolism), "lipid metabolism" (e.g., biosynthesis and desaturation of fatty acids, β -oxidation, phospholipase A2 activity), "xenobiotic detoxification" (e.g., CYP2E1-mediated reactions), and "sensory perception" (e.g., olfactory and visual signal transduction) are consistently enriched for RE-linked activating TFBS and histone marks.
5. REs have been a major driver for the evolution of post-transcriptional gene regulation, evidenced by the significant overrepresentation of microRNA ($p < 10^{-17}$)

and lncRNA ($p < 10^{-16}$) genes within gene sets most enriched by RE-linked TFBS. This is further supported by the identification of "gene silencing by microRNAs" as the most statistically significant RE-enriched biological process ($p < 10^{-9}$) for the H3K4me1 enhancer chromatin mark analysis.

6. The fundamental patterns of RE-mediated regulation are remarkably consistent across diverse human cell types. Pairwise comparisons of RE-linked regulatory scores across 13 cell lines of different tissue origins show a median Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.88 for both gene-level and pathway-level normalized metrics (NGRE and NP11).
7. RE-driven regulation at promoters and enhancers follows distinct evolutionary paths. Promoter-level regulation is highly conserved across cell types, with a core set of 92 genes showing consistent RE-enrichment in all five cell lines analyzed, whereas enhancer-level regulation is highly cell-type specific, with only three such genes being consistently regulated.
8. The regulatory potential of an RE is strongly correlated with its evolutionary age. Evolutionarily young REs ($\leq 8\%$ sequence divergence) exhibit a ~ 14 -fold lower density of RE-linked TFBS compared to the entire RE pool, indicating that newly inserted elements are transcriptionally silenced before potential co-option.
9. The immune system displays a modular evolutionary architecture shaped by REs. T and NK cell immune pathways, such as "naive CD8 T-cell signaling", are enriched in RE-linked TFBS and show signs of rapid evolution, while intracellular innate defenses like the "Toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4) cascade" are RE-deficient and evolutionarily conserved.
10. A consensus set of 92 genes consistently activated by RE-linked promoters across five cell lines is significantly enriched in pathways directly related to oncogenesis and viral response. These include "Small cell lung cancer" (12.6-fold enrichment), "Chronic myeloid leukemia" (11.4-fold), "Cell cycle" (9.2-fold), "Cellular senescence" (7.4-fold), and "Human T-cell leukemia virus 1 infection" (7.8-fold).

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